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Part 2, the current document, is the depository of the 40 in-depth cases, introducing and providing an analysis of the cases in the form of case summary reports.

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INTRODUCTION

This document provides a description of the methodology used to study the 40 energy citizenship cases selected for detailed study in EnergyPROSPECTS project, and then prepare the case summary reports. Furthermore, it includes the 40 individual case summary reports prepared based on this methodology.

EnergyPROSPECTS (PROactive Strategies and Policies for Energy Citizenship Transformation) works with a critical understanding of energy citizenship that is grounded in state-of-the-art social sciences and humanities (SSH) insights. The project aimed to develop a broad understanding of energy citizenship as a policy concept, a sociotechnical imaginary, and a knowing-of-governance – i.e., a social construction of desirable/normal civic agency in future energy systems. The project set out to identify and examine a range of crosscutting issues in energy citizenship, which informed the iterative typology development and criteria for case selection. Drawing on pre-existing databases and a search for new cases, 596 energy citizenship initiatives were mapped, and typology refinement exercises were undertaken that demonstrated the depth/breadth of the energy citizenship concept in theory and practice. The project is implemented between May 2021 and April 2024.

1. WHAT IS ENERGY CITIZENSHIP, AND HOW IS A CASE OF ENERGY CITIZENSHIP DEFINED?

As part of the energy citizenship mapping exercise, methodology was developed for pursuing the overall project aim of identifying the diversity of types and empirical manifestations of energy citizenship. The methodology was created to help answer the main research questions the EnergyPROSPECTS project team intends to respond to by undertaking the mapping activity, which are as follows:

1. Which forms of energy citizenship (henceforth referred to as ENCI) can be found in Europe today? How can we account for their diversity?
2. Do we find the same forms in different regions/countries of Europe?
3. In what contexts do different forms of ENCI emerge and develop?

For the **definition of energy citizenship**, we turn to the conceptual framework of the EnergyPROSPECTS project presented by [Pel et al. \(2021\)](#):

Energy citizenship refers to forms of civic involvement that pertain to the development of a more sustainable and democratic energy system. Beyond its manifest forms, ENCI also comprises various latent forms: it is an ideal that can be lived up to and realised to varying degrees according to different framework conditions and states of empowerment. (Pel et al., 2021:64)

Building on this definition of energy citizenship, a case of ENCI in the EnergyPROSPECTS project is understood as...

1. a constellation of actors (in a context) and how it enables/supports citizens to become active private and/or public energy citizens; acts as a collective energy citizen by contributing to change in the energy system or,
2. including individual energy citizens and how they realise their potential in a private, public or organisational setting.

As indicated by these definitions and underlined by the agency dimension of the conceptual typology presented in [Debourdeau et al. \(2021\)](#), a case can be centred around an individual or realised in a multitude of collective forms. During the mapping of the ENCI landscape, the focus was on collecting data about both types of cases.

Furthermore, as [Pel et al. \(2021\)](#) indicate, we also recognise that even within the boundaries defined for ENCI mapping in EnergyPROPECTS, "enabling" and "supporting" citizens to become active private and/or public energy citizens can take many different forms. Similarly, energy citizenship itself can have many different forms. In reality, many types of cases can enable or support several different forms of energy citizenship in parallel – often less as well as more active forms may be associated with the same case (e.g., citizens voluntarily organising carbon reduction groups as a more *active* form of citizenship, and citizens participating in these groups as a *less active* form).

As a result, a very diverse collection of ENCI cases emerged as an output of the mapping process ([Debourdeau et al., 2023](#)).¹ Indeed, it is important to note that although the term “energy citizenship” is often associated with energy communities or community energy projects, the objective of the EnergyPROSPECTS project has been to uncover other forms of energy citizenship as well.

Disclaimer about this document

When reading the case summary reports, please bear in mind the following:

- The assignment of the cases into the various categories (cf. in the spider chart) in our analysis is not intended to reflect a value judgement but rather to indicate their diversity. All types of cases are needed for the sustainable energy transition.
- Since providing details on the conceptual and methodological underpinning of the work presented here would go beyond the scope of this document, the process is only summarised here. Details are available in other project deliverables, especially in:
 1. methodology for ENCI mapping and data collection: [Vadovics et al., 2022a](#)
 2. conceptual framework and defining energy citizenship: [Pel et al., 2021](#)
 3. conceptual typology: [Debourdeau et al., 2021](#)
 4. catalogue of energy citizenship cases and typologies: [Debourdeau et al., 2023](#)
 5. selection of cases for detailed study and main research topics and questions: [Pel et al., 2022](#)
 6. methodology for detailed case collection: [Vadovics et al., 2022b](#)

¹ Information about the 596 cases of ENCI that were mapped has been made available in various ways:

- in an online database, available at data.energyprospects.eu/;
- in a [public deliverable according to their ideal-type](#) (Debourdeau et al., 2023)
- in a descriptive analysis of the data associated with the cases mapped in the Energy Citizenship Factsheet Series, available at www.energyprospects.eu/results/energy-citizenship-factsheets/,
- in the form of country profile reports, available at <https://www.energyprospects.eu/results/country-profiles/>.

OVERVIEW OF THE DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS PROCESS

The data collection process can be summarised as follows:

1. THE METHODOLOGY USED FOR MAPPING ENERGY CITIZENSHIP

The data this document builds on come from the ENCI mapping process that the EnergyPROSPECTS consortium completed between November 2020 and May 2021. The methodology for the desk-based mapping is described in detail in [Vadovics et al. \(2022a\)](#); here, we provide a very brief summary.

The objective of the mapping process was to capture the diversity of ENCI in Europe rather than to map each and every ENCI that exists. The definition of ENCI that was adopted in the project is intentionally broad (see [Pel et al., 2021](#)) to ensure that as many cases of ENCI as possible, including latent forms, were incorporated. Since a huge variety of cases and initiatives exist that would fit our definition, and mapping all of them would be beyond the scope and resources of the project, there was a need to further define which cases should be included within the research focus of the EnergyPROSPECTS project. The consortium decided that the ENCI mapping activity would cover cases that:

- are **based in European countries** (including EU, EEA and accession countries);
- are **currently active or were concluded no earlier than 2015** when the Energy Union Strategy was published;
- are **focused on direct energy production and/or consumption** (e.g., involving households, organisations, etc.), **mobility** (with a direct connection to energy issues), or have a **more holistic focus on sustainable and just energy**.

Furthermore, to ensure that the greatest diversity of ENCI was captured according to this scope, a sampling strategy that specified five categories of diversity that should be covered was developed. The latter included:

1. Geographical diversity;
 2. Diversity in terms of the main focus of the cases (i.e., covering direct energy production/consumption, mobility and holistic cases);
 3. Diversity in terms of mapping both individual and collective cases of ENCI;
 4. Diversity associated with the ideal's types described in the conceptual typology;
- and finally,

5. Diversity in terms of cases of ENCI that include a variety of additional foci (such as gender, disadvantaged groups, low-tech/high-tech/behaviour change-based solutions, and rural/urban settings).

With this methodological guidance, the ENCI mapping process resulted in the mapping of 596 cases² ([Debourdeau et al., 2023](#)). The country-level distribution of mapped cases is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Country-level distribution of mapped ENCI cases

² An interactive online database of all cases can be found at <https://data.energyprospects.eu/>

2. SELECTION OF THE 40 CASES FOR DETAILED STUDY

The cases for detailed study were selected from the 596 cases identified and studied at the empirical mapping stage. These cases (n=40) constitute less than 10% of the whole database and were selected using a very detailed and specific methodology to ensure they were suitable for further research on energy citizenship related to various topics, including intermediation ([Markantoni et al., 2023](#)), social innovation and business models ([Debourdeau and Markantoni, 2023](#)), transformative agency ([Kemp et al., 2023](#)), and very importantly, as part of a QCA (qualitative comparative analysis) ([Schmid et al., 2023](#)). Thus, it is important to bear in mind that **they are not representative of energy citizenship in any way**. They are simply a diverse selection of cases the EnergyPROSPECTS research team chose for detailed study.

The methodology for selecting the cases is detailed elsewhere (see [Pel et al., 2022](#)). However, to summarise, the set of 40 cases was chosen through a three-step process primarily designed to support the systematic comparison of (greater and lesser) achievements and conditioning factors of energy citizenship. The steps were as follows:

Step 1: Pre-selection of cases: suitable cases were filtered out from the database of 596 cases with the use of the following criteria:

- nomination by a partner for further study;
- location in a partner country to ensure ease of access to information and interview subjects as well as relevance to other project tasks;
- data availability: sufficient amount of information about the case potentially available, and/or the partner in question is already in contact with the case.

Additionally, since we planned to analyse 20 of the selected cases through QCA methodology, additional filters were applied:

- typologisation as ENCI ideal-types 7 and 8³ (categorisation as “citizen-based and hybrid” during the mapping stage);

³ See [Debourdeau et al., 2022](#) for details on the ideal types of energy citizenship.

- diversity in evaluation as “high”, “medium”, or “low” (but not “n/a”, etc.) regarding ‘achievements’ related to citizen power during the mapping stage;
- currently active cases that started operating and engaging in activities no later than 2020.

Step 2: Selection by case researchers: Following the filtering process, the list of suitable cases was presented to project partners along with instructions to select the most appropriate cases for study in their countries, considering factors such as the accessibility of the case (e.g., in relation to conducting interviews), diversity among cases, relevance to research objectives, etc.

Step 3: Verification: once partners had made their selection of cases, members of the research topics lead team completed a final review.

The map in Figure 2 summarises the final number of cases by partner country, while Annex I includes a list of all cases of energy citizenship that were studied, organised by country.

Figure 2: Number of cases selected for detailed study in each of the project partner countries

3. METHODS USED FOR STUDYING THE 40 CASES

A survey questionnaire with the research questions was collaboratively developed by the various research topic leads (see [Pel et al., 2022](#) and [Vadovics et al., 2022b](#) for a description of the main research topics, questions, and the final research questionnaire). The 40 cases were studied using a mixed-methods approach consisting of document research and case participant interviews, with the following research steps proposed to case researchers:

Step 1: Review case data about the case from the mapping stage of the research. This material already included references and links to additional materials.

Step 2: Further document research on selected cases (e.g., the website of the case, founding document(s), other programmatic materials, evaluation reports, annual reports, research reports, media articles, academic papers, etc.).

Step 3: Based on already available information and document research, fill in as much information as possible in the survey questionnaire while identifying pertinent questions for case actor interviews.

Step 4: Conduct interviews with case actors to fill in the missing information as well as expand on and verify what was learned through the documents.

Step 5: Review data and information and submit case information to the research team through the online version of the research survey questionnaire.

In order to standardise the research approach as much as possible, all case researchers were invited to an online training session prior to the case research ([Vadovics et al., 2022b](#)). Furthermore, due to the complexity of the research approach due to the many research topics being covered, case researchers were invited to participate in five check-in meetings during the detailed case study process. These were organised to focus on the main research topics and increase alignment and understanding of the research concepts, framings, and methods.

Data collection took place between August 2022 and May 2023.

4. THE CASE SUMMARY REPORTS

In the case summary reports, our objective was to summarise and present the most important information about the 40 cases in relation to how they contribute to the sustainable energy transition. Thus, in these short reports, not all information that was collected is presented. At the same time, our intention was to present the cases using a framework built on the main conceptual elements of the EnergyPROSPECTS research, partly in the hope of translating and introducing them to a wider audience. These are as follows:

- the specific and highly inclusive framing of energy citizenship we adopted (as summarised in the introduction to this document and in detail in [Pel et al., 2021](#));
- the conceptual typology of ideal types of energy citizenship we developed (see more in section 4.2 below and in detail in [Debourdeau et al., 2021](#) and [2023](#)); and
- the main aspects of energy citizenship that characterise the reformative and transformative dimension of the conceptual typology (see section 4.3).

Furthermore, the case reports are intended for a more general audience, including all stakeholders working in or with energy citizenship, such as CSOs, policymakers, smaller and larger businesses, social enterprises, people involved in or interested in getting involved in energy citizenship cases, the media, etc. in addition to academics and experts.

Finally, to facilitate comparison between cases and provide an accessible overview, the case summary reports follow the same structure and format as introduced in the sections below.

4.1. CASE DESCRIPTION, MAIN CHARACTERISTICS, WHY A CASE IS AN ENCI AND GOALS

In the first part of the report, partly building on the mapping stage of data collection, we present

- a short summary of the case;
- followed by an explanation of why the EnergyPROSPECTS research team believes the case is a good example of energy citizenship (ENCI) and
- we then introduce, in the form of a list, the main goals of the case.

In addition, using icons, we provide information as to how the case was categorised in the project concerning

- its main focus;
- whether it is an individual or collective case; and
- what its main area of operation is.

As for the focus, in EnergyPROSPECTS, we decided to focus on collecting cases with three main foci:

Direct energy consumption and/or production	Mobility	Holistic
HOLISTIC		

As mentioned in the introductory chapter on defining energy citizenship, we felt it necessary to collect both individual and collective cases. In the case reports, these are identified by the following icons:

Individual	Collective
COLLECTIVE	

Finally, we used icons to define where the case operates, including in the countryside, periurban, or urban area. If a case is not associated with a specific area of operation (e.g., if it is virtual or its operations are not targeted at a particular area), no symbol is used in the case report.

Urban	Periurban	Rural
RURAL		

4.2. CASE HISTORIES AND TYPOLOGY

Following the introduction and basic characterisation of the case, we present its “story”, or in other words, developmental history, focusing on changes in the energy citizenship typology characteristic of the various developmental phases of the case as well as the major changes in the case concerning its main form of operation, widening or narrowing of focus, etc., that do not necessarily correspond to a change in the typology.

In this part, we first present a summary of the development or evolution of a case together with a figure representing the process (see example in Figure 3). In the figure, we identify the main developmental phases (indicated by the arrows) and the corresponding main (**in colour**) and secondary (**in grey**) energy citizenship ideal type(s) characteristic of the case in each phase of its development. The icons in the figure refer to the main typology dimensions of the ideal types (the first icon refers to the outcome orientation dimension, and the second the agency, as summarised in Tables 1 and 2 below).

Figure 3: Example of a case history figure

Table 1 provides an overview of the ideal energy citizenship types the EnergyPROSPECTS team identified, and Table 2 shows how this typology is depicted in a simplified form in the case summary reports. For a more detailed description of the conceptualisation of the typology, please refer to [Debourdeau et al. \(2021\)](#), and for an elaboration of the typology following the mapping stage of the research, please see [Debourdeau et al. \(2023\)](#).

Table 1: The EnergyPROSPECTS typology (source: Debourdeau et al., 2021)

AGENCY		INDIVIDUAL			COLLECTIVE	
OUTCOME ORIENTATION	PRIVATE (HOUSEHOLD)	ORGANISATIONALLY EMBEDDED (E.G., WORKPLACE)	PUBLIC	CITIZEN-BASED AND HYBRID	SOCIAL MOVEMENTS	
REFORMATIVE 	1. DO THEIR BIT (in the household) Complying with the green energy transition	3. DO THEIR BIT (within organisations) Energy citizenship within organisations	5. MAKE THEIR VOICE HEARD Participating in societal energy discussions	7. DO THEIR SHARE Joining green energy projects	9. DO THE JOB Facilitating the energy transition through alignment activities	
TRANSFORMATIVE 	2. DO THEIR OWN (in the household) The change-making energy citizen	4. DO IT THEIR WAY (within organisations) The energy-related change maker in organisations	6. MAKE THEIR VOTE COUNT Mobilising votes for energy transition	8. GO AHEAD Building, expanding and linking citizen-based organisational forms	10. MAKE THEIR CLAIM Protesting against the current energy system	

Table 2: Typology table used in the case summary reports

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organisations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organisations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

In the typology tables included in the case reports, the main type of energy citizenship case typology is indicated by **coloured highlighting**, while secondary citizenship types are marked using **bold** characters and icons. As highlighted in the introduction, cases of energy citizenship often enable several types of energy citizenship in parallel. In agreement with the case researcher team, we identified one main form or type of energy citizenship for each case and then, if relevant, indicated one or more secondary types also supported by the case. For example, citizens voluntarily organising carbon reduction groups as a *collective and more active* form of citizenship, citizens participating in

these groups as a *less active* form, and the same citizens also undertaking various climate and energy-related activities in their homes (e.g., installing solar panels, reducing indoor temperature, etc.) as a result of being part of the group as *individual forms* of citizenship.

In the typology tables, we also indicated changes in the main and secondary energy citizenship types by using arrows: **coloured arrows** for change in the main type and **grey** arrows for change in the secondary types.

4.3. ASPECTS OF ENERGY CITIZENSHIP: THE SPIDER CHARTS

In the last content-focused part of the case summaries, we present the main aspects of energy citizenship related to contesting the current energy system and contributing to the transition to a more sustainable one. In our research, we placed special emphasis on studying three aspects in particular that are related to social sustainability⁴:

- How does the case contribute to the democratisation of the energy system? Is it one of the objectives, and if so, how important an objective is it?

- Does the case exhibit strong elements of effective citizen control?
- How important are the goals of equity and justice to the case? To what extent are they pursued?

We also wanted to identify aspects related to environmental sustainability, in particular:

- How important are the goals of environmental sustainability to the case? To what extent are they pursued?

- How important are goals related to meeting the maximum 1.5 °C target of the Paris Agreement and observing the carbon limit to the case? To what extent are they pursued?

⁴ You can find more background information on the conceptualisation of these aspects in Debourdeau et al., 2021.

Each of these five aspects was evaluated by case researchers on a numerical scale (see Annex II), followed by a more detailed explanation of how exactly the case approaches each of them. These are summarised in the spider charts for each case, next to the individual figures.

To describe the equity/justice aspect, we also used icons to indicate a specific focus on disadvantaged groups and/or gender-related issues.

It should be noted that in addition to these five aspects selected for inclusion in the case summary reports, we studied others related to both social and environmental sustainability – please refer to [Pel et al. \(2022\)](#) and [Vadovics et al. \(2022b\)](#) for details and [Vadovics and Szöllőssy \(2024\)](#) for a more detailed analysis of these aspects.

4.4. CONTACT INFORMATION AND REFERENCES

At the end of each case summary report, we provide details of where more information about the case can be found and how the representatives of the case can be contacted. We also provide a list of references for the data and information included in each report. We finish by listing all the researchers and reviewers involved in the preparation of the case reports.

4.5. REVIEW PROCESS FOR CASE SUMMARY REPORTS

Case summary reports were prepared by members of the research team at GreenDependent Institute based on information gathered by case researchers. Once the draft reports were ready, they were reviewed by case researchers. Following the review, cases were modified as necessary and proofread and edited. In the final stage, where

possible, they were also shared with case owners, and case participants were invited to share comments and raise any concerns about factual mistakes or if something about the case had been misrepresented. Following this final review stage, cases were finalised and published.

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ANNEX I: LIST OF THE 40 CASES STUDIED IN DETAIL

Case no.	Title of case in English	Country	Main focus
			As in mapping survey: Energy (i.e. Direct energy production and/or consumption) Mobility Holistic
1	Hydro Electricity Ourthe and Sambre (HOSe)	BE	Energy
2	Extinction Rebellion Etterbeek	BE	Holistic
3	BBL's Home renovation project	BE	Energy
4	Energy Efficiency Mission ULB	BE	Energy
5	Bike Evolution	BG	Mobility
6	Energy Transition of City of Burgas: Going Smart and Sustainable	BG	Holistic
7	Student Switch Off campaigns in Bulgaria	BG	Energy
8	Student Energy Teams	BG	Energy
9	Solocal Energy	DE	Holistic
10	LAVIDAVERDE	DE	Holistic
11	Berlin Citizen Energy (BEB)	DE	Energy
12	NATURSTROM AG	DE	Energy
13	Tregor Energ'ethic	FR	Energy
14	Energie Partagée	FR	Energy
15	Railcoop	FR	Mobility
16	Hauts de France Pass Renovation	FR	Energy
17	Biobriquettes for the energy poor	HU	Energy
18	Nagypáli, the renewable energy village	HU	Holistic
19	TreeDependent	HU	Holistic
20	Zsuzsanna Hojtsy-Keresztény - EnergyNeighbourhoods energy master, local change maker	HU	Holistic
21	Cargonoma	HU	Holistic
22	From the Community Energy Programme to Community Energy Service	HU	Energy
23	Energy Community Tipperary Cooperative ECTC	IE	Energy
24	Aran Islands Energy Cooperative	IE	Holistic
25	Galway Energy Co-operative	IE	Energy
26	Citizens' Assembly on "How the state can make Ireland a leader in tackling climate change"	IE	Holistic
27	Public Consultation: Shaping Our Electricity Future	IE	Energy
28	Installation of solar heat panels in multi-apartment buildings, with energy efficiency improvement of the building	LV	Energy
29	Association "city for people"	LV	Mobility
30	OFF-GRID: Renewable energy DIY (do it yourself) for rural development	LV	Energy
31	Social media influencer Edgar Fresh	LV	Holistic
32	Weert Energy	NL	Energy
33	Reindonk Energy & Co: Energy from your own region	NL	Energy
34	The Drechtsteden cooperative	NL	Energy
35	Loenen Energy	NL	Energy
36	National Association of Active Residents - Landelijk Samenwerkingsverband Actieve bewoners (LSA)	NL	Holistic
37	GoEner	ES	Energy
38	Couso's Project	ES	holistic
39	La Borda. Housing cooperative in transfer of use	ES	Holistic
40	SomEnergia	ES	Energy

ANNEX II: CATEGORIES USED TO DESCRIBE THE MAIN SUSTAINABILITY ASPECTS OF THE CASES

1. Democratic energy future

Do/did the actors envision and pursue a more democratic energy future?

Shortened, used in case summary reports	Full description used in the case study survey questionnaire
Energy democracy has not been among the goals	1. Not a goal: energy democracy has not been among the aims of the case.
Energy democracy is considered as a positive value, but the vision does not really address it	2. It is not so important: energy democracy is considered a positive value as such, yet the case activities and visions do not really address issues related to energy democracy (whether in terms of democratic participation, inclusive, deliberative and transparent decision-making processes, compulsory and effective decisions).
Energy democracy is considered a positive value, but it remains limited to formal energy democracy	3. It is important but limited to formal issues: energy democracy is considered a positive value that the case intends to support by increasing the democratic participation of citizens and improving inclusiveness. Yet, the democratic energy future envisioned remains limited to formal energy democracy (democratic procedures or declarations regarding energy justice).
A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case and is part of the vision	4. It is a core concern: a more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case and parts of its vision. The case aims to promote an effective democratisation of the energy system by putting it in citizens' hands and intends to implement concrete actions to improve access and inclusivity to self-governance.

2. Equity and justice

In terms of equity and justice, please indicate the level of equity/justice pursued, as they are defined in Debourdeau et al., 2021 (pg. 31.):

Shortened, used in case summary reports	Full description used in the case study survey questionnaire
Equity and justice issues are not relevant/not addressed by goals	1. Equity and justice issues are not relevant to this case in the sense that they are not addressed by case goals or activities.
Justice or equity are essentially out of scope or restricted to access to market	2. Justice or equity are essentially out of scope or restricted to equal access to markets
Equal access is granted but limited by various criteria	3. Equal access is granted to all concerned citizens, but the framings tend to limit them to a particular geographical area or amount of financial contribution, which does not guarantee "real" equity.
Involvement is fully open	4. Involvement is fully open, without specific belonging conditions. Issues such as energy poverty, gender and inclusivity are taken into account and foster adaptive measures to guarantee more equity.

3. Citizen power/control

Does (did) the case exhibit strong elements of effective citizen control?

Shortened, used in case summary reports	Full description used in the case study survey questionnaire
No effective citizen power/control	1. No effective voice citizen power/control
Citizens' voices remain hardly heard or taken into account	2. Low level: when expressed (e.g., within "invited" deliberative processes), citizens' voices remain hardly heard or taken into account. Being a minority, citizens' voices do not really count, or in a voting process, the framings tend to limit the possibility of expressing an opinion.
Citizens can express their views, but their views are not necessarily taken into account	3. Medium level: citizens can express their views, but their voices are not compulsory (within deliberative, representative or consultative processes). Within organised / participative structures, citizens remain a minority group, i.e., unable to impose their views on other groups.
Citizens exert effective control, and their votes have to be taken into account	4. High level: citizens exert effective control, and their votes are mandatory. This governance takes place mainly in an "invented" process (as opposed to "invited" ones by Radtke et al., 2020). Citizens represent a majority group, empowered enough to control the process and thus make their voices predominant.

4. Environmental sustainability

In terms of environmental sustainability, please indicate the importance thereof based on the definition of various levels of environmental sustainability in Debourdeau et al., 2021 (pg. 31.):

Shortened, used in case summary reports	Full description used in the case study survey questionnaire
Environmental sustainability issues are not relevant/not addressed by goals	1. Environmental sustainability issues are not relevant to this case in the sense that they are not addressed by case goals or related activities.
Environmental sustainability issues are not explicitly taken into account	2. Environmental sustainability issues are mostly seen as self-evident and not explicitly taken into account. In the lowest forms, environmental sustainability tends to be dealt with as a positive or negative externality.
Environmental sustainability is part of the process; energy remains the main focus	3. Environmental sustainability is part of the process or case, but this concern is addressed in a superficial (non-radical) way (focus on efficiency strategies) and without dedicated assessment. Energy remains the main focus.
Environmental sustainability is a core issue and is considered in goal-setting	4. Environmental sustainability is a core issue, and it is even considered in goal setting, which is followed with a holistic strategy (mix of efficiency, consistency and sufficiency measures). Its assessment through indicators is seen as desirable.

5. Carbon limit

Does the case recognise environmental limits and openly talk about a sustainable carbon footprint that is necessary to reach the 1.5 °C target?

Shortened, used in case summary reports	Full description used in the case study survey questionnaire
There is no recognition or mention of the carbon limit related to the case goals	1. Related to the case concerning case goals and activities, there is no recognition or mention of the ecological limit of atmospheric carbon emissions and/or reaching the sustainable carbon footprint.
Implicit recognition of the carbon limit	2. Implicit recognition: there is no explicit mention of the ecological limit of atmospheric carbon emissions and/or sustainable carbon footprint. But despite the lack of formal references to either of them, the case is involved in activities to reduce carbon consumption and/or emission.
Explicit recognition of the carbon limit	3. Explicit recognition: the ecological limit of atmospheric carbon emissions and/or sustainable carbon footprint is mentioned in core case documents, and the actors involved in the case are clearly engaged in attempts to reduce consumption and/or emission of carbon.
Explicit recognition with mention/objective of reaching the max. carbon footprint	4. Explicit recognition with mention/objective of reaching the max. carbon footprint: in addition to mentioning the ecological limit of atmospheric carbon emissions and/or sustainable carbon footprint, the maximum sustainable carbon footprint and/or emissions are also defined.

THE 40 CASE SUMMARY REPORTS

CLUSTER 1 CASES:

Name of case in English:	Country
Extinction Rebellion Etterbeek	BE
LaVidaVerde	DE
SoLocal Energy	DE
GoiEner Taldea	ES
Railcoop	FR
Shared Energy	FR
Cargonoma	HU
From the Community Energy Programme to Community Energy Service	HU
TreeDependent	HU
Aran Islands Energy Cooperative	IE
Citizens' Assembly on 'How the State can make Ireland a Leader in tackling Climate Change'	IE

Extinction Rebellion Etterbeek

Summary

XR Belgium, of which XR Etterbeek forms a part, is the Belgian branch of Extinction Rebellion, a global network that uses non-violent direct action to try to force governments to act on the climate and ecological emergency. Its development over time involved a fairly quick rise, followed by a degree of decline soon after (due to the COVID-19 epidemic) and a shift towards localisation, i.e. smaller-scale action. XR did not become a mass movement in Belgium with significant political-social impact. It did develop a specific organisational structure and collective identity, and many individuals were trained and empowered to stand up when the time comes.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

Although Extinction Rebellion is a global network, a closer look at the national/local "branches" shows that their demands and framings can differ. Regarding Extinction Rebellion Belgium specifically, one of their three main demands is *"that the Government enacts a comprehensive, legally-binding National Emergency Plan which phases out the extraction and import of fossil fuels by 2025"*.

HOLISTIC

COLLECTIVE

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Goals

1. Having a state of climate and environmental urgency declared in Belgium;
2. Developing a mass civil disobedience movement;
3. Raising public awareness about climate urgency and the environmental crisis.

The story and the typology

XR Etterbeek is a local group within the Extinction Rebellion Belgium movement. It has remained quite stable in terms of aims, principles, and narratives since its start in 2019. Thus, throughout its history, the type of energy citizenship enabled by this case has remained unchanged. As XR is a social movement with essentially transformative goals that fundamentally contest the current energy system, the ideal type of energy citizenship is also reflected in this, it being a social movement with transformative outcome orientation (Type 10).

Case history summary

For the summary
methodology,
click [HERE!](#)

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Phase 1: Rise of XR in 2018-2020

The XR movement had a tremendous impact when it started in the UK in 2018. XR Belgium and its local groups, such as XR Etterbeek, joined the movement early on (XR Belgium in 2018, XR Etterbeek in 2019) and made use of the formats and structures developed by XR UK.

The rise of XR attracted many activists, who saw an opportunity to make – collectively and under an inspiring, internationally recognised banner – a bigger impact. Many XR members were engaging in environmentally conscious behaviours before joining the movement, but the movement allowed them to make them more visible and join forces with like-minded people.

Creating XR was an initiative that appeared to have the potential to spur collective change. Thus, the ideal energy citizenship type of XR Etterbeek is defined as a transformative social movement (Type

10). Moreover, as many activists continued with their individual energy citizenship practices, inspiring and learning from others in the movement, household-level individual agency is also supported by the case as a secondary energy citizenship type.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Make their claims

Transformative outcome / Social movements agency

Secondary type: Do their own (in the household)

Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Phase 2: COVID-19-related disintegration, 2021-2022

The COVID pandemic and associated limitations on public gatherings hit this energy citizenship initiative particularly hard. The latter involved quite a strong blow for the just emerging XR Belgium (including the organisation in Etterbeek), and it may now have lost the momentum to become a mass movement with a major political-societal impact. However, a specific organisational structure and collective identity have been developed, and many individuals have been trained and empowered to stand up when the time comes.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Make their claims

Transformative outcome / Social movements agency

Secondary type: Do their own (in the household)

Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Phase 3: Localised action, 2022 -

The objective of creating a mass movement with significant national-level events/actions has been forestalled and partly abandoned. However, action at the local level continues, still guided by essentially the same principles, aims, methods and objectives, albeit with a somewhat reduced focus and localised targets proportional to the smaller-scale activities (e.g., organising XR cafés to introduce people to the movement, the activists and the issues).

Some of the ambitions of creating a mass civil disobedience movement were fulfilled by the case joining Code Rouge,¹ a coalition of social movements. This coalition involves addressing

broader societal struggles beyond environmental issues, such as socioeconomic inequality and gender disparity.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Make their claims

Transformative outcome / Social movements agency

Secondary type: Do their own (in the household)

Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

¹ Code Red is a civil disobedience movement created by activists and supported by different organisations and action groups who are working on environmental issues.

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The aspects of energy citizenship

One of the core demands of XR Belgium is that **a Citizen's Assembly is installed, with the means and the executive power to ensure decisive action** (to steer society away from climate crisis). "A Citizens' Assembly, equipping our regions and communities with the resources and the authority to ensure a managed transition to an equitable post-growth society".

XR challenges representative democracy regarding its incapacity to act on the climate/environmental crisis. In doing so, XR is also very strongly committed to alternative modes of (horizontal; inclusive) decision-making and direct democracy (they demand the establishment of a Citizens' Assembly with extensive executive power). **XR is strongly committed to effective citizen control, and to the fundamental democratisation of society.** Their internal decision-making is in line with these principles/objectives.

Democratic energy future

A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

Citizen control

Citizens exert effective control, and their votes have to be taken into account

FOCUS ON GENDER ISSUES

The XR Belgium website includes several principles that **underline the organization's commitment to radically democratic, inclusive governance that actively redresses power imbalances.** Notable examples are the following principles: "We welcome everyone and every part of everyone working actively to create safer and more accessible spaces. We actively mitigate [campaign] for breaking down hierarchies of power for more equitable participation."

Equity and justice

Involvement is fully open

The distinctive feature of XR is the narrative about climate urgency and the associated necessity of taking decisive action to address this issue. **The activities of XR typically address environmentally unsustainable practices and laws that exemplify how current environmental policies are insufficient or too permissive of environmentally damaging practices.** Environmental sustainability is a core issue; for example, this is clear from their activities against the 'Salon d'Auto' (which glorifies cars and car culture), a convention for private jets, fast food and the associated animal exploitation, and the production/export of pesticides.

Environmental sustainability

Environmental sustainability is a core issue, and is considered in goal setting

Carbon limit

Explicit recognition with mention/objective of reaching the max. carbon footprint

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Further information

facebook.com/extinctionrebellionbe
facebook.com/p/Extinction-Rebellion-Etterbeek-100063482893847

www.extinctionrebellion.be/en/
www.extinctionrebellion.be/en/local-groups/etterbeek

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LaVidaVerde

GERMANY

HOLISTIC

COLLECTIVE

URBAN

Summary

With the LaVidaVerde project, a diverse assemblage of people is realising their jointly developed idea of future-oriented living in Berlin's Weitlingkiez, thought to be an answer to current ecological and social challenges in the form of a residential project. LaVidaVerde is an energy-plus building¹ for a colourful group of committed young and older people who have consciously decided to engage in a project that enables communal living as well as resource-saving life and political work in and for the neighbourhood. The activity of the community is not limited to living together in the house but is also visible in the realisation of common goals.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

It is a case of energy citizenship since it consists of a communal and participative housing project aimed at building a plus-energy house. In addition to the sustainable energy aspects, it promotes sustainable community housing and living at the "Kiez" scale.²

¹An energy-plus building (also called a plus-energy house or efficiency-plus house) produces more energy from renewable energy sources over the course of a year than it imports from external sources.

²A "Kiez" is never originally defined by the municipality or government but rather by the inhabitants and, therefore, does not necessarily coincide with administrative divisions. [...] In Berlin, the term usually has a positive connotation, as inhabitants often identify with the "Kiez" they live in. There has been an increase in the number of approximately 20 unofficial "Kiez"-areas in Berlin, most often in and around the city centre. (Source: Wikipedia)

Goals

1. Creating a self-governed, solidarity- and sustainability-oriented housing project that enables resource-saving lifestyles;
2. Ensuring that the land the communal house stands on, as well as the house, is not subject to real estate speculation;
3. Creating the first German multi-generational and plus-energy house in an inner-city location, thus setting an example for the public.

“We see ourselves as a lighthouse project that wants to make its solutions to technical and organisational questions accessible to a broad public. We want to directly impact our living environment and make community spaces available for shared use by neighbourhood groups.”

The story and the typology

The case started in 2008-2009 by two families deciding to create a more sustainable, just and ecologically sound communal living space. They gradually assembled a larger group with the same interest and created the infrastructural conditions for building their home. This process meant that their transformative, individual agency became organisationally embedded and collective in its main focus.

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

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Phase 1: Setting up the case, 2008-2020

In 2008, two families initiated a shared, communal housing project, constituting the very first members and founders. They began by contacting a planner and an architect and progressively assembled a group of 10 people who became the core of the project. Thus, the initial main agency was manifested in private individuals in the household, with a transformative outcome orientation.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their own (in the household)

Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Phase 2: Creation of organisational background, acquiring land, 2010-2012

In 2010, MustAhaus e.V. association and LaVidaVerde GmbH (LLC) were created for the practical reason of self-managing the building. Thus, the agency became collective, on the one hand, and organisationally embedded on the other, as shown in the 'types' table. At the same time, the transformative orientation remained, as the aim was to create more just and sustainable housing. LaVidaVerde was composed of the core group of the project, who were joined by additional people recruited through word-of-mouth and newspaper advertisements. In 2011, the group managed to acquire the building plot Sophienstraße in

Lichtenberg. Everything was ready for construction to begin.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type 1: Do their bit

Reformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Secondary type 2: Do it their way

Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

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Phase 3: Construction of the shared and communal Passive House, 2012-2014

In 2013, the construction of the building began, so both the collective and organisationally embedded agency remained important.

From 2014 onwards, LaVidaVerde started to engage deeply in contesting legislation proposed by the federal government following the bankruptcy of the wind power operator Prokon that argued for the protection of small property owners but endangered alternative collective projects such as Lavidaverde. A collective movement called “wir sind nicht Prokons” led by the Mietshäuser Syndikat was created,³ and thus LaVidaVerde acquired additional collective agency with a social-movement

component by taking part in the adaptation of the law to address such collective housing projects.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types

Do their bit

Reformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Do it their way

Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Make their claims

Transformative outcome / Social movements agency

Phase 4: Moving in, living in, and future, 2015-

The most recent and current phase in the history of LaVidaVerde started in 2015, once members moved in. This added a new type of secondary agency as inhabitants also became active energy citizens in their new homes. Meanwhile, the social movement orientation became less intense, but the LaVidaVerde collective is still highly engaged, notably within the “Kiez” or in favour of refugees. Furthermore, in the longer term, the case still intends to broaden its alternative housing and living model and support other similar projects once its loans are reimbursed.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types

Do their own

Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Do their bit

Reformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Do it their way

Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Make their claims

Transformative outcome / Social movements agency

³ See more details at <https://direkteaktion.org/228-wir-sind-nicht-prokon/>, <https://www.openpetition.de/petition/online/fuer-sinnvolle-ausnahmen-vom-vermoegensanlagengesetz-vermanlg> and at https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mietsh%C3%A4user_Syndikat (Accessed: 30.09.2023)

In accordance with the rules that drive the Mietshäuser Syndikat: "Well, the housing market in Berlin is very competitive, and there are actually no more affordable flats. And everything that is being built now, or that currently exists, is to be converted into condominiums. And we want to explicitly bring a counter-design to this, together with the Mietshäuser Syndikat in Berlin. That is, we build our house with

bank loans, obtain loans from private individuals and then live there for rent, and the rent then pays back the loans. And at some point, the house is paid off, and we then finance, so to speak, reconstruction measures, renovation and house projects all over Germany".

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The aspects of energy citizenship

The decision-making processes encompass all the aspects of community self-governance. The case owners are tenants and landlords at the same time, and they manage their building themselves. Decisions are made by consensus, and individuals have veto power. They are aware that this is not always the easiest way and that it often takes a long time. Yet, what is important is that “in the group, the process is above all mutual respect and the constructive handling of conflicts”. **The decision-making process is thus centred on consensus, even beyond basic democratic principles, to ensure the cohesion of the community and the support of each member for each decision that is taken.**

Citizen control
Citizens exert effective control, and their votes have to be taken into account

The case is highly involved in reducing consumption and emissions of carbon as it involves a certified energy-plus building, and highly detailed monitoring of the building realised through a research project underlines this. Therefore, though carbon emissions or avoided carbon emissions are not explicitly calculated, the case can be considered as recognizing explicitly this environmental limit and as undertaking all possible measures to reduce members' environmental impact, notably in terms of energy consumption (which is a quarter of an average Berliner's).

Carbon limit
Explicit recognition of the carbon limit

Democracy in general lies at the very heart of the project and, considering the interest given to citizens' energy by the case, it can be seen as considering energy democracy as part of its vision. Furthermore, the case is highly involved in networking with and promoting sustainable alternative housing projects, notably through the Mietshäusersyndikat, which **prevents any private ownership of the building and therefore any speculative interests.**

Democratic energy future
A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

FOCUS ON DISADVANTAGED GROUPS

As a housing project, it cannot be open to all, for obvious reasons. Yet, equity and justice are strongly considered in the project considering its inclusivity (ground floor equipped to welcome disabled persons, inclusion of people of non-German origins, intergenerational project), and the solidarity it demonstrates in everyday life as well as through the group fund aimed at helping residents who would face financial difficulties. **Equity and justice concerns thus have to be balanced with the basic requirements for the functioning of the community.**

Equity and justice
Equal access is granted, but limited by various criteria

Environmental sustainability is a core concern and is manifested in different ways in the case. 1) At LaVidaVerde, the combination of the KfW 40 standard with the concept of an energy-plus house has resulted in a building that consumes significantly less energy than an average one. 2) LaVidaVerde is characterised by high space efficiency. 3) Water consumption is also significantly lower than the Berlin average. 4) Tools and space are shared. **Continuous efforts are made to further reduce environmental impact.**

Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability is a core issue, and is considered in goal setting

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Source of images

<https://www.cohousing-berlin.de/en/node/819>, <https://www.lavidaver.de/>, <https://www.berliner-woche.de/>

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SoLocal Energy

GERMANY

HOLISTIC

COLLECTIVE

URBAN

Summary

SoLocal Energy is part of a proactive and progressive energy transition. It aims to address global climate change from the bottom up by empowering the community. Based on corporate values oriented towards the common good, the initiative intends to get people from all population groups on board simultaneously. For this purpose, they have founded the non-profit association SoLocal Energy e.V. This serves as an umbrella for their various activities, from balcony power plants to neighbourhood climate circles to the self-build solar plant community, supplemented by various workshop and lecture formats.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

This is a case of ENCI since the motto of the association is "Shaping [...] climate change from the bottom in a visionary way!" To do this, SoLocal Energy wants to contribute to addressing global climate change from below and empower the community. Their vision consists of putting a sustainable energy supply in the hands of citizens to achieve climate-just energy democracy. Their values are solidarity, justice, sustainability and personal responsibility.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Goals

1. Addressing global climate change from the bottom up;
2. Contributing to the empowerment of individuals and the community with regard to the energy system;
3. Putting sustainable energy supply in the hands of citizens to achieve a climate-just energy democracy, including reducing energy poverty.

The story and the typology

The case started in 2019-2020 with support from an innovation fund (Hessen Ideen) at Kassel University. An NGO was established right at the start of the project to ensure the case's longer-term viability. However, even since 2020, the case has gone through several stages of development.

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Phase 1: Creation of the case, 2019 - 2020

Three graduate students from Kassel University received funding from Hessen Ideen to establish SoLocal Energy. Thus, the case and the individuals starting it were organisationally embedded at the university. SoLocal Energy began its operations in January 2020 as an NGO, intended to be a citizen-based organisation.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do it their way

Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded individual agency

Secondary type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Collective agency

Phase 2: Assuming collective agency and enabling individual agency, 2020 - 2021

In the second phase, with the establishment of the Association, the case became independent and assumed collective, citizen-based (and hybrid) agency with a transformative outcome orientation. However, in addition to enabling collective agency, the case also empowers individuals to become energy citizens either in a relatively passive and reformative way when they install solar plants on balconies or in a more active and transformative way by teaching the people how to do the installation themselves. The organisers explain this process and how the second way of doing it progressively became the norm: *“In the beginning, we had this approach with the balcony power plants: We do complete installation and consulting and deliver them to people with a wheel and [...] do everything and so on. In the meantime, we have taken more of an approach so that we can simply*

achieve more in the same amount of time by informing people, showing them how to do it and that they can do it themselves”.

Furthermore, SoLocal also started cooperating with similar organisations, e.g., they joined a network of self-build organisations.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types:

Do their bit (in the household)

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Do their own (in the household)

Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Phase 3: SoLocal energy evolution, 2021 - 2022

In phase 3 of its evolution, SoLocal Energy focused more and more on enabling people to install renewable energy on balconies and rooftops themselves so that the association progressively abandoned installing the equipment, thus promoting a more transformative form of energy citizenship.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Do their own (in the household)

Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Phase 4: Current state and future, 2023 -

The initiative is currently undergoing some level of change. Indeed, the case actors themselves consider it an ongoing and evolving process through which they intend to move even further towards engaging people in the energy transition. Therefore, while some of their activities have become more “mainstream” (for example, installing balcony solar power plants), they intend to use the revenue from these activities to initiate and develop further innovative projects. Their objective is also to support (or become?) the social movement of local, DIY, individual and collective energy production. Moreover, a new secondary transformative and collective ideal type of energy citizenship emerged as the case was well-established by 2022, and it started playing a role as a social movement that is part of the local climate debate and policy-making.

In the future, the people involved in the case plan to reach out more to disadvantaged communities and strengthen their networking activities. In the longer run, the ambition of the case is clearly to enable citizens to take an increasingly active role in the energy system so they can be considered fully entitled stakeholders of its management.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types

Do their own (in the household)

Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Make their claims

Transformative outcome / Social movements agency

The aspects of energy citizenship

Solocal Energy actively promotes individual and self-organising community for the ownership of solar power plants as well as the creation of neighbourhood circles – all of which encompass many forms of ENCI and energy infrastructure ownership and participation, with the aim of involving disadvantaged users as well. Solocal Energy manages to make its voice heard in the public debate, thus **ensuring the broad involvement of local citizens in the energy system while also providing a forum for deliberation for local people.**

Citizen control is ensured by the statutes of the Association and is also required by law. Thus, among other principles, the following rules are observed: 1) **“each member shall have one vote.** The right to vote is transferable to other members. Each member may represent a maximum of two other members.” 2) Furthermore, “consensus decisions shall be sought; voting shall only take place after discussion without convergence of views.” Making decisions based on citizen votes is compulsory, since they are following cooperative principles. Furthermore, the association has adopted the principles of sociocracy, which also enhances citizen control.

Citizen control

Citizens exert effective control, and their votes have to be taken into account

The case explicitly recognises the ecological limit of carbon emissions, and the importance of renewable energy systems in avoiding carbon emissions. In an effort to better communicate this, they display details about emissions avoided with the help of their activities on the internet site of the Association using visual representations.

Carbon limit

Explicit recognition with mention/objective of reaching the max. carbon footprint

Democratic energy future

A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

FOCUS ON DISADVANTAGED GROUPS

The case is accessible to all people who want to get involved, since membership fees can be freely determined based on the financial resources of members. However, the involvement of the Association in justice and equity issues goes way beyond simple membership in the association. Members believe that **“Electricity is an important prerequisite for participation in public life”** and that **“there is a basic right to energy.”** Accordingly, they want to enable everyone to have access to energy. Those who are cut off temporarily can borrow island balcony solar power plants from the Association.

Equity and justice

Involvement is fully open

The case has a global/holistic approach to climate change and environmental sustainability that they try to take into account in all their activities, e.g., as highlighted by their use of a cargo bike to transport the solar panels. Though they are focused on solar energy, whether at a small individual or larger collective scale, case members’ goals extend beyond energy and are intended to achieve environmental sustainability in general, which is particularly clear in their effort to create neighbourhood circles for climate change. In this framework, the Association goes beyond a focus on energy and addresses issues related to climate-friendly cooking, mobility, etc.

Environmental sustainability

Core issue, considered in goal setting

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

grünIndependent
Institute

Further information

facebook.com/SoLocalEnergy
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Source of images

www.solocal-energy.de/

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GoiEner Taldea

Summary

GoiEner Taleda is a cooperative project that promotes the generation and consumption of renewable energy. It was created in 2012 because of "dissatisfaction with the functioning of the national energy system." GoiEner believes that electricity is now a need that is as basic as that of food and wants consumers to reclaim their energy sovereignty and make them aware of its importance. Its main purpose is to make energy something that belongs to everyone and for everyone – far from big projects, models that perpetuate the use of fossil fuels, and practices that do not empower people. This will be achieved by protecting, informing, and promoting consumer rights and reclaiming energy sovereignty from the oligopoly of large distribution companies.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

It is a clear example of a citizen initiative for energy sustainability and democracy. GoiEner's long-term goal is for citizens to regain control and become aware of the importance of energy, promoting responsible and sustainable energy consumption and carrying out important awareness-raising work.

DIRECT ENERGY
PRODUCTION /
CONSUMPTION

COLLECTIVE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Goals

1. Providing services and distributing products related to the commercialisation of renewable energy;
2. Promoting more democratic energy decision-making: defending and improving consumer rights by raising awareness of the cooperative model;
3. Facilitating greater community ownership of a decentralised energy system (supporting the community to regain energy sovereignty).

The story and the typology

GoiEner was born at the end of 2012 as a collective, citizen-based initiative due to social discontent with the national energy system. The organisation, which started out with transformative goals, for a short period shifted from its primary goal (restoring energy sovereignty) to a more reformative type of citizenship due to external circumstances: a new policy that resulted in an exponential growth in membership. In later phases, the cooperative found its purpose again in a transformative direction by returning to the work of achieving energy sovereignty, with a strongly renewed emphasis on volunteering and local development.

Case history summary

For the summary
methodology,
click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Phase 1: From the initiation of the case in 2012 to the new solar law in 2013

The case was initiated due to the dissatisfaction of several people with experience and knowledge of the energy system.

The starting point was a discussion that began between September and October 2012 with a group of people who were "fed up with the fact that they [were] just customers with no other rights than to pay the bills". This led to the decision in December of the same year to create a non-profit cooperative.

Beyond cooperation regarding renewable energy production and consumption, there was also a desire to regain energy sovereignty.

This was a grassroots initiative that attempted to make radical changes to the national energy system. Thus, a collective, citizen-based project was started with a transformative goal orientation, classified as the "Go ahead" ideal type.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformativo	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: **Go ahead**

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Phase 2: Marketing and growth of membership, 2013-2015

In this phase, the cooperative experienced difficulties due to the undesired growth in membership.

At the beginning of 2013, Spain introduced a solar tax, which resulted in significant changes and made many energy production projects unprofitable. It involved a tax on all electricity bills for those who switched to self-consumption. It was a very controversial law due to its negative consequences for developing and using renewable energies, such as photovoltaic solar energy.

The cooperative had no choice but to increase its commercialisation. Members wanted to act locally but needed money to maintain the organisation. While they were busy with the process of commercialisation, the social aspect of the

cooperative was sidelined, and the original mission (restoring energy sovereignty) was marginalised.

As GoiEner adapted to the market, it began to grow exponentially, which for a time hindered the realisation of its core vision and mission, so the case became more reformativo than transformative. Thus, the main energy citizenship type became "Do their share".

	Individual			Collective	
Reformativo	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims				

Main type: **Do their share**

Reformativo outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Phase 3: After the creation of Elkarteia in 2015 until the current phase (since 2021)

In 2015, GoiEner Elkarteia (a pillar of the cooperative movement) was born, which helped the cooperative return to its original goals. Elkarteia has become one of the pillars of the organisation. It is designed to help organise volunteer work and make it more dynamic, giving the project a more substantial social dimension.

With the creation of Elkarteia, the social vision of the initiative strengthened. The activities of sensitisation, training, dissemination and awareness-raising aimed at citizens, educational, economic and social agents, and public administrations were introduced.

With this, the organisation began to return to its original purpose, again with the transformative

goals of achieving sovereignty, so the main type can again be classified as the “Go ahead” ideal type. Also, a secondary energy citizenship type emerged as the organisation began to mobilise others and acquired a growing volunteer base.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Do the job

Reformative outcome / Social movements agency

Phase 4: Current state, 2021-

After these difficulties, the cooperative has now been able to return to its starting point and again identifies a more democratic energy future as its main goal.

Today, GoiEner is an initiative with little influence in Spain, mainly because power is concentrated in the hands of large corporations. Despite this, it maintains its motivation and interest in strengthening and inspiring all those who are currently part of the initiative (volunteers and members) and anyone who may be interested in becoming a part of it.

The ENCI ideal types have not changed in the most recent phase.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Do the job

Reformative outcome / Social movements agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

The aspects of energy citizenship

The purpose of the case is to restore energy sovereignty for citizens because “energy should belong to citizens and for citizens”. **A central thread has been guaranteeing the rights of customers to be part of and make decisions about the energy system.** GoiEner fights against large trading companies that limit the capacity for citizen control. GoiEner believes that the most democratic energy future lies with “collective self-consumption and especially energy communities”.

At the organisational level: at general assemblies, resolutions are deliberated and taken that are binding for all members, which result from prior discussions among members and are based on annual reports. At the technical or practical level: people's participation usually involves being part of working teams led by a manager, which is a rotating position. **Although theoretically all citizens can participate and their voices are always taken into account, too often people do not participate, and decisions are ultimately taken at the assembly.**

Democratic energy future

A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

The case operates at the highest level of “equity and justice” due to the idea that a fair energy system should not leave anyone without the basic resources to live a dignified life. **Its social focus is on training and providing instruments to different people and groups for tackling energy poverty.** Although there is a membership fee, there is an alternative way to participate through volunteering. There are also limits on capital contributions. In addition, GoiEner supports other local co-operatives throughout Spain.

Equity and justice

Involvement is fully open

GoiEner publishes a social balance report, which includes indicators that evaluate the degree of compliance with the commitment to the environment in terms of the provision of a policy, action plan or environmental management system; internal control of CO₂ emissions; alternatives to or aid for transport; **energy saving and efficiency and water consumption practices and procedures; electricity services with 100% renewable suppliers;** use of recycled paper or paper with a sustainable forestry certificate; and the incorporation of responsible consumption criteria. These indicators have been improving over time.

Environmental sustainability

Environmental sustainability is a core issue, and is considered in goal setting

Citizen control

Citizens can express their views, but their views are not necessarily taken into account

Although GoiEner promotes consumption from renewable sources, its internal activity is not free of emissions (e.g., travel, the purchase of materials, etc.). For this reason, **GoiEner Taldea is currently working together with the Carbon Footprint Foundation Commission to offset the footprint generated by the cooperative.** Broader objectives of the initiative are linked to the recognition of “biophysical limits and energy savings”.

Carbon limits

Explicit recognition with mention/objective of reaching the max. carbon footprint

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Further information

facebook.com/goiener
youtube.com/user/Goienner

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Source of images

www.goiener.com/
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Railcoop

MOBILITY

COLLECTIVE

Summary

Railcoop is the first rail cooperative in France, consisting of more than 14,000 shareholders, and was established following the liberalisation of the rail market. Railcoop wants to strengthen access to rail mobility to contribute to the energy transition. It aims at complementing the public service of the national train company SNCF with new lines, especially in rural areas and small cities. A freight service was launched in November 2021 (but as of April 2023, it is no longer running), and a public transportation service is also planned.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

Railcoop is a citizen movement that works as a cooperative using democratic and transparent governance and aims to foster the citizen-led development of sustainable rail mobility services, especially in rural regions that have suffered due to train station closure policies of recent decades.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Goals

1. Strengthening the use of rail broadly, i.e., beyond the cooperative. Make trains accessible to all and foster a culture shift to make this happen;
2. Creating a new structure of democratic intermediation: making political claims through action. The goal is to promote another mode of democratic expression beyond trade unions or NGOs, which are dependent on company boards or public action;
3. Preserving the democratic internal governance of the organisation despite the vertical organisation of the rail sector.

The story and the typology

Railcoop started out working more like an NGO, with a very transparent culture, openly sharing information with all shareholders. Due to the very fast growth in shareholders as well as the large size of its projects and the highly regulated rail sector in France, Railcoop was forced to transform into a more conventionally functioning company. However, its main vision and objectives have not changed since its inception.

Thus, Railcoop went from a citizen-based agency type of initiative, leaning towards a social movement-type agency at its beginnings, to a more organisationally embedded agency today. However, the democratic governance principles still make Railcoop stand out, corresponding to a citizen-based model. Today, despite the professionalisation required to work within the rail sector, Railcoop's objectives remain to contribute to the energy transition and democratise the transport system.

Case history summary

Et si votre voix
comptait pour une voie ?
Devenez sociétaire !

For the summary
methodology,
click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Phase 1: Creation of the case in 2019 and initial operation, 2019 - 2021

Railcoop started out working more like an NGO, thus was a citizen-based collective agency type of initiative (Type 8) with a transformative outcome orientation. It had a transparent culture and openly shared information with all shareholders. The case has witnessed very fast growth in shareholders since its beginning, from 30 to 14,000 shareholders. Thus, its classification as a secondary ideal energy citizenship type, namely Type 10 (transformative social movement), is also relevant due to the successful, general mobilisation for recruiting

shareholders united in their desire and will to promote rail transport.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Make their claims

Transformative outcome / Social movements agency

Phase 2: Current status, 2021-

Due to its rapid growth, Railcoop was forced to transform into a more conventionally functioning company, with restricted access for shareholders to sensitive information defined as “business confidential”. As Railcoop’s projects are too big to be handled outside of the parameters of conventional business law, the case had to start functioning more as a regular company (Type 4). However, its democratic governance principles mean that Railcoop still stands out and remains intact as a citizen-based model with a transformative outcome orientation.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Do it their way (within hybrid organisations)

Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

The aspects of energy citizenship

Railcoop is supporting a more democratic energy future in two key ways: first, it strives to **offer a service that allows access to sustainable rail mobility services**, especially in rural regions and smaller cities. Second, **the cooperative is governed democratically**, with a general assembly where five 'colleges' each have 20% voting rights. There is one college for each shareholder group (employees, physical persons, legal persons, technical and financial partners, local authorities). Within the colleges, all shareholders have the same voting power (one vote per shareholder).

Membership **allows members to participate in different ways**. First, economic participation through shareholding. Second, democratic participation by being informed, expressing their voice in open deliberations, voting, and participating in the General Assembly. Third, activist participation by voluntarily getting involved to defend and support the development of Railcoop. By joining local and thematic Railcoop groups, **members can participate in the construction of the cooperative** by contributing to the identification of future goals.

Democratic energy future

A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

Citizen control
Citizens exert effective control, and their votes have to be taken into account

The initiative is presented as a response to the climate emergency and has **carried out direct and indirect carbon footprint calculations of their freight and planned passenger train services**. The analysis showed that with Railcoop services included in the overall rail transport network in France, there is a potential for significant emissions reductions (33-59%).

Carbon limit
Explicit recognition of the carbon limit

FOCUS ON DISADVANTAGED GROUPS

FOCUS ON GENDER ISSUES

Railcoop is open to anyone becoming a shareholder and its services aim at matching the cost of car-sharing, hence favouring social inclusion and access to rail mobility for all. It has the **strong feature of inclusiveness since it aims to connect villages and small cities with train services**. There is no particular requirement for becoming involved as a shareholder, beyond the need to be able to buy at least one share worth 100€. By **indirectly increasing access to rail in rural areas, it benefits vulnerable people** like women, elderly, children, so has a potentially strong social impact.

Equity and justice
Involvement is fully open

Railcoop is dedicated to making the ecological transition happen while respecting strong social standards and reducing trains' ecological footprint as much as possible. "In a context of global warming, the train is an essential link in the ongoing ecological transition. Transporting passengers by rail requires less than a twelfth of the energy required to move one person or one ton of goods by road. Developing rail also means, indirectly, protecting biodiversity, curbing the artificialisation of land and therefore preserving our territories. Trains consume less space than roads and are a complementary to soft mobility (bicycles, walking, etc.)."

Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability is a core issue and considered in goal setting

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Further information

facebook.com/Railcoop/
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Source of images

<https://www.railcoop.fr/>, <https://www.facebook.com/Railcoop/>

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Shared Energy

Summary

Energie Partagée (Shared Energy) is an organisation that unites the citizen energy movement in France. The case unites and advocates; provides project assistance; and finances citizen-led 100% renewable energy projects. To carry out these activities, Energie Partagée consists of three different legal structures: a cooperative, an investment tool, and an association. The three parts of the organisation are linked through the core values defined in their founding charter. These core values are additionally multiplied by the local cases that benefit from their citizen-energy label.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

The case is a good example of an organisation that enacts and enables collective energy citizenship by supporting the development of local citizen renewable energy projects by different means and pursuing advocacy activities at different levels of government.

COLLECTIVE

DIRECT ENERGY
PRODUCTION /
CONSUMPTION

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Goals

1. Reducing energy consumption through sufficiency and efficiency and covering the remaining energy consumption entirely from renewable energy;
2. Enabling the active participation of each citizen and each community in the decisions and/or activities necessary to achieve objective 1;
3. Spatial and temporal sharing of burdens and benefits, integrating principles of international energy solidarity into energy consumption and use.

The story and the typology

Energie Partagée was created by the pioneers of the French citizen energy movement to support early adopters (and beyond) in the energy transition. Hespul, one of Energie Partagée’s founders, inaugurated their photovoltaic centre in 1992 and actively lobbied for regulatory changes to enable citizen renewable energy production in France. Energie Partagée Investment tool was created in 2008, the association in 2010 following the elaboration of the founding charter and with the financial and administrative support of the French Environment Agency ADEME.

In addition to Hespul, the other founding members were the electricity supplier Enercoop, the financial cooperative La Nef, the consultancy Inddigo, Crédit coopératif, Christel Sauvage, director of Enercoop Ardennes-Champagne, Stéphane Chatelin, director of the Négawatt association, Michel Leclercq, chairman of Éoliennes en Pays de Vilaine, and Raphaël Claustre, director of the Comité de Liaison Énergies Renouvelables.

Over the years, the organisation has undeniably changed a lot, for example, regarding the number of partnerships, the number of citizen renewable energy projects supported, the money invested, and the coverage of the regional support networks. However, the transformative vision of the future energy system described in the charter has remained intact. Thus, the primary ideal energy citizenship type supported by the case has stayed the same.

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Phase 1: Beginnings and set-up

As mentioned, frontrunners in the French citizen energy movement came together to create Energie Partagée. Energie Partagée (the movement for citizens' energy) consists of three different legal structures: the cooperative (simplified joint-stock cooperative company, created in 2010); the investment tool (partnership limited by shares, created in 2008); and the association (association law, created in 2010). The three parts all share the values defined in their founding charter. The three parts work together to enable financing, support and advocacy for citizen renewable energy projects. The three most important goals mentioned in the

Phase 2: Becoming a key actor in the French context and future objectives

While the vision has been the same since the Energie Partagée Charter was adopted in 2010, the case's objectives are currently undergoing change. The Energie Partagée movement has gained ground in France over the past decade and become a central actor in the citizen energy movement. The entirety of metropolitan France is now covered with regional support networks that could potentially take on the task of supporting new initiatives. Furthermore, a citizen energy label was introduced in 2021, through which Energie Partagée shares its vision through the projects it supports, ensuring local ownership and mobilisation, ethical and citizen-based financing, democratic governance, and added ecological value. Now, the case is looking into restructuring its activities, focusing more on developing large-scale renewable energy projects and building

partnerships with private developers who can engage in more significant projects.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Make their claims

Transformative outcome / Social movements agency

partnerships with private developers who can engage in more significant projects.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Make their claims

Transformative outcome / Social movements agency

No big changes have occurred in the case's type since it was founded in 2010. However, the case could be seen as supporting all other kinds of ENCI through its range of activities, such as mobilising citizens for renewable citizen energy projects and financing them, awareness-raising, support structures, partnerships, lobbying, etc.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

The aspects of energy citizenship

Democratic governance is a core value of the case regarding both the internal functioning of the organization and as a value supported through the activities of the case (through labelling and financing). The governance of the case is set up to ensure transparency and democratic decision-making. The governance mode chosen for the supported projects must allow for community control of production prices and total transparency about operational and financial issues.

Citizen control

Citizens exert effective control, and their votes have to be taken into account

*Climate change is mentioned in the Energie Partagée founding charter which corresponds to an implicit recognition of the ecological limit of atmospheric carbon emissions. Furthermore, on the case's website they have published resources for their members that pertain to carbon neutrality. Several of their members furthermore undertake activities that **seek to limit carbon emissions/carbon footprints**, and Energie Partagée has shared these on their webpage.*

Carbon limit

Explicit recognition of the carbon limit

*The movement empowers citizens by supporting the democratic governance of renewable energy citizen projects with a quality check during an assessment to decide whether they can receive the Energie Partagée label. **Through its label, the case supports strong democratic governance of projects, local ownership and limits financial profits to ensure that investments are used for clean citizen energy production, not for speculation.***

Democratic energy future

A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

FOCUS ON DISADVANTAGED GROUPS

Energy Partagée is open to everyone and reducing energy poverty is mentioned as an objective of renewable energy citizen projects in its founding charter. While it is likely that there is a socioeconomic bias in the citizen shareholding and which citizens take part in citizen projects, the Energie Partagée investment tool offers shares for 10€ for marginalised communities to make shareholding more accessible.

Equity and justice

Equal access is granted, but limited by various criteria

Energy Partagée clearly supports sufficiency and efficiency first and commits to fostering a reduction in energy needs. Ideally, the long-term objective is that remaining energy needs should be covered by renewable energy citizen projects.

Environmental sustainability

Environmental sustainability is a core issue, and is considered in goal setting

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Further information

facebook.com/EnergiePartagee.org

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 - <https://energie-partagee.org/decouvrir/energie-citoyenne/label-charte-energie-partagee/la-charte-energie-partagee>
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Source of images

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Cargonomia

Summary

Cargonomia is the formalisation of a pre-existing collaboration between three socially and environmentally conscious small enterprises operating in or near Budapest. Partners in the project include the Cyclonomia Do it Yourself Bicycle Social Cooperative, Zsamboki Biokert (an organic vegetable farm and sustainable agriculture community education centre), and Kantaa (a self-organised bike messenger and delivery company). Cargonomia and its partners' activities aim to showcase how environmentally friendly and equity-based partnerships can create sustainable and meaningful community empowerment opportunities.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

Cargonomia represents the crossover point between the activities of the partners involved in the project (sustainable food production, the promotion of low-carbon transport solutions, and bicycle competency advocacy). Thus, based on sustainability and fair trade principles, Cargonomia enables a holistic form of energy citizenship by increasing access to locally produced products by promoting direct trade from local producers to consumer communities and creating a community centred around local food distribution.

HOLISTIC

COLLECTIVE

Goals

1. Using and promoting low-carbon and sustainable transport solutions that are concrete alternatives to standard profit-driven social and economic systems;
2. Distributing local organic food products and propagating conscious and sustainable consumption;
3. Creating open community spaces where people can walk in and have discussions, network with each other when they pick up their food boxes, and rent cargo bikes.

The story and the typology

Cargonomia is a unique combination of activities created to promote more sustainable societies and socioeconomic systems. In addition to directly marketing and distributing local food products, Cargonomia is a logistics centre for sustainable urban transport solutions where community members can borrow, rent and buy locally manufactured cargo bikes. It is also an open space for community activities focusing on sustainable transition, conviviality and Degrowth, enabling citizen-based collective energy citizenship with a clearly and explicitly transformative outcome orientation.

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Phase 1: Creation and setting up, 2015 - 2020

The first five years of Cargonomia were a smooth process: the initiators created the project, which “evolved organically”, as one of the co-founders put it, and it grew continuously: the number of partner organisations increased during this period.

The “business model” changed over time: the initiative connected three organisations focusing on organic food production, sustainable urban mobility based on cargo bikes, and bike creation and repair.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: **Go ahead**

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Phase 2: From the COVID pandemic to the present and future, 2020 -

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the project changed tremendously: it shifted most activities from the city, Budapest, to the countryside (the village of Zsámbok, about 25 km from Budapest). During the pandemic, people were allowed to meet outdoors but not indoors. In addition, sales of locally produced fruit and vegetables peaked during the epidemic (because people changed their habits, including shopping). As the lockdowns were gradually completely lifted (at least in Hungary), and because their contract for the space for the headquarters in Budapest ended, the project owners started to look for a new place.

In parallel with this search, the case suffered an identity crisis due to the different psychological, economic, etc. changes that the pandemic induced and because many people who had been in close touch with Cargonomia left Hungary.

Nevertheless, Cargonomia has several ongoing, successful (mostly EU-funded) projects with municipal governments and other organisations (e.g., establishing and managing so-called climate gardens). Furthermore, they have also shifted their focus to educational activities, including organic, low-tech agriculture and building, as workshops can be conducted in the countryside. They also want to reflect more on their successes and failures in the future and publish and disseminate more.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: **Go ahead**

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

The aspects of energy citizenship

Energy democracy is not an explicit goal, but there is a need for this in order to achieve Cargonomia's goals, namely, **building a society, which is independent from the for-profit, market-centred economy**, in accordance with the ideas of the Degrowth movement, which is very strongly based on participatory democracy.

Democratic energy future

A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

FOCUS ON DISADVANTAGED GROUPS

The mission of Cargonomia is to contribute to sustainable transformation toward a socially and environmentally just future by questioning the dominant economic paradigm through practical, educational and research activities.

Cargonomia is open to everyone, with a special focus on those who are disadvantaged and marginalized. For example, they hire Roma people at Zsámbok to help with managing the land; they have projects with autistic people; and they have planned two projects with secondary schools from disadvantaged districts, etc.

Equity and justice
Involvement is fully open

One of the core activities of Cargonomia is delivering food products by cargo bike, which is a **sustainable (emission-free) mode of transport**. The food products that are delivered also support **sustainability in the form of biodiversity and promoting locally produced organic food**, etc. Furthermore, the atelier where **people can repair their own bikes** promotes sustainability through (self-)repair. It is also considered important to use bike parts and accessories that are environmentally friendly.

Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability is a core issue, and is considered in goal setting

Citizen power/control
Citizens exert effective control, and their votes have to be taken into account

Carbon limit

Explicit recognition of the carbon limit

The whole project is partially based on the goal of reducing the carbon footprint (although not just the carbon footprint, but all harmful environmental impact), but there is no mention of the carbon footprint as an indicator. However, in one of the documents it is mentioned how much carbon they save by using the cargo bikes. The Degrowth movement explicitly claims that the planet is finite, so we cannot base our lifestyles on growing our consumption.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Further information

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Source of images

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From the Community Energy Programme to Community Energy Service

HUNGARY

DIRECT ENERGY
PRODUCTION /
CONSUMPTION

COLLECTIVE

URBAN

Summary

Friends of Earth Hungary (FoE), the Solidarity Economy Centre, and the Gólya community house and bar joined forces to create the Community Energy Service Company (CESCO) in 2021. The objective is to develop a decentralised renewable energy generation model owned by local communities or solidarity economy enterprises. CESCO managed to obtain funding for a programme in which community energy projects will be implemented in seven locations; the first location will be the Kazán Community House, thereby becoming one of the first community energy projects in Hungary.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

Investments in Renewable Energy Sources (RES) in Hungary are challenged by multiple factors, such as the rapid drying up of national financing schemes, the complicated bureaucracy associated with permitting processes, and very limited national RES appliance production, services and expertise. The project aims to promote energy citizenship and energy transition by monitoring policymakers and reviewing legislation (legal advocacy), organising forums, and educating residents (raising awareness).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Goals

1. Engaging in the energy transition, putting sustainability and transition into practice;
2. Accelerating the development of energy-efficient, renewable energy projects by creating a favourable regulatory environment;
3. Informing citizens about the opportunities connected to community energy and involving them in community energy projects; supporting groups and communities in starting their projects.

The story and the typology

From the beginning, the initiative has been aimed at supporting community energy projects. Thus, it is a citizen-based and hybrid case in terms of energy citizenship. As the organisation is also involved in political lobbying, public agency is also present as a secondary type. The project was more reformative in its early stages but progressively became more transformative as collected knowledge was put into practice.

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Phase 1: Creation and initial knowledge gathering, 2013-2016

The Community Energy Programme of FoE Hungary has been running since 2013. During the first phase, national and international experience was gathered through case study collection, which provided a good framework and materials for future development. FoE HU also started building a community around community energy.

During this phase, the agency of the initiative was collective, citizen-based and hybrid, as community energy was the focus. As the focus was on building a knowledge base, at that time, the case was rather reformative (this can be seen in the main ideal type, type 7).

In addition, the initiative regularly participated in relevant policy review processes, so public agency was also present (as shown in the secondary type).

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Make their voice heard Reformative outcome / Public agency

Phase 2: Education, awareness raising, community building and advocacy, 2016-2021

In the second phase, mainly educational and awareness-raising publications were produced, and a number of conferences, workshops and lectures were held to disseminate the knowledge and experience that had been gathered.

An informal network of experts was also set up, involving a number of prominent organisations working on energy issues or specifically on energy poverty.

A pilot project for the development of a community energy system was launched, and advocacy started in connection with the new Renewable Energy Directive.

In the second period, the case changed from reformative to transformative (reflected in the

designation of both primary and secondary types). Accumulated knowledge was put into practice, and active community building and advocacy became a strong feature.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Make their vote count Transformative outcome / Public agency

Phase 3: Establishment of the Community Energy Service Company, 2021-2023

In 2021, the Community Energy Service Company was established, and a pilot community energy investment design started. The first one, at the Kazán Community House, started already in 2022. Although the solar panel installation has been completed, operating it in the current Hungarian regulatory context is difficult.

Under the CESCO project, small-scale cooperation has started with the municipality of Alsómocsolád, an inspiring small village. For now, the solar potential of the village's houses has been measured, and it is hoped that an energy community will be established there in the future.

The CESCO project was funded by the Ministry of Innovation and Technology, together with six other major programmes (quite different but linked in some way to community energy).

Phase 4: Transformation and future, 2023-

The initiative is currently undergoing major transformation. The two partners leading the project (FoE Hungary and the Solidarity Economy Centre) are expected to continue their work separately, but both will continue to support community energy initiatives and cooperate where possible. FoE Hungary will instead support the development of larger-scale pilots that fit the currently funded national tenders. The Solidarity Economy Centre will focus on promoting grassroots initiatives, which, under current regulations, cannot yet collectively produce and distribute energy.

The organisations leading these funded projects have jointly established the Association of Hungarian Energy Communities and Flexibility Aggregators (in Hungarian: MERSZ) to combine their experience to develop a policy proposal for detailed rules that can create real opportunities for developing energy communities.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Make their vote count

Transformative outcome / Public agency

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Make their vote count

Transformative outcome / Public agency

The aspects of energy citizenship

The project clearly **aims at creating a more democratic energy system by supporting the implementation of community energy projects and creating opportunities for the development of jointly owned household-sized power plants.**

It can help raise energy awareness, reduce energy poverty, strengthen the community and generate financial benefits

In this case, citizen power/control is one of the most important aspects. **The whole project is about raising the energy awareness of communities and giving them real opportunities** (e.g. through legal advocacy) to actually implement community energy projects.

Citizen power/control
Citizens exert effective control, and their votes have to be taken into account

Democratic energy future

A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

The main aim of the project is to promote the energy transition and democracy, so the equity/justice issue is very important to the case. Although the idea of **reducing energy poverty is noted in the programme description, it is not included in the core objectives.**

Equity and justice

Equal access is granted, but limited by various criteria

The project will clearly contribute to carbon emission reduction, but this is not emphasised enough in their messages and core documents. **Overall the focus is more on the practical side: implementation, the regulatory and technological side of community energy.**

Carbon limit
Explicit recognition of the carbon limit

Promoting environmental sustainability is an important background aspect of the project, but its main theme is energy and reforming the energy system. Looking at the overall case, it **goes a long way towards promoting environmental sustainability** and the related principles are included in the conceptual background to the project.

Environmental sustainability

Environmental sustainability is a core issue, and is considered in goal setting

Further information

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Source of images

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TreeDependent

HUNGARY

Summary

The ‘TreeDependent – responsible events, responsible travel’ programme is about providing support to reduce carbon emissions, as well as calculating and compensating them through various services. However, this is not a typical compensation programme as it emphasises reduction before compensation. Furthermore, only native fruit trees that are planted in school or non-profit gardens are used to achieve fully voluntary compensation, thereby connecting activities related to different sustainable development objectives. This is a programme run by GreenDependent, a non-profit organisation in Hungary.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

The TreeDependent programme helps others to become more active energy citizens and offers a variety of tools/services for this. Calculating the carbon footprint of events, travel or lifestyles and compensating them through planting native fruit trees is the programme's main focus. However, through the planting activities, different organisations and social and environmental objectives are also connected.

HOLISTIC

COLLECTIVE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Goals

1. Awareness-raising about more conscious (sustainable) lifestyles / environmental education;
2. Helping participating companies, organisations and individuals in their carbon compensation and reduction efforts;
3. Connecting participants – individuals and companies on one side and tree-hosting educational, social and non-profit institutions on the other, with the involvement of the tree nursery that collects and provides the native fruit trees.

The story and the typology

The project started as a carbon footprint compensation tool for the host organisation, GreenDependent. It only later became a more extensive project as more and more individuals and organisations desired to participate in it. Hence, it went through various phases of development. In the beginning, only a few compensation projects were implemented, and it took several years for TreeDependent to manifest as a fully functioning project. Later, the project became very successful and grew exponentially for a period, but the COVID-19 pandemic led to a significant decline in project finances. After the COVID-19 epidemic passed, project activities started to pick up again with new and old clients.

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Phase 1: Creation and initial years, 2010 - 2017

The initiative started organically, as the original idea was not to create a separate project but simply to calculate GreenDependent’s own carbon footprint (events, travel, etc., and later organisational emissions) as well as to take responsibility for them by compensating them by planting native fruit trees in the gardens of educational, social and non-profit institutions (who then became active participants in this collective case). Furthermore, it was important for GreenDependent to integrate this approach into all its projects (European, national and local) and to implement them as sustainably as possible (‘walking the talk’). Slowly, the process was picked

up by some partner organisations that participated in GreenDependent’s events. They considered it an effective way to influence their employees’ and partners’ attitudes towards energy efficiency and sustainability.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Phase 2: Growth, 2017 – 2019

Although there was initially no expectation at all of creating a separate project, the project became more successful than expected. As the project emerged and became a success, the organisers developed some ideas and started developing related plans. Nine years after the initial concept was born, a logo and the project name were coined (in 2019).

TreeDependent is the only programme to plant native fruit trees but not other types of trees (e.g., oak, beech, or pine). This means that compensation-related activities and responsibility-taking are better ‘owned’ by clients. The social acceptance of planting trees is high in Hungary, and there are not many programmes which help people understand and take responsibility for their action (in terms of carbon footprints), and it is an alternative to carbon credit programmes. Slowly, well-known companies started using this programme (Business Council for Sustainable Development Hungary, E.ON Hungary, ALTEO, etc.)

– improving the programme’s reputation. All in all, the project’s innovative aspects helped it come to life.

Furthermore, in addition to the collective energy citizenship agency enabled by the project, individuals became interested in participating during this period. Several people approached GreenDependent to inquire about calculating the carbon footprint of their overseas travels and taking responsibility for it by planting trees.

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types

Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Do their own

Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Phase 3: Peak, 2019 - March 2020

Gradually, more and more external customers – institutional and individual – approached GreenDependent to calculate the carbon footprint of their events or travelling and compensate them, regardless of the very strict selection criteria GreenDependent had defined. The process that is employed avoids the possibility of greenwashing: Clients cannot be companies whose actions are inherently harmful to the environment (e.g., oil or car manufacturing or fossil fuel companies) or are not in accordance with the project’s principles (e.g. not ready to reduce their emissions at following events).

After several years, some long-standing clients started to request more services from

GreenDependent within its TreeDependent programme (e.g., awareness-raising campaigns for employees and training on low-carbon event solutions).

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types

Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Do their own

Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Phase 4: Lockdown & pandemic, March 2020 - 2022

The COVID-19 crisis interrupted the project’s successful momentum. GreenDependent had to let people go, and the organisation lost most of their customers as well because events could not be organised as a result of the strict pandemic-related regulations; people stopped travelling, and partners (usually, business ones) put a halt to “extra investments” (i.e., providing funds for sustainability or education-related activities) due to uncertainty about the future. Furthermore, finding host institutions for the fruit trees became more difficult. In this period, the project returned to its original type, and only GreenDependent, with some core partners, continued to participate.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types

Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Do their own

Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

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Phase 5: Picking up again and renewed growth, March 2022 -

As the major phase of the COVID pandemic passed, the project gradually started to pick up speed again; some old and new clients have been participating with the educational and social institutions that are home to the trees.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types

Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Do their own

Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

GreenDependent ©

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

The aspects of energy citizenship

One of the project's outcomes is **helping people to become more active energy citizens; the project offers instruments and services** for this.

One of the goals is to raise awareness and for people to become more conscious about the related issues. TreeDependent puts tangible options and tools in people's hands, letting them take responsibility for their action/footprints.

Democratic energy future

A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

The partners (the clients) decide for themselves how much responsibility they wish to take. Schools (where the trees are planted) can also decide how many and what kind of trees they want to plant – taking into account external limitations. In the case of communities, they decide about everything; the project only facilitates the process.

Citizen power/control

Citizens can express their views, but their views are not necessarily taken into account

When distributing trees for planting, the project pays special attention to social aspects, such as involving institutions that deal with people with special needs or who have a disadvantaged background. The hosts receive the trees for free.

On the other side, the trees have a fixed price, but the calculation/the service provided by the project is adjusted to the customer, making the project more equal. For example, multinational companies pay a higher price, while for individuals the service is free; in the case of communities, the price is tailored to the circumstances.

Equity and justice

Involvement is fully open

The SDG goals of “responsible production and consumption”, taking “climate action” and “creating partnerships” are mentioned and **the goal of the whole project is to reduce our (people's, organization's, companies' etc.) carbon footprint, take responsibility for it and to draw the attention to the carbon limit.**

Carbon limit

Explicit recognition with mention/objective of reaching the max. carbon footprint

Environmental sustainability

Environmental sustainability is a core issue, and is considered in goal setting

The activity itself mainly aims at carbon compensation and protecting biodiversity by planting trees. This activity is strongly related to environmental issues. Usually, the first step is to calculate the carbon emission of an event or a person's travel and then reduce it, while avoiding greenwashing. **The project only works with partners who are willing to reduce their carbon footprint and do not only want to compensate it.**

Furthermore, TreeDependent adopts a more holistic approach: in addition to reducing carbon emissions and other environmental impact, preserving biodiversity through planting local species is an important objective.

Further information

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Aran Islands Energy Cooperative

Summary

The Aran Islands Energy Co-operative (CFOAT) is a community-owned energy cooperative on the Aran Islands at the mouth of Galway Bay. Through the cooperative, the residents of the three islands aim to become self-sufficient in clean, locally owned energy and to build the local economy of the islands, harnessing the benefits that arise from this. The main activities are related to energy efficiency and retrofitting of houses, renewable energy generation, the electrification of mobility, and participation in research projects.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

The case is exemplary as an energy-holistic energy community with strong civic engagement. The cooperative's purpose does not only concern climate issues but the survival of an independent island community and is linked to far-reaching transformative ambitions and actions.

HOLISTIC

COLLECTIVE

RURAL

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Goals

1. Stabilising and sustainably increasing the population on the three islands;
2. Maintaining the language, culture, and heritage of the three islands;
3. Being sensitive to the beauty and richness of the natural environment on the islands;
4. Increasing the comfort, energy efficiency and sustainability of homes and transport;
5. Promoting the three Aran Islands as lighthouse communities, offering inspiration, support, and examples of best practices to other communities in Ireland and throughout the world.

The story and the typology

Regarding the cooperative, which started in 2012, there has been no change in the main type of energy citizenship. Regarding the secondary ideal type, it is worth noting that it started out as organisationally embedded and then shifted its focus to households. Regarding the outcome orientation, the case has remained transformative throughout its history.

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

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Phase 1: Aran Island Development Cooperative, 2012

CFOAT emerged from the Aran Island Development Cooperative in 2012. In this cooperative, a group of people worked on the energy transition issue as a subcommittee, out of which they formed the CFOAT cooperative. Thus, there was an element of organisationally embedded agency at the beginning of the case, which is displayed as the secondary type in the table.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead
Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Do it their way (within hybrid organisations)
Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Phase 2: Early years, 2012-2017

Especially in the first few years, the main focus of the case was on participation in the Better Energy Community scheme of the Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland (SEAI). As part of this scheme, households were supported to retrofit their houses and install heat pumps and solar panels. Therefore, a shift from the original, organisational secondary type of case towards involvement at the household level is shown in the figure (type 2).

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead
Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Do their own (in the household)
Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Phase 3: EU-funded projects as key enabler, 2017-2021

Since the start of the case, a key factor was the ongoing leadership of a committed champion who has led and shaped the cooperative since its inception. After 2017, collaboration with academic partners in EU-funded projects became a key enabler, allowing the creation of paid positions. These positions provided not only the capacity but also ongoing commitment to the further development of the case. However, to some extent, reliance on project funding also impaired the case

as there was a need to prioritise funded project goals over organisational goals and ambitions.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead
Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Do their own (in the household)
Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Phase 4: Recent development after the reformulation of goals, 2022 -

One recent development was the reformulation of goals in 2022. While the actual operational goals of the case, which have significant transformative elements, have not been changed, there has been a reframing of the very purpose of the cooperative. The newly formulated goals are much more focused on the well-being of the islanders, including the preservation of the culture, language and identity of the island communities. The envisaged energy transition has become a means to an end for this purpose.

	Individual			Collective	
 9. Do the job					
 10. Make their claims					

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Do their own (in the household)

Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

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The aspects of energy citizenship

In 2019, the cooperative had around 100 members, which represents a considerable share of the 1,300 residents of the three islands. Each of the three islands is represented in the cooperative, at least through participation in board meetings. **The cooperative has the aspiration to be representative of the communities on the three islands.** It has reached out to all the communities to get broad support for its strategic objectives. This is reflected in the newly formulated goals that focus on benefits for the community.

Citizen power/control
Citizens exert effective control, and their votes have to be taken into account

Addressing climate change and reducing carbon missions is a key concern of the cooperative. **In its “Energy Master Plan”, the ambition to achieve carbon neutrality on the Aran Islands by 2022 is formulated.**

Carbon limit
Explicit recognition with mention/objective of reaching the max. carbon footprint

CFOAT is intended to be “the vehicle through which all the island residents can share their opinion on the clean energy transition” and “to **act as an open and island-wide platform** that consists of and is supported by actors from multiple stakeholder groups that drive the energy transition process”. It is thus a prime example of a case where citizens engage in the democratic self-governance of their environment.

Democratic energy future
A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

Membership in the cooperative is open to all residents of the three islands. Beyond that, **anybody is allowed to join the annual meetings as a non-voting participant, not only the members.** Centrally, the case focuses on the Aran Islands as its geographical scope. Measures are not specifically geared to fostering equity within the communities but to creating prosperity and improving the self-determination of the Aran Islands as a whole.

Equity and justice
Equal access is granted, but limited by various criteria

Environmental concerns and protection are at the heart of the cooperative, for instance, when aiming at being “sensitive to the beauty and richness of the natural environment in which we live”. **The biodiversity crisis is mentioned as a key source of motivation for the case.** Regarding operative goals, energy remains the main focus.

Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability is part of the process; energy remains the main focus

Further information

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Citizens' Assembly on “How the state can make Ireland a leader in tackling climate change”

Summary

In 2017, a citizens' assembly of 100 participants, chosen to be representative of the Irish population, engaged in a deliberative process. Following impartial and factual advice from experts, they were tasked with discussing the question, “How can the state make Ireland a leader in tackling climate change?”. The process resulted in a report comprising a series of recommendations for the attention of the Parliament of the Republic of Ireland.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

The Citizen's Assembly on Climate Change represents the institutional context for effective participation by individual citizens in the area of climate and energy. It underlines that energy citizenship in its public form is not limited to a singular act of voting but can involve participation in a distinct and deliberative process.

HOLISTIC

INDIVIDUAL

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Goals

1. Allowing a cross-section of the public to hear presentations from experts and civil society groups and to engage in rational and reasoned discussion, following the principles of deliberative democracy.
2. Formulating recommendations to the Irish Parliament on how the state can move forward in addressing climate change
3. Contributing to wider public engagement and national debate on the issue according to recommendations

The story and the typology

The perspective of energy citizenship Citizens' Assembly on “How the state can make Ireland a leader in tackling climate change” is one of public agency. The main ideal type of the case is more reformative (Type 5, “Make their voice heard”), but it also has some transformative features (Type 6, “Make their vote count” indicated as secondary).

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE](#)

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The climate assembly as a case was a one-time event in 2017. It is not ongoing.

The general topic of the Assembly was determined in the mandate of the Parliament, yet setting the agenda for the specific issues to be addressed was a pivotal issue. In preparation for the Assembly, a Steering group consisting of ten elected members of the Assembly was formed, which, in collaboration with the Secretariat, prepared a draft work programme. Submissions made by the public prior to the event also fed into this process.

At the event itself, the plenary of all participating citizens was again asked for input, thus giving them considerable say in the framing of the discussion and substance of the Assembly. The preparation of the draft recommendations on which the Assembly would eventually vote featured a similar iterative process between the Secretariat and Assembly members. Moreover, this process was supported by an Expert Advisory Group.

A major part of the deliberation involved refining the exact wording of the recommendations while ensuring that the deliberation was fair, informative and evidence-based – key principles of deliberative democracy.

Overall, participating citizens had considerable agency in the agenda-setting related to climate change in Ireland. And although the recommendations of the Assembly were not formally compulsory, they could hardly be ignored by the Parliament in the subsequent shaping of energy policy. Thus, from the perspective of energy citizenship, the case is one of public agency. The main ideal type of the case is more reformative (type 5), as it was not compulsory. Still, it has some transformative features (type 6, indicated as secondary), as there was real citizen involvement and a substantial impact on results.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims
Transformative					

Main type: Make their voice heard
Reformative outcome / Public agency

Secondary type: Make their vote count
Transformative outcome / Public agency

The aspects of energy citizenship

The participating citizens had considerable agency in agenda-setting related to what they wanted to deliberate about. **The resulting recommendations had strong legitimacy and were hard to ignore, although not formally compulsory.** A key issue was ensuring the quality of deliberation according to the principles of deliberative democracy that guided the Assembly. It was important to structure a discussion that was “fair, informative and evidence-based based.”

It is a core concern of the Citizens’ Assemblies to give citizens more voice in policymaking – in this case, on the matter of climate, including energy. **The case adhered to the principles of deliberative democracy.** Although the recommendations are not formally compulsory, they increased the pressure on the government but also increased the legitimacy to act on climate-related governance.

Citizen power/control

Citizens can express their views, but their views are not necessarily taken into account

Due to its focus on climate change, carbon emissions and the necessity of meeting the 1.5 °C target were the central issues of the case. **Recommendations on how the state could reduce carbon emissions covered the transport, energy and agriculture sectors due to their key role in Ireland’s carbon emissions.**

Carbon limit

Explicit recognition with mention/objective of reaching the max. carbon footprint

Democratic energy future

A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

FOCUS ON DISADVANTAGED GROUPS

Although access to the assembly was randomised and thus limited for most citizens, it was designed to accurately represent the Irish public in relation to the factors of age, gender, social class and regional distribution. The deliberation itself adhered to the principles of deliberative democracy, which includes transparency, mutual respect and the equality of voice. Issues related to **fairness, climate justice and social justice made up a considerable portion of the public submissions prior to the event.**

Equity and justice

Involvement is fully open

The focus of the assembly was on how the state should address climate change. **This was approached in a holistic manner, including the (governing of) the transport, energy and agriculture sectors.** Energy nevertheless remained a central aspect, even if not exclusively.

Environmental sustainability

Environmental sustainability is part of the process; energy remains the main focus

Further information

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CLUSTER 2 CASES:

Name of case in English:	Country
Berlin Energy Citizen	DE
Trégor Energ'éthiques	FR
Biomass briquettes programme (for the energy poor)	HU
Energy Communities Tipperary Cooperative	IE
Galway Energy Co-operative	IE
Loenen Energy	NL
National Association of Active Residents	NL
Weert Energy	NL

Berlin Energy Citizen

Summary

BEB - BürgerEnergie Berlin eG - is a cooperative that brings citizens together to work for a sustainable, climate-friendly, citizen-owned energy system in Berlin. It is a free cross-party association of citizens.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

BEB is focused on citizen's empowerment regarding the energy system at the city scale. It aims at developing involvement in citizen energy in Berlin and at empowering citizens in the energy transition, first by fostering citizen commitment in the management of the publicly owned electricity network and second through renewable energy generation, notably tenant electricity (*Mieterstrom*)

DIRECT ENERGY
PRODUCTION /
CONSUMPTION

COLLECTIVE

URBAN

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Bürger Energie Berlin

Goals

1. Putting the energy supply in Berlin in the hands of its citizens with the help of the cooperative;
2. Furthering the energy transition in Berlin by phasing out fossil fuels and transitioning to renewable energy sources;
3. Setting an example with their cooperative and its role in empowering citizens to engage actively in the energy system and its transition.

The story and the typology

In the beginning, BEB aimed to buy shares in the energy grid in Berlin so that direct citizen participation would be possible, which can be seen as a very transformative goal. After the “re-municipalisation” of the grid, the cancellation of municipal elections, and the respective new voting process, this became less possible, at least in the immediate future, so BEB focused on being a platform for citizen participation and tenant electricity projects. This was more aimed at working with the current system and thus had a more reformative purpose regarding the overall goals, whilst the initial plans were very transformative. This shift is mainly reflected in the changes in secondary energy citizenship ideal types.

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

Phase 1: Creation of the case, 2011

The main goal of the BürgerEnergie Berlin (BEB) cooperative is to transform Berlin's energy industry into a decentralised, sustainable and socially oriented industry.

BEB was founded in 2011 as a cooperative by individual citizens and took part in the concession procedure as a bidder for the electricity grid in Berlin but lost to the Berlin state, which was still an outcome that BEB supported. However, as a result, BEB has not been able to establish citizen participation either in the decision-making processes regarding the electricity grid in Berlin or in terms of citizens' ownership of shares in the power grid, which were central goals for the initiative.

In August 2021, the co-founder Arwen Colell became part of the supervisory board of the now re-municipalised Berlin energy grid, which BEB sees as a step toward its original goal.

Until now, BEB has contributed significantly to drawing attention to the issue, and it is still an achievement for the initiative that the energy grid is now back in the hands of the city government. The cooperative has emerged as a nationwide example of an energy cooperative trying to gain ownership of public infrastructure and as a player in the re-municipalisation campaign.

	Individual			Collective	
 9. Do the job					
 6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims			

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Make their claims

Transformative outcome / Social movements agency

BürgerEnergie Berlin

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Phase 2: Last state, since 2021-

In 2021, they did not successfully achieve one of their main founding goals, acquiring the electricity grid in Berlin, because the state of Berlin won the bid. Changes in the case are mainly connected to growth and maybe fields of action because the initiative's initial aims did not seem to be achievable in the near future.

In the beginning, their activities were exclusively directed at achieving direct citizen participation in the decision-making process regarding energy infrastructure in Berlin, namely the electricity grid. This is still their primary goal, but they have further developed into a bigger platform for informing citizens about these topics.

They also started to actively initiate citizen energy projects such as balcony plants and tenant electricity in cooperation with housing associations, for example. Generally, they have grown significantly in terms of members to 1,500 in 2023, established themselves as a reliable partner for cooperation and information platform and expanded their networks.

However, their legal form as a cooperative, which is the main characteristic of the initiative, has not changed at all. Their focus on democratising the

energy infrastructure and furthering the energy transition is still the main focus that shapes their activities. In this sense, the ENCI collective ideal-type “Go ahead” and the kind of actors who are involved have stayed the same. However, it could be argued that the initiative's goals have become less transformative over time (But the secondary ideal type has also remained the transformative and collective “make their claims”, as it is still transformative, notably through the social movement lens). The new focus of the case's activities has also led to the emergence of new secondary types (Type 1).

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types:

Do their bit (in the household)

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Make their claims

Transformative outcome / Social movements agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

The aspects of energy citizenship

Citizens can participate by becoming members of the cooperative; **every member has one vote, no matter how many shares in the cooperative they have.** There is a possibility to share membership and the cost of shares and people can contribute by volunteering. **The decisions that are reached during this process are binding;** they are especially valued because citizens make them.

Citizen control
Citizens exert effective control, and their votes have to be taken into account

There is no explicit mention of the ecological limit of atmospheric carbon emissions or sustainable carbon footprint. But **despite the lack of formal references to either, the case is involved in activities to reduce the consumption and/or emission of carbon.**

Carbon limit
Implicit recognition of the carbon limit

A more democratic energy future is literally the core of BEB's goal, specifically for Berlin, but they also want to set an example for other regions. The power grid in Berlin was owned by Vattenfall, but **BEB wanted to bring ownership back to the city of Berlin so that citizens could influence the decision-making process regarding the power grid more easily.** They see their role in this as having made the process related to the Berlin power grid and the importance of this infrastructure for the energy transition more public and transparent.

Democratic energy future
A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

FOCUS ON DISADVANTAGED GROUPS

Access is rather open, but to be involved, individuals have to buy at least one share. Issues related to energy poverty and inclusivity are not explicitly addressed, but **there are options for people who cannot afford to pay for shares on their own to obtain cooperative membership,** and the chance to participate in the cooperative through volunteer work.

Equity and justice
Equal access is granted, but limited by various criteria

Environmental sustainability is the main reason why the cooperation wanted to take the energy grid in Berlin into the hands of citizens. **The transition to renewable energy can be carried out simply by giving citizens' votes in the first place but also, for example, by citizens initiating energy production themselves such as by using PV on roofs or balconies.**

Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability is a core issue, and is considered in goal setting

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Trégor Energ'ethic

Summary

Trégor Energ'étiques is a local association based in Trégor, Brittany, that is working to accelerate the development of solar energy on their territory and raise awareness of citizen-led renewable energy projects, energy sufficiency and efficiency. The idea was born from the first solar project on the roof of a municipal sports facility and was realised with the support of the regional renewable energy network.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

The case shows how active energy citizens can mobilise and create collective engagement on their territory. By joining forces with similar projects in the region, the association is now part of a regional ecosystem that supports citizen-led renewable energy production.

DIRECT ENERGY
PRODUCTION /
CONSUMPTION

COLLECTIVE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Goals

1. Developing photovoltaic projects in the area that the association is active;
2. Raising awareness about energy and citizen-based renewable energy projects among the public and different stakeholders;
3. Developing educational resources and tools for communication about energy sufficiency and efficiency.

The story and the typology

The initiative was launched in 2019 by two representatives of the Local Development Council and members of Enercoop. With support from the regional renewables network TARANIS, these two individuals successfully organised a public documentary screening to mobilise citizens to create the association. The initiation of the case was thus enacted through the individual agency of these two individuals within the organisational setting of the Local Development Council (type 4, see illustration below). Once the association was established to raise awareness and support citizen-based renewable energy projects on their territory, Trégor Ener'g'éthiques enacted and enabled collective participation in the energy transition (type 8).

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Phase 1: The creation of the case in 2019

Trégor Energ'éthiques was founded in June 2019. Being members of the Local Development Council facilitated the two co-founders' decision to create the association and put them in contact with the right actors (type 4). Through their support, the two individuals were able to mobilise and launch the association that is engaging in the energy transition, particularly with citizen-owned and financed renewable energy.

Main type: Do it their way (within organizations)
Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Secondary type: Make their voice heard
Reformative outcome / Public agency

Phase 2: Association up and running, establishment of Kerwatt SAS in 2020

Once the association was up and running, the case was able to undertake collective endeavours, moving from type 4 to 8. The most significant development that simplified the administrative, legal, and financial aspects of the development of photovoltaics for the association during this phase was the creation of the joint-stock company Kerwatt and three other similar associations in the region.

and organisations to practice energy citizenship (types 1, 3 and 4).

Main type: Go ahead
Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types
Do their bit (in the household)
Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency
Do their bit (within organizations)
Reformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency
Do it their way (within organizations)
Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Through establishing Kerwatt regionally, the case solidified its collective agency while keeping the objective of transformative change of the energy system that has characterised the case from the beginning (see 'the aspects of energy citizenship' in the following pages). Through their work, in addition to supporting others in setting up similar associations, the association supports households

Phase 3: Current state, 2020-

Having developed a seemingly sustainable business model wherein the local association Trégor Energ'éthiques does the prospecting and identifies viable projects, after which Kerwatt takes over to finance and implement them, Trégor Energ'éthiques is now pursuing additional goals, in particular, related to awareness-raising.

While the functioning of the case stabilised during this last phase, nothing changed about the ideal-type categorisation from phases 2 to 3.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Collective agency

Secondary types

Do their bit (in the household)

Reformative outcome / Individual agency

Do their bit (within organizations)

Reformative outcome / Individual agency

Do it their way (within organizations)

Transformative outcome / Individual agency

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The aspects of energy citizenship

The association was initiated and is driven by individual citizens. The members of the general assembly elect the board, which may consist of up to 16 members. The board has the “broadest” powers to administer the association but is responsible to the general assembly and regulated by the association’s statutes. Decisions in the general assembly are also taken according to the majority principle.

Citizen control

Citizens exert effective control, and their votes have to be taken into account

There are no formal references to the ecological limit of atmospheric carbon emissions or sustainable carbon footprint. The latter is, however, implicitly recognised by key figures in the association. In the preamble, “climate change” is mentioned as one of three key contextual factors that motivate its activities that contribute to reducing carbon emissions.

Carbon limit

Implicit recognition of the carbon limit

Creating a more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case. In its statutes of January 19, 2022, **the core purposes of the association** are outlined, all of which **have a bearing on creating a more democratic energy future**. The involvement of citizens in the deployment of renewable energies pertains to citizen ownership, control, and benefits of energy production. Supporting the emergence of similar citizen-led local projects targets overcoming the barriers associated with technical, financial and legal knowledge that is necessary for democratizing the energy system.

Democratic energy future

A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

Equal access is ensured and the membership fee of €10 is purely symbolic. The association is, however, a local case, and membership, while not limited, is more likely to occur within the association’s geographical area. Other than the small membership fee, the socioeconomic bias (towards more educated/well-off citizens) does not seem to be mitigated in any concrete way.

Equity and justice

Equal access is granted, but limited by various criteria

Consistency (developing photovoltaic projects), **as well as efficiency and sufficiency** (developing educational tools to promote sufficiency and efficiency) **are part of the case’s objectives and vision for the energy system**. “The vision consists first in reducing needs through sufficiency in individual and collective energy uses. Efficiency then makes it possible to reduce the quantity of energy necessary to satisfy these needs which should be covered by energy from renewable sources”.

Environmental sustainability

Environmental sustainability is a core issue, and is considered in goal setting

Further information

facebook.com/Trégor-Energétiques

youtube.com/channel/UCVmQVOIBKHNLVfF4oPyG77Q

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Biomass briquettes for the energy poor

HUNGARY

Summary

The biomass briquettes (“Biobriquettes”) programme was established in a disadvantaged region of Hungary where the unemployment rate is higher than the national average, and many people live below the poverty line. The target area is a Roma village whose inhabitants are a socially marginalised group in Hungary with even less access to combustible materials for heating. The project was developed by the Real Pearl Foundation and Art School. The project contributes to creating new jobs and strengthening the community, reducing the heating costs of families involved, and saving local forests from being illegally cut down.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

It is a unique feature that NGOs that were initially dealing with social problems tried to find a solution that combines improving quality of life with an environmental sustainability approach. The Biobriquettes program uses cheap technology to create more environmentally friendly, energy-efficient, and lower-cost living conditions.

DIRECT ENERGY
PRODUCTION /
CONSUMPTION

COLLECTIVE

RURAL

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

IGAZGYÖNGY
ALAPÍTVÁNY

Goals

1. Enabling people in need to heat their homes (healthily and effectively, at a decent price), thereby reducing energy poverty;
2. Eliminating pollution and raising environmental awareness by hand-making biomass briquettes, a cheap, environmentally friendly fuel;
3. Decreasing the illegal procurement of heating fuel (e.g. stealing of timber).

The story and the typology

After the project's initial (“dreamlike”) start and evolution, it is no longer improving or changing. Even though the infrastructure and the raw materials are available, the NGO has struggled to motivate the local population to participate – despite offering job opportunities and a cheap or free fuel source. Thus, the case has changed regarding the level of activity it has managed to inspire. The method and the circumstances have not changed, and the NGO hopes it will be able to change local attitudes in the future.

Case history summary

For the summary
methodology,
click [HERE!](#)

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Phase 1: Creation and setting up, 2011 - 2018

It was a “lucky combination” of circumstances that this project emerged from scratch. A hot summer coincided with some agricultural residue and the availability of volunteers, so the case started relatively informally. First and foremost, the leader of the Real Pearl Foundation, who is inspirational due to her personality and attitude towards innovation, strives to go one step further and make the impossible possible.

The technology used for starting bio-briquette production was pioneered in the region because of the low-tech approach, using locally available agricultural waste. An expert, Nóra Feldmár, played a major role in the introduction of the technology, helping to adapt a model she had seen in other communities in connection with her master thesis. The entire approach of the Real Pearl Foundation towards helping families break out of generational poverty is also unique and pioneering. The Biobriquettes programme was intended to be part

Phase 2: Facing challenges, from 2018 -

In 2018, after the briquetting machine was introduced and took over much of the work that had been done by hand, a new phase began. The volunteers continued working with local residents, but the improved technical situation did not help avoid the gradual decline in the activity of the programme. This was because 1) it has been challenging to maintain the motivation of the locals, especially when utility costs (gas, electricity, timber) are controlled by the central government and are maintained at a relatively low price (‘to protect poor families from price fluctuations’) and also because both hand-pressed and straw briquettes have more ash and therefore requires more cleaning and attention; 2) the leaders of the host foundation do

of this overall approach by creating a longer-term solution for heating homes based on local resources and, at the same time, employing local people (who can later use the briquettes they produce).

The main social advantage of these technologies lies in their simplicity; using them makes the community more self-sufficient, independent and confident, while local residents can easily participate and learn the necessary skills and competencies.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way within organizations	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

not see real long-term political will to make substantial social change; and 3) the foundation itself has energy-related problems due to the energy crisis that started in 2022.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way within organizations	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

The aspects of energy citizenship

The aim of the foundation is to **prepare the community for a democratized and self-governed future** so that the foundation's efforts will ultimately not be needed and they can be phased out. The foundation wants the locals to be capable of taking control of and managing their own lives. Thus, it is a core concern, and they aim to **provide power to residents so they can heat their homes without relying on external sources of fuel.**

The foundation has the leadership to set goals and achieve them. **Participating locals have autonomy in terms of deciding whether they seize the opportunity**, work to make the briquettes, or only buy them at a low-price, so they are not part of the project's decision making, yet they still influence the programme through their behaviour.

Democratic energy future
A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

Citizen power/control
Citizens exert effective control, and their votes have to be taken into account

FOCUS ON DISADVANTAGED GROUPS

Beside some geographical limitations (locals mainly participate in the project, and mobility is an issue in the region), anyone can join, participate in the production of briquettes, and benefit from the outcomes. **This enables a reduction in energy poverty with no gender barriers or other criteria for involvement.**

Equity and justice
Involvement is fully open

Although not explicitly mentioned, **environmentally friendly fuel production replaces more carbon-intensive emission sources and unsustainable consumption practices.**

Carbon limit
Implicit recognition of the carbon limit

The primary goal is alleviating energy poverty, but environmental concerns were part of the technological development process and an **ecologically friendly material is the outcome. The input material is also eco-friendly** by nature (using agricultural by-products/residue). Further, the method of producing the briquettes is **low-tech and low-energy intensity.**

Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability is part of the process; energy remains the main focus

Further information

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Energy Communities Tipperary Cooperative (ECTC)

DIRECT ENERGY
PRODUCTION /
CONSUMPTION

RURAL

COLLECTIVE

Summary

Energy Community Tipperary Cooperative ECTC brings together 14 communities in the Tipperary region. It aims to enable communities in Tipperary and surrounding areas to create local employment and to benefit from reducing their carbon footprints and generating community-owned energy. ECTC facilitates energy efficiency work on older houses and community buildings by leveraging grants from the Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland and the Just Transition Fund.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

ECTC shows the collective agency of civic engagement. It emerged as a community initiative and has since activated and supported other communities to become active – a cooperative of communities. ECTC's main concern has been with retrofitting houses to improve efficiency.

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Goals

Overall, ECTC has the mission of “allow[ing] communities in Tipperary and surrounding areas to create local employment and community benefit through reducing their carbon footprint and generating community-owned energy”. Through this, it strives towards its vision “of a community-led energy transition, which benefits communities, creates warmer, healthier homes while saving homeowners money, helps tackle climate change, and in a post-COVID world helps create new employment” (Energy Master Plan).

More concretely, ECTC goals include:

1. Citizen empowerment by helping communities to become more resilient, especially regarding their energy use;
2. Using energy efficiency and generation as a means and driver of local economic benefit;
3. Keeping money and jobs in the area, creating employment

The story and the typology

Since ECTC's emergence in 2012, four phases can be distinguished in the evolution of energy citizenship. Whereas the formation of the case in Phase 1 was marked by agency embedded in another organisation, the main form of agency since then has been collective and community-based (classified as Type 8 in the EnergyPROSPECTS typology). The differentiation between phases 2-4 is due to other factors, as outlined below.

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

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Phase 1: Emergence of the case and its establishment as a cooperative, 2012 - 2014

The genesis of the case was linked to a community team exploring ways to improve the area's economic development. The emerging organisation first ran as a pilot project of the Tipperary Energy Agency, involving four communities. The focus on energy and retrofitting ultimately led to the formation of ECTC as an organised citizen-driven initiative in the form of a cooperative in 2014.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do it their way
Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Phase 2: Developing from individual to collective agency, 2014 - 2019

The establishment as a cooperative marked the beginning of the second phase. This meant a clear shift from organisationally embedded agency to new collective agency in the form of the newly founded organisation (cf. the arrow in the figure). While retaining its general transformative outcome orientation, this was reinforced by the continuously growing number of communities joining the cooperative, which necessitated the forging of a suitable internal governance structure.

another form of secondary agency. With the main focus of ECTC being leveraging grants for home retrofits, the participating homeowners – the “target group” of the case’s activities – express agency by committing to these retrofits and financing a substantial part of the investment.

At the same time, the organisationally embedded agency described in Phase 1 continued to play a role even after ECTC was formalised as a cooperative, specifically in the communities that have become new members over the years. Usually, these new member communities build on or emerge from pre-existing community groups with another focus, e.g., tidy town groups, local development teams, etc. Furthermore, private agency in households became

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead
Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types:
Do it their way
Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency
Do their bit
Reformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Phase 3: Focusing on renewables and becoming a trusted point of contact on community engagement, 2019 - 2023 and ongoing

While still growing in terms of the number of member communities, in an (ongoing) third phase, ECTC has advanced in two significant ways. First, it has expanded its focus to include new leadership roles by investigating options for community-owned renewable energy generation, not least in developing an Energy Master Plan. Second, ECTC has become a trusted point of contact for the Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland (SEAI) – a government-funded agency – in respect of providing policy advice and programme implementation. ECTC has gained legitimacy through its expertise and working “on the ground” concerning issues of community engagement in energy-related governance and is regularly contacted for advice.

Furthermore, ECTC plans to collaborate more with local councils, especially when providing information for residents and their communities. During this phase, the expression of energy citizenship agency did not fundamentally change.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types:

Do it their way

Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Do their bit

Reformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

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The aspects of energy citizenship

The project aims at **creating a more democratic, and in the longer run, self-sufficient energy system, first, by strengthening local communities both socially and economically, and, second, in the longer term, through promoting and enabling the community ownership of renewable energy.** It actively contributes to raising energy awareness, reducing energy poverty, strengthening community and providing financial benefits locally.

In this case, citizen power/control is a key aspect, with **elements of self-governance**. “**Belief and trust in people**” and “**principles of community cooperation and self-organising**” are stated to be core values. The cooperative is made up of local communities, which themselves are represented by local community councils and development associations, which are usually perceived as being democratic institutions.

Citizen power/control
Citizens exert effective control, and their votes have to be taken into account

As with the “environmental sustainability” goal, environmental limits and carbon footprints are not directly mentioned in organisational goals but are taken into account through the acknowledgment of the goals of the Irish Government, and are important context for the case.

Carbon limit
Implicit recognition of the carbon limit

Democratic energy future
A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

The case touches upon **core aspects of justice and equity, especially those related to energy poverty.** It emerged from a situation after the financial crisis after 2008, by which the Tipperary region was heavily impacted. Energy-saving measures implemented in the context of ECTC were one instrument for easing the economic burden and revitalising local economies. Fuel poverty is specifically addressed. However, issues of justice and equity are delineated by the geographical focus of the case.

Equity and justice
Equal access is granted, but limited by various criteria

The main rationale of the case is using energy-related measures for the purpose of local (economic) development. **Environmental sustainability aspects are acknowledged and are a part of the motivation, but not necessarily central ones.** Assumptions about the benefits for sustainability of using renewables (compared to fossil fuel-based energy) and energy are acknowledged, but have not been made primary goals.

Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability issues are not explicitly taken into account

Further information

[facebook.com/EnergyCommunitiesTipp](https://www.facebook.com/EnergyCommunitiesTipp)

www.youtube.com/channel/UCwRW3ZO3zillyIkW1gamc9Q

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Galway Energy Co-operative

Summary

The Galway Energy Co-operative is an organisation that aims to advocate for the provision of clean, renewable energy and services for Galway City and the surrounding area. As a member of the Sustainable Energy Communities Initiative Network, the cooperative has been coordinating an Energy Master Plan for the city of Galway and offers consultancy services.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

Galway Energy Co-operative exhibits collective energy citizenship in that the locally embedded cooperative is engaged in various activities related to the energy transition in Galway City. This especially concerns coordinating and developing an energy masterplan for the city.

HOLISTIC

URBAN

COLLECTIVE

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Goals

1. Developing renewable energy to support climate change mitigation efforts: To be an advocate for the provision of clean, renewable energy and services for Galway City and the surrounding area.
2. Democratising energy production – increase the resilience of Galway City communities and develop local employment opportunities.
3. Engaging the knowledge, energy and expertise of the local community.

The story and the typology

Galway Energy Co-operative was only established in 2018. Abrupt disruption by the COVID-19 pandemic in subsequent years affected the early momentum of the case. We have therefore identified three phases in the case so far.

Case history summary

For the summary
methodology,
click [HERE!](#)

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Phase 1: Creation and initial phase, 2018 - 2019

When the cooperative was established in 2018, it defined transformative goals (democratising energy production). These goals have remained the same until today.

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Phase 2: COVID-19 years, 2019 - 2021

The development of the cooperative in the years 2019 to 2021 was strongly affected by the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, as this hampered its early momentum. This phase was also characterised by a degree of ambiguity between the aforementioned long-term, transformative goals and visions of the cooperative on the one hand (community involvement in energy in Galway City) and concrete activities and short-term goals on the other. The latter tended to be reformative in orientation (focus on energy storage) and emanated from individual members of the cooperative rather than from the organisation as a whole. This pointed to a need for more fundamental strategising to translate long-term goals into concrete actions and responsibilities. Overall, this phase was thus characterised by more pronounced expressions of

individual energy citizenship within the context of the cooperative (rather than collective action by the cooperative itself), which can be associated with the Ideal Type 4 according to the EnergyPROSPECTS typology.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Do it their way

Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

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Phase 3: Current state, 2021 -

In Phase 3, since 2021, the cooperative has been working to regain momentum after the COVID-related years. In the context of conducting community engagement workshops in Galway City, working with Galway City Council to create a decarbonisation zone, and developing an energy master plan, the cooperative is now creating internal structures that will ensure its ability to act and provide the necessary strategic direction for the future.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

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The aspects of energy citizenship

The democratization of the energy system is listed as **one of four main goals** of GEC and relates strongly to the cooperative's long-term vision. 'Democratization of energy' is understood as **increasing the share of energy consumption that is locally generated from renewable sources**, either in the form of self-consumption, by neighbours, or through other local sources.

The case exhibits high levels of citizen control as it is organised in the legal form of **a cooperative, which works according to democratic principles**. The implementation of community engagement workshops also indicates that the cooperative **envisages the greater involvement of citizens and residents in its activities**, not least by implementing community engagement workshops.

Democratic energy future

A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

Citizen power/control
Citizens exert effective control, and their votes have to be taken into account

Access to the cooperative is open to the public. It currently consists of five members. Motivating new members has been a side goal of community outreach events. Furthermore, the cooperative references the Sustainable Development Goals, including the issues of energy poverty, inclusivity and gender equality.

Equity and justice
Equal access is granted, but limited by various criteria

The main focus of GEC is expanding local renewables for the purpose of **improving community resilience and mitigating carbon emissions and climate change**. One of the main goals is "to develop renewable energy to support climate change mitigation efforts". Furthermore, there is explicit recognition of environmental limits in the work of the cooperative – for instance, in its **involvement in 'Decarbonisation zones'**, which prescribe a concrete quantity of emission reductions.

Carbon limit
Explicit recognition of the carbon limit

Although the major focus is local communities, the case does **acknowledge environmental sustainability, not least by relying on the Sustainable Development Goals in relation to its community engagement action**. Although not explicitly mentioned as a stated goal, environmental sustainability is considered an important motivation. Overall, **the cooperative focuses on energy**, especially renewables, and to a lesser extent on house retrofitting and energy efficiency.

Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability is part of the process; energy remains the main focus

Further information

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Source of images

www.galwayenergy.coop

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Loenen Energy

Summary

The story of Loenen Energy started in the village of Loenen in east Netherlands. In 2013, a group of enthusiastic residents won a competition organised by the municipality of Apeldoorn for the best sustainable idea, called: ‘the Energetic Village’. This one-off subsidy triggered a long-term process for Loenen via the Loenen Energy Fund (LEF). The aim of this fund was to achieve ‘full energy neutrality for Loenen by 2050’. More than 300 projects have now been implemented in Loenen.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

One of the defining features of Loenen Energy is its community Virtual Power Plant (cVPP) project. The "c" in cVPP stands for "community" (i.e., everyone involved and affected) and determines how the Energy Management System is used: what values does the community consider important, and for which activities is the flexibility deployed? The implementation of the cVPP was a bottom-up process with workshops involving 100 local citizens and various local stakeholders, guided by shared values and interests.

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Goals

1. Promoting the use of renewable energy and energy conservation in its area of operation directly or indirectly for the benefit of its members;
2. Implementing (and financing) local projects;
3. Activating local people, improving social cohesion and public relations.

The story and the typology

Loenen Energy was started by a group of residents from the village of Loenen who won the 'Energetic village' competition of Apeldoorn municipality. The group needed an entity to do business with rather than citizens as a condition of accessing and implementing EU funds. Therefore, in 2014, the Loenen Energy Cooperative was established as an organisational entity to manage these EU funds. The type of agency has remained the same in all phases of the cooperative, but objectives have changed from a reformatory to a transformative type. In the first phase, the case was citizen-based but still primarily reformatory, so it was classified as "Do their share", and the transformative "Go ahead" only appeared as a secondary phase. Later, 'transformative' became the main ideal type.

Case history summary

For the summary
methodology,
click [HERE](#)

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Phase 1: Since the creation of the case in 2013 until 2017

In 2013, the municipality of Apeldoorn launched a competition for the best sustainable village idea. A number of residents from Loenen applied and won the prize, which was used to set up the Loenen Energy Fund (LEF), a local fund for financing projects related to energy savings, such as insulation and providing renewable energy expertise and financial assistance (the fund is managed by a locally based organisation called Loenen Energy Neutraal LEN). This proved to be a success, as 300 projects have since been implemented. By supporting participants with preferential purchasing and subsidies, Loenen Energy makes participation attractive, which helps to drive the energy transition.

Even at this phase, the case was a collective and citizen-based one because it was set up and managed by citizens. It still shows a primarily reformative orientation (indicated by the main type

of energy citizenship manifested in the case (Type 7). However, transformative features were already present (as indicated in the secondary type, Type 8). ‘The success driver here is the volunteers and the commitment of these volunteers [...] The participants' enthusiasm contributed to giving the board the necessary energy and motivation to continue on the chosen path’.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Phase 2 Part of an EU project consortium, 2017-2022

In 2017, the cVPP project¹ was launched under the leadership of TU Eindhoven and the Loenen Energy cooperative was established towards the end of this project to ensure continuity. Loenen was a pilot study area that participated in collaboration with Irish and Belgian partners (as part of an EU project consortium). To develop the cVPP, Interreg North-West Europe made available a grant of 850,000 euros. Besides the European grant, the Province of

Gelderland in the Netherlands also contributed financially to the implementation of the project.

In 2021, the Energy Management System (EMS), part of the cVPP of Loenen Energy, was launched, and the cooperative won the prestigious EU Sustainable Energy Award.

EMS is a smart energy management system that matches the supply and demand of renewable energy. This system is called the DE power plant

¹ Technically, the cVPP consists of close to 100 residential PV systems, an 0.9 MWp industrial PV, several steerable heat pumps and an EV-charging point, all connected through a tailor-made EMS.

and, in Loenen, involves residents in the electricity system of the future. Large energy companies are also betting on this technology, but what is special in Loenen is that the residents of Loenen themselves have control over the DE power plant. The new energy system is for and by citizens.

This shows that the project was already transformative at this phase (as shown by the change in the main ideal type to Type 8).

Phase 3: Current phase, since 2020

In addition to being an innovative cooperative with the piloting of the cVPP, Loenen Energy grew its operations not only by providing energy advice and support regarding energy measures but also by developing its own local solar farm, called Zonnendak Thomassen – the first major project developed by the Loenen Energy Cooperative - on the solar roof of the Distribution Centre Thomassen. Local residents, businesses, and organisations are co-owners and co-investors of this solar farm. The ambition of the cooperative is to use all rooftop capacity in Loenen for PV and become self-

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

supporting. However, this strategy requires smart energy management. Currently, Loenen Energy supplies 50% of household demand with local PV.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

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The aspects of energy citizenship

Loenen Energy was founded with aim of promoting the use of renewable energy in Loenen to make the village energy neutral. It is a cooperative of and for all Loenen residents. The members jointly own the cooperative. **They generate and supply energy locally and encourage, advise and support residents and entrepreneurs to make their homes and/or businesses more sustainable.**

One of Loenen Energy's key quotes is: "Benefiting from renewable energy together". **The members jointly own the cooperative. As members, they can think, talk, decide and invest.** In this way, they hope to involve as many Loenen residents as possible in the energy transition.

 Democratic energy future
A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

Citizens/residents are free to become involved (all who want to join the cooperative without any specific conditions), but they have to live in the region. To increase involvement and participation in the cooperative, **Loenen Energy aims to reduce the monthly energy payments of its members, including for people who find it challenging to participate in the cooperative.** The cooperative is aware of the lack of equity and justice associated with the energy transition. Members recognise that a large segment of society (i.e., households with medium to low incomes compared to the average) have not benefited from the national support schemes that are now being phased out.

Citizen control
Citizens exert effective control, and their votes have to be taken into account

Equity and justice
Equal access is granted, but limited by various criteria

There is no mention or recognition of the 1.5C target or environmental limits in general. **However, by focusing on building a more sustainable, decentralised energy system based on renewable sources, the initiative implicitly contributes to reducing carbon emissions and promoting cleaner production.**

Carbon limit
Implicit recognition of the carbon limit

Environmental sustainability is mentioned within the wider context of 'sustainability and glocalisation': Loenen Energy aims to do as much as possible locally, using the local revolving fund. **Creating an energy infrastructure involves facilitating awareness, decision-making and the implementation of sustainability projects** by offering organisational, knowledge-content and financial support.

Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability is part of the process; energy remains the main focus

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Further information

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Source of images

loenenenergie.nl/de-centrale ; [facebook.com/Loenenenergie](https://www.facebook.com/Loenenenergie)

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National Association of Active Residents

Summary

The National Association of Active Residents (Landelijk Samenwerkingsverband Actieve bewoners-LSA) is an association of and for groups of active residents in the Netherlands. The association is a wider national network of resident groups, independent community centres, neighbourhood cooperatives and neighbourhood enterprises ('BewonersBedrijven') who share their knowledge and expertise with others. One of the key aims of LSA is to advocate and lobby for (the goals of) resident initiatives, including at the (local and regional) government level and in national policies.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

LSA supports community and neighbourhood groups in transitioning their district heating and disconnecting from natural gas by 2030. LSA supports and guides residents' initiatives aimed at developing tailor-made solutions for self-managed heat sources. LSA is also helping neighbourhood heat initiatives to collaborate with municipalities because democratic policy instruments that offer action perspectives for both municipalities and initiatives do not yet exist.

HOLISTIC

COLLECTIVE

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Goals

1. Increasing public involvement and giving residents a shared national voice for communicating with politicians and policymakers and obtaining better support for residents' initiatives;
2. Strengthening community building, guided by the principles of equity and justice;
3. Contributing to the energy transition, offering opportunities for neighbourhood development and local democracy.

The story and the typology

The National Association of Active Residents is an association of residents' collectives in the Netherlands that acts as an intermediary at a national scale. It has not changed much in terms of its agency type: namely, citizen-based and hybrid. Its primary purpose (to act as a knowledge exchange and empowerment network for various groups of residents and to support active citizenship and agency) has remained constant since its foundation in 1985. However, its focus on the issues it supports has evolved and environmental and holistic issues have become more prominent. Thus, we have distinguished several phases in its development.

For the summary methodology, click [HERE](#)

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Phase 1: Since the creation of the case in 1985 until 2018

The National Association of Active Residents was founded in 1985 as an association of active residents' groups throughout the Netherlands who are committed to developing their neighbourhoods. Residents' groups run/own community centres, administer local funds and host essential local meeting places. They work towards a fair and social energy transition.

In the early years of the initiative, there was strong dependence on government funding. However, over time, this has changed to include more partnerships, making the case more financially diverse and less vulnerable.

Throughout the years, the form of the organisation has not changed. The initial purpose was (and remains) promoting the democratic participation of residents in disadvantaged neighbourhoods to improve their living conditions. This is reflected in

the ideal energy citizenship type defined for the case (“Go ahead”), as this is a collective, citizen-based, transformative initiative. As the initiative helps people in local groups, it also supports the individual, organisationally embedded form of energy citizenship (indicated as secondary types).

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types:

Do their bit (within organizations)

Reformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Do their way (within organizations)

Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Phase 2: Integrating environmental sustainability into reporting, 2018-2022

Since 2018, the National Association of Active Residents has focused more on environmental sustainability. One of the action points of their 2018 Annual Report was to become active in relation to the energy transition, i.e. in sustainable energy initiatives, as a new form of neighbourhood approach: this has become a goal for ensuring that the jobs and wages created by this significant task are taken up by people and organisations in the neighbourhood; and that this transition is used as a springboard for the broad and integrated upgrading of neighbourhoods and districts.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types:

Do their bit (within organizations)

Reformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Do their way (within organizations)

Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Phase 3: Focusing on broader issues since 2022

The National Association of Active Residents has expanded its scope since 2022 to cover an increasing number of social and environmental themes.

This was a logical step as the respective groups of residents are connected across all areas (such as social, economic, and environmental). They are largely driven by the same motivations, desires and interests and benefit from the same support and structures embedded in the core functions of the National Association of Active Residents.

Currently, the initiative focuses on a broad number of issues in the neighbourhoods, such as energy and sustainability, equality, care for each other,

entrepreneurship in neighbourhoods, and having a voice.

	Individual		Collective		
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types:

Do their bit (within organizations)

Reformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Do their way (within organizations)

Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

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The aspects of energy citizenship

The association is classified as in between the medium and high level of effective voice/citizen control, depending on the specific programmes. However, taking the initiative as a whole, it could be classified at the high level **as it is a forum for citizen control in decision making and an intermediary for active participation in local and national government.** It also represents new forms of local democracy.

Citizen control
Citizens exert effective control, and their votes have to be taken into account

The association does not explicitly mention environmental limits or reducing carbon footprint although one of its focal areas is related to the energy transition, SDGs, and climate crisis. **Although environmental limits are not explicitly mentioned, they are implied during the activities, case studies, and other areas of work** (e.g., in their neighbourhood, bottom-up and community approach).

Carbon limits
Implicit recognition of the carbon limit

Promoting a democratic energy future is a key goal of the association and part of its agenda. **The overall approach of the urban renewal of disadvantaged neighbourhoods and a bottom-up community approach are closely linked with their position concerning creating a more democratic energy future.** “The energy transition will have a major impact on every neighbourhood, street and resident. That is why we support residents to organise themselves, to work on their own perspectives and to build networks that take initiatives towards a more sustainable world.”

Democratic energy future

A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

FOCUS ON GENDER ISSUES

FOCUS ON DISADVANTAGED GROUPS

All members and community groups can attend the meetings of the association and receive publications and newsletters. They are part of the main national association that stands up for active residents in the Netherlands. It recognizes the energy crisis and the need to meet climate targets in the Netherlands. **The widening gap between the privileged and the underprivileged is also becoming bigger and increasingly magnified.** To respond to these challenges, the association calls for a new form of neighbourhood approach that also deals with declining confidence in the government and tough processes of democratic renewal.

Equity and justice
Involvement is fully open

Environmental sustainability is one of the focal areas of the association. It further endorses and commits to climate goals and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). While many of the residents are not always aware of the contribution of their initiatives, the association aims to familiarize residents with the SDGs, to get the discussion going and, above all, **to provide practical perspectives that help create healthier, greener and more social neighbourhoods.**

Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability is part of the process, energy remains the main focus

Further information

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twitter.com/LSAbewoners, www.lsabewoners.nl/over-ons/

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Weert Energy

NETHERLANDS

Summary

Weert Energy (Weert Energie) is a local green energy cooperative operating in the municipality of Weert in the Netherlands. Founded in 2013, the cooperative generates and supplies electricity locally at an affordable price to its members and supports citizens' measures to save energy in their living environment. The cooperative members believe they can manage the transition to green energy in Weert themselves because together, they can ensure that green energy is accessible to all Weert citizens. Weert Energy works with its members, Weert municipality, and other regional energy cooperatives to shape the energy goals Weert wants to achieve. To implement their projects, they also collaborate with local businesses.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

The cooperative structure of Weert Energy is unique in the Netherlands as it combines a cooperative neighbourhood battery (COOP-Store) with the large-scale local generation of sustainable energy. The battery project is the largest in the Netherlands and the first one. By combining the business models of self-supply, energy trade, and balance maintenance, a profitable concept may be realised.

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Goals

1. Contributing to, investing in and implementing local energy projects in the municipality of Weert for a more sustainable and affordable energy future;
2. Helping to increase the energy self-sufficiency of the region through renewable energy projects;
3. Providing financial support and advice to members and local residents and guiding them through the energy transition.

The story and the typology

Although the cooperative's business model has developed over the years, the main aims of Weert Energy remain the same. Thus, the ideal types of energy citizenship supported by the case have not changed. As this is a citizen-based initiative with a transformative focus, the main type of energy citizenship is classified as "Type 8: Go ahead".

Case history summary

For the summary
methodology,
click [HERE](#)

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Phase 1: From the creation of the case in 2013 until 2015

Weert Energy is an energy cooperative that operates in the municipality of Weert. Since 2013, the goals of this cooperative have been to contribute to sustainable energy in the Weert region, generate and supply electricity locally at an affordable price to residents, and support citizens' measures to save energy in their living environments.

As this is a citizen-based initiative with a transformative focus, the main ideal type of energy citizenship is defined as "Type 8: Go ahead".

Phase 2: Neighbourhood battery project (COOP-Store), since 2015

In 2015, Weert Energy launched its flagship pilot neighbourhood battery project called COOP-Store. This addresses how local energy generation, storage and consumption can work in a more decentralised manner and thus increase energy self-sufficiency. This was the first pilot project in the Netherlands to combine a cooperative neighbourhood battery with the large-scale local generation of sustainable energy. A special feature of this project is that Weert Energy members collectively own both the solar park and the neighbourhood battery.

The background to the pilot project is that energy storage is indispensable for maintaining the reliability of energy supply because the sun does not always shine, and the wind does not always blow. To achieve a fully sustainable energy supply, it is therefore crucial that green energy can be stored on a sunny or windy day and be used on a grey and windless day.

The project partners demonstrated that energy storage in combination with sustainable production

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

could be profitable with the aid of the Top Sector Energy Subsidy awarded by the Dutch government (RVO – the Dutch agency responsible for the implementation of innovation policy) for testing and running a "neighbourhood" battery in combination with large-scale power generation. In 2019, Weert Energy's solar park Altweeterheide, associated with a "neighbourhood" battery, became operational. Cyclists can charge their electric bicycles for free using green energy from the solar park.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

The aspects of energy citizenship

Creating a democratic energy future is a core concern for Weert Energy, as illustrated in the realisation of its large-scale local projects that aim to benefit members, local organisations and businesses, but also all the local residents of Weert. **The initiative seeks to put energy in the control of local hands, and to generate, store and use electricity at the local level and in a decentralised manner.** This gives control of energy to local residents.

Democratic energy future

A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

Weert Energy supports a high level of citizen voice and control. **The cooperative operates on the principle 'from members for members' and strives for transparency and openness.** At least twice a year a general members' meeting is held at which members make decisions by casting a vote. Decisions are based on a majority of votes.

Citizen control

Citizens exert effective control, and their votes have to be taken into account

Anyone from Weert or the surrounding area who wants to (residents, companies and organizations) can invest in the local generation of sustainable energy. Members pay an annual membership fee. **All members can attend member meetings, cast votes, receive publications, newsletters and get a free heat scan of their home and free advice about energy saving.**

Equity and justice

Equal access is granted, but limited by various criteria

There is no mention or recognition of the 1.5C target or environmental limits in general. **However, by focusing on building a more sustainable, decentralised energy system based on renewable sources, the initiative implicitly contributes to reducing carbon emissions and promoting cleaner production.**

Carbon limit

Implicit recognition of the carbon limit

The income from various projects is spent on sustainable projects within the municipality (e.g., an environmental fund). The environmental fund is now being deployed to support socially sustainable projects and cover the development costs of projects in the municipality of Weert. **Although the focus is on energy production, the initiative contributes greatly to attempts to promote environmental sustainability.**

Environmental sustainability

Environmental sustainability is part of the process; energy remains the main focus

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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CLUSTER 3 CASES:

Name of case in English:	Country
BBL Home renovation campaign	BE
Hydro Electricity Ourthe and Sambre	BE
Student Switch Off campaigns in Bulgaria	BG
Naturstrom AG	DE
La borda. Housing cooperative in transfer of use	ES
Zsuzsanna Hojtsy-Keresztény - EnergyNeighbourhoods energy master, local change maker	HU
Social media influencer "Edgar Fresh"	LV
Drechtsteden Energy	NL

BBL's home renovation campaign

Summary

Bond Beter Leefmilieu (BBL) is a Belgian umbrella organisation for Flemish environmental and nature associations, citizens, governments and companies that aims to foster the transition to a sustainable society involving a circular economy. Its activities include movement-building, lobbying and raising awareness. The initiative under discussion here is specifically their home renovation campaign, which is one of the more recent projects of BBL.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

The main focal areas of BBL are renewable energy, plant-based nutrition, sustainable agriculture, emission-free mobility, the circular economy and spatial planning. Energy is considered a transversal issue, but some campaigns have an energy focus: the home renovation campaign targets the energy performance of homes and the directly associated issues of energy poverty and energy literacy.

HOLISTIC

COLLECTIVE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Goals

1. Accelerating the Flemish ‘home renovation wave’;
2. Counteracting energy poverty;
3. Increasing energy literacy.

The story and the typology

Different layers (manifested as different types of energy citizenship) of the home renovation campaign form part of a rather organically growing and broadening set of activities. The main type of energy citizenship associated with the home renovation campaign addresses the household level – the individuals who undertake home renovation, empowered by governmental policies that create the conditions for this. Such home renovation activity can be classified as a reformative type of energy citizenship. However, the campaign is implemented by social movements and ‘organisationally embedded’ forms of energy citizenship. It is brought about by a broad coalition, yielding a combination of ‘reformative’ and ‘transformative’ agendas. And whilst home renovation can be considered a rather pragmatic and not particularly controversial form of energy citizenship, the campaign has a clear transformative orientation as it calls for a far more ambitious approach that also covers disadvantaged groups.

Type 1: Do their bit (in the household)
Reformative outcome / Individual agency

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

ULB UNIVERSITÉ
LIBRE
DE BRUXELLES

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Institute

Phase 1: A social movement, a business network and a household campaign, 2020-

BBL is an association of NGOs – a social movement which focuses on sustainable development issues (as reflected in the social movement energy citizenship Types 9 and 10). The home renovation campaign is one of BBL’s more recent projects, which supports several different ideal types of energy citizenship, described as “layers” of the case below. The main citizenship type, or main layer of this case, due to its title and main focus, is enabling citizens to undertake steps to improve the energy performance of their homes.

BBL as a whole, and also the home renovation campaign, have been adapted to be more citizen-oriented – by paying particular attention to the relevance of their campaigns to the average citizen. Although BBL is focused on political lobbying rather than directly empowering citizens, this layer of their campaign indicates efforts to support energy citizenship within the household in a more direct way, e.g. through an online self-assessment tool (as reflected in Type 1 as the main, and Type 2 as a secondary ideal type).

The other important layer of the campaign is the Energy Saving Pioneers (ESP), a network of ‘frontrunner’ businesses, other NGOs and politicians established by BBL to speed up the energy transition and boost the Flemish 'renovation wave'. The ESP represented a new alliance with business actors. It fortified lobbying of the Flemish

government and made further critical linkages with the business sector organisations that ESP members were members of. This pillar of the campaign relates to energy citizenship within (business) organisations (as reflected in Types 3 and 4, as secondary energy citizenship ideal types).

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their bit (in the household)
Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

- Secondary types:**
- Do their own (in the household)**
Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency
 - Do their bit (within organizations)**
Reformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency
 - Do it their way (within organizations)**
Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency
 - Do the job**
Reformative outcome / Social movements agency
 - Secondary type: Make their claims**
Transformative outcome / Social movements agency

The three layers of the case (social movement, organisational embeddedness, and household-level action) exist alongside each other as mutually reinforcing activities and forms of energy citizenship.

The aspects of energy citizenship

BBL is a platform organization with NGOs as its members. **Each of the associated organisations has one delegate in the general assembly, and together they nominate/vote for the 16-person executive board.** BBL as a whole, and also the home renovation campaign, have been adapted to be more citizen-oriented – paying particular attention to the relevance of their campaigns to the average citizen.

Citizen control

Citizens can express their views, but their views are not necessarily taken into account

The home renovation campaign in itself implicitly contributes to reducing carbon emissions. **But it is important that BBL's communications often underline the existence of international governmental commitments and policy targets, so overall it is classified into the 'explicit' category.** BBL engages in evidence-based activism in which climate targets, environmental footprints, and quantitative assessments of environmental impacts play a very prominent role.

Carbon limit

Explicit recognition with mention/objective of reaching the max. carbon footprint

Democratic energy future

Energy democracy is considered as a positive value, but the vision does not really address it

The BBL campaign underlines the importance of equal access to home improvement. **Access is formally open to everyone, but many citizens lack the material means to be able to act upon this theoretical freedom.** Energy poverty is a strong concern in this campaign. Gender and issues of marginalization are considered as well, to the extent that BBL proposes a tailored pre-financing scheme that is sensitive to the specific limitations and possibilities of different kinds of households.

Equity and justice

Equal access is granted, but limited by various criteria

BBL is an NGO focused on sustainability. **The home renovation campaign is one of the many campaigns associated with different domains of sustainable development.** This underlines how the ultimate rationale for BBL is sustainable development. Their renovation plan revolves around tailor-made pre-financing schemes that considerably reduce energy poverty, but the starting point remains environmental sustainability.

Environmental sustainability

Environmental sustainability is a core issue, and is considered in goal setting

Further information

[facebook.com/BondBeterLeefmilieu](https://www.facebook.com/BondBeterLeefmilieu)

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Hydro Electricity Ourthe and Sambre

Summary

Hydro Electricity Ourthe and Sambre (HOSe) develops and operates several hydroelectric power plants on two rivers in Wallonia. This enterprise was created by ten renewable energy cooperatives and the company Hydro-B to produce electricity for households.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

This is a hybrid case of energy citizenship that brings together energy cooperatives and a company dealing with renewable energy projects to launch the first Walloon hydroelectric power plants (partially) financed by citizens (50%).

DIRECT ENERGY
PRODUCTION /
CONSUMPTION

COLLECTIVE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Goals

1. Seeking to maximise Belgium's hydropower potential as a means of generating renewable, sustainable and environmentally friendly energy,
2. Introducing a profit- or return-on-investment incentive, as it involves a private sector partner, Hydro-B.
3. Promoting energy democracy, particularly through the associated cooperatives, with the explicit aim of using democratic, horizontal decision-making.

The story and the typology

HOSe involves an interesting institutionally hybrid form of energy citizenship. From the outside, it may appear to be a regular case of an energy cooperative, but it is not a pure cooperative because 1) it involves a commercial private sector partner, and 2) it is built up of about a dozen cooperatives.

It was established in December 2018 as an institutionally hybrid and mildly transformation-oriented collective energy citizenship actor. The approach is pragmatic, seeking to develop a balance between sustainability-oriented initiatives and ensuring a solid financial bottom line.

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

Phase 1: Exploiting Hydroelectricity, 2000-2014

The case started with an enlightened, societally engaged and environmentally conscious entrepreneur, a transformation-oriented citizen who has acted on his ideals throughout his professional life.

Following a call for projects (and in addition to the opening up of the development of hydroelectricity in Belgium), his small company Mérytherm (later, Hydro-B) obtained concessions to explore hydroelectricity.

This organisationally embedded example of energy citizenship (as indicated by the main type, “Do it their way (within hybrid organisations)”) was created by engaged individuals operating as

Phase 2: Rise of Emissions-Zero, 2007-2014

In this phase, the approach of Mérytherm (the founding company mentioned above) involved a willingness to engage in institutionally hybrid projects (as indicated by the main citizenship type for this phase) – sometimes leaning towards clever investment and sometimes involving more risk-bearing, idealistic, ‘transformation-oriented’ ventures.

Additionally, in this phase, Emissions-Zero (one of the founding cooperatives) was growing in the area of renewable energy, seeking to diversify its projects and explore hydropower. This phase

activists privately in the household (as indicated in the secondary type, “Do their own (in the household)”).

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do it their way (within hybrid organisations)
Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Secondary type: Do their own (in the household)
Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

indicates that the roots of HOSe are in collective, mildly transformative, citizen-based and hybrid energy citizenship.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead
Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Phase 3: Civic co-funding, 2014 - 2018

Emissions-Zero teamed up with Mérytherm, at first through financing. Once they had jointly founded Monceau-Hydro (a limited company), they took the first step towards more extensive (i.e., not merely financial-transactional) cooperation. At first, the collaboration involving Monceau-Hydro was rather reformative (as indicated by the main type) in nature, involving co-financing but no significant co-development. However, all the partners who are involved can be considered energy transition idealists.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims				

Secondary type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Do their own (in the household)

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Phase 4: HOSe, institutionally hybrid energy citizenship, 2018 -

The establishment of HOSe (a result of the further development of Monceau-Hydro) in 2018 marked the phase of upscaling to a more prominent role for the cooperatives.

HOSe acquired its character of a mildly transformative, institutionally hybrid, collective form of energy citizenship. It significantly differs from the originally somewhat more profit-seeking and environmentally oriented Hydro-B enterprise. It also pursues less profitable options and has broader transformative agency in pursuing energy democracy.

This last phase involves various dynamics associated with new projects and turbulent external circumstances (rising energy prices, major

floodings, and periods of drought). Still, HOSe appears to have achieved a relatively stable final form (in terms of energy citizenship ideal types).

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims				

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

The aspects of energy citizenship

Effective citizen control has been achieved only partly. **The cooperative model ensures a significant level of the latter and indeed the case has advanced on this front – yet there are certain limitations to citizen control.** Quite a lot of citizen agency remains delegated to specific groups of other actors such as experts, frontrunner individuals and administrators in the cooperatives, and in the various intermediaries that have allowed/helped HOSe to be successful.

Citizen control

Citizens can express their views, but their views are not necessarily taken into account

HOSe has creating a more democratic future amongst its three main objectives. **This is a core concern and transmitted from the explicit commitments of its members to the cooperative model and consensual decision-making.** Democratization also involves efforts to stimulate energy literacy in society more widely, i.e., through guided visits and the communication activities of the cooperatives.

Democratic energy future

A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

Equity and justice are somewhat implicit concerns. **The cooperative model that has been chosen and the shared commitment to environmental gains and societal surplus all indicate commitments to equity and justice.** Still, the cooperative is bounded by its membership, and the management of the cooperative/business venture is quite strongly oriented towards members/shareholders. There are efforts to recruit new members, but also a responsibility to ensure long-term viability and a return on investment for members

Equity and justice

Equal access is granted, but limited by various criteria

The name HOSe stands for hydropower itself, and the initiative has emerged from, or revolves around, achievements – made possible through technological innovation in hydro-turbines – in environmental sustainability and clean energy. Environmental performance is measured, monitored and planned. “Hydro-electricity has a lot of advantages that compensate for its higher cost compared to wind power: The production is predictable and stable, especially during the six cold months of the year when the energy demands are high.”

Environmental sustainability

Environmental sustainability is a core issue, and is considered in goal setting

Carbon limit

Explicit recognition of the carbon limit

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Further information

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Student Switch Off campaigns in Bulgaria

Summary

Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski” (UoS) participated in the Student Switch Off (SSO) campaign organised within the SAVES2 project. The SSO campaign was an inter-dormitory energy-saving competition that focused on a predefined set of activities, encouraging students to save energy in their dormitories, while the SSO+ campaign focused on students living in the private rented sector and aimed at raising awareness of energy performance certificates (EPC), smart meters and energy efficiency, thus helping students reduce their energy costs and their exposure to energy poverty.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

The SSO campaigns represent the collective efforts of students to reduce their energy consumption through changes in their behaviour, encouraging them to become energy citizens. Moreover, the campaigns support students to minimise their carbon footprint at their university and private accommodation, raising awareness about energy efficiency and smart metering and establishing good sustainability habits which last beyond their time in education.

DIRECT ENERGY PRODUCTION / CONSUMPTION

COLLECTIVE

URBAN

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

ARCFUND

grⁱⁿdependent
Institute

SAVES 2

Goals

1. Helping students become environmentally conscious by motivating them to engage in energy-saving action;
2. Reducing the carbon footprint of students by changes in their energy consumption habits;
3. Decreasing the exposure of university students to energy poverty by decreasing their energy bills.

The story and the typology

The Students Switch Off campaigns were active at the University of Sofia (UoS) for three consecutive academic years between 2017 and 2020, with about 14,000 students involved in the SSO campaign and 5,000 in the SSO+ campaign. Energy savings were determined by comparing pre-intervention and post-intervention electricity consumption in each dormitory/private accommodation. The dormitories that saved the most energy were announced winners and rewarded for their efforts.

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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Phase 1: The first year and start of the case, 2017

The case started with recruiting students for participation in the initiative and the awareness-raising campaign (tips through the Facebook page of the initiative, the monthly newsletter, leaflets and posters, and dormitory visits during the academic year). Once students were made aware of the simple activities they could execute on a daily basis to change their energy behaviour, the dormitories started competing to save energy and reduce their energy expenses.

The case started within an organisation (university/student dormitories) but later also

affected energy consumption and behaviour within the private homes and households of students.

	Individual		Collective		
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organisations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organisations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their bit (within organisations)

Reformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Secondary type: Do their bit (in the household)

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Phase 2: Continuation and expansion of the case, 2018 - 2020

One of the challenges of the SSO/SSO+ campaigns was that the UoS team changed after the first academic year. However, the new team stayed on board during the last two years, bringing stability and predictability. Students continued saving energy and monitoring energy consumption at dormitories and private households. Students also started to apply what they had learned about energy saving when they returned home during holidays and during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The team analysed each year's experiences, building upon good practices and pinpointing new areas to improve. One important change was the use of social media. During the first year, there was no social media presence. In the second and third years, the active use of social media and email communication considerably increased engagement. About two-thirds of students who participated in Bulgaria's SSO/SSO+ campaign said

they would continue saving energy after graduation.

Social relations among students were an important aspect of the SSO/SSO+ initiative because students motivated each other, thus creating a community of active energy citizens.

	Individual		Collective		
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organisations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organisations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their bit (within organisations)

Reformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Secondary types

Do their bit (in the household)

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

The aspects of energy citizenship

The students participated in an initiative that was a part of an international project. Therefore, they largely followed the instructions and workplan designed by someone else before their involvement. During the implementation, they were supervised and instructed by their academic supervisors. However, at the same time they had considerable autonomy concerning what and how to achieve the objectives of the case.

The SSO/SSO+ campaigns promote simple energy efficiency tips that can be easily applied in everyday life. Their focus is on changing the personal habits of students and energy democracy is beyond this objective.

Democratic energy future

Energy democracy has not been among the goals

FOCUS ON DISADVANTAGED GROUPS

The SSO/SSO+ campaigns at Sofia University (UoS) aimed to reduce students' energy usage and exposure to energy poverty. **Involvement in the campaigns was open to all students** at the UoS. Moreover, the campaigns involved creating social media pages where tips for saving energy were regularly posted. These social media pages are still accessible to the wider public, including people who are not students at UoS, who are now able to take advantage of the information posted online.

Equity and justice

Involvement is fully open

One of the objectives of the SSO/SSO+ campaigns within the SAVES2 project, including Sofia University in Bulgaria, was to reduce students' carbon footprints and thus positively affect the environment. Therefore, it can be claimed that **environmental sustainability was also addressed by the campaigns as a spillover effect** of the activities involved with the case, but energy saving was the focus of the initiative.

Environmental sustainability

Environmental sustainability is part of the process; energy remains the main focus

Citizen control
Citizens' voices remain hardly heard or taken into account

Reducing the carbon footprint was one of the objectives of the SSO/SSO+ initiative. By reducing their energy consumption, students in UoS managed to reduce their carbon footprints significantly. This was achieved by following the tips they received, the monthly newsletters, and information about energy-saving and dormitory visits during the academic year aimed at raising awareness face-to-face.

Carbon limit
Explicit recognition with mention/objective of reaching the max. carbon footprint

Further information

www.facebook.com/UOSSSO

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Naturstrom AG

GERMANY

Summary

Naturstrom AG aims to provide a 'clean, safe and economical' energy supply based on renewable energy. It claims sustainability is the core of its business activity, and more than 300,000 households, companies, and associations are using its energy products, which are focused on the areas of electricity, heating and mobility and include energy delivery, energy production, energy infrastructure and decentralised energy supply.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

It is a case of energy citizenship because citizens can opt for the renewable energy supplied by Naturstrom in their homes, workplaces, or other organisations in which they are active. Naturstrom also supports and connects local energy projects, where citizens can play a more active role in energy production.

DIRECT ENERGY
PRODUCTION /
CONSUMPTION

COLLECTIVE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Goals

1. Producing and delivering renewable energy regionally;
2. Driving forward the energy transition and the further expansion of renewable energies;
3. Supporting citizen participation and allowing citizens to participate in the energy transition.

The story and the typology

Naturstrom AG was founded in 1998 as a joint stock company by members of environmental and renewable energy associations, including BUND (Friends of the Earth Germany), NABU (Nature and Biodiversity Conservation Union), BWE (German Wind Energy Association), and EUROSOLAR. In 2003, its 100th energy production site was built, and in 2004, there were more than 50,000 customers. The case has changed in form and expanded its services in many ways. However, its typologisation regarding the agency and outcome orientation of the state of energy citizenship that is enabled has not changed since its formation.

Type 4: Do it their way (within organisations)

Transformative outcome / Individual agency

Type 4: Do it their way (within organisations)

Transformative outcome / Individual agency

Type 4: Do it their way (within organisations)

Transformative outcome / Individual agency

1998

2005

2012

Type 1: Do their bit

Type 1: Do their bit

Type 7: Do their share

Type 8: Go ahead

Type 1: Do their bit

Type 7: Do their share

Type 8: Go ahead

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

grün independent Institute

Phase 1: Creation of the case, 1998 - 2005

From the very beginning, Naturstrom has played a pioneering role in the field of sustainable energy supply. Since 1999, the tariff provided by Naturstrom has been awarded the highest quality, the green electricity label. The reason for this is the high level of funding for new eco-power plants (1 euro cent net per kWh). In its founding phase, it was a small emerging company among large energy companies, the innovative concept being that it financed the building of new renewable energy plants. The first was a small photovoltaic system in Weil am Rhein in 1998. One of the biggest obstacles

then was the low legally determined electricity feed-in tariff and higher solar panel investment costs.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do it their way

Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Secondary type: Do their bit

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Phase 2: Consolidation of the case, 2005 - 2011

Since approximately 2005, Naturstrom AG has expanded its business areas by building its own eco-power plants to further the energy transition. A growing awareness of the emerging climate crisis and the long-standing opposition to nuclear power are helping Naturstrom and the few other independent green electricity providers to grow out of their niche, taking green electricity into the mainstream. From 2007 onwards, the number of Naturstrom customers will double yearly, albeit from a very modest level initially. Naturstrom is the first company to offer up to 100% eco gas on the German market. Naturstrom is building up a pool of smaller green electricity producers who sell their electricity directly to Naturstrom. Still, to resell this electricity as green electricity per the law, the plant operators must waive the statutory feed-in tariffs. Naturstrom can pay slightly higher prices because energy suppliers who market green electricity directly in this way are exempted from the EEG levy under strict conditions. More than half of the electricity that Naturstrom has supplied to customers since 2008 comes directly from wind

turbines in Germany. At its peak, there are more than 200 plants from which Naturstrom draws its electricity. At the end of the 2000s, there were no other electricity suppliers in Germany who sold green electricity from eligible wind or solar systems to household customers nationwide. It was not until the early 2010s that other energy suppliers appeared alongside natural electricity providers and changed their procurement practices

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do it their way

Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Secondary type: Do their bit

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Secondary type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Phase 3: Current state, 2012 - 2023

The reactor catastrophe in Fukushima in March 2011 marked a turning point: an increasing number of people started taking a stand against nuclear energy and switched to green electricity from Naturstrom, independent of the coal and nuclear industries.

In 2014, the legal basis for the Naturstrom supply model was eliminated from the Renewable Energy Sources Act. Nevertheless, the direct marketing of green electricity prevails and is now standard for larger green power plants.

Since 2015, Naturstrom has developed more and more innovative projects in which ecologically generated energy is consumed directly on-site with electricity projects, sustainable local heating solutions and district concepts. Therefore, it can be seen as fostering forms of energy citizenship corresponding to both the ideal types 7 and 8. The organisational structure and the main goals of Naturstrom have remained mainly the same in that Naturstrom shares are primarily held by micro shareholders (about 1700), employees share in the profits, and shares are not traded on the stock exchange, so no other company, such as a conventional energy supplier, can influence Naturstrom. Corporate goals are not aimed at short-

term profit maximisation, and there are no yield or dividend targets; instead, most profit remains in the company to enable energy transition projects and growth.

The company will mainly continue as it did, focussing on expanding its number of renewable energy plants with citizens, municipalities and other companies and supplying consumers with renewable energy. They plan to look more into the topics of digitalisation and, connected to this, future models of energy communities.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do it their way

Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Secondary type: Do their bit

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Secondary type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

The aspects of energy citizenship

Citizens, as employees or outsiders, can be stakeholders of the company and in this way take part in the internal decision-making, according to their shares in the company. Citizens, communities, and companies that are cooperating with Naturstrom in relation to energy projects/plants have voting rights as well. Finally, employees have the option to buy shares, too. In the end, a limited group of people play a part in the decision-making process and ultimately, decisions are made by the management board.

Citizen control

Citizens can express their views, but their views are not necessarily taken into account

There is no explicit mention of energy democracy, but the focus is on producing renewable energy in the form of a company with goals concerning sustainability but also profitability. Participation is possible for consumers, shareholders and owners/producers, so **there is an interest in decentralisation and supporting local communities to build their own renewable energy projects**, which relates to making the energy system more safe, sustainable and democratic.

Democratic energy future

A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

Access is fairly open, equity and justice are explicitly pursued, and Naturstrom considers economic, ecological and social sustainability to be core values. The main and only limit is that people with low incomes are probably not able to afford Naturstrom electricity. However, Naturstrom is making an effort not only to aim at homeowners with their renewable energy projects but also address renters with tenant electricity.

Equity and justice

Equal access is granted, but limited by various criteria

Naturstrom recognises the 1.5°C target explicitly on their website, where they are vocalising their support for Fridays for Future and their **success with a lawsuit against the federal climate protection law** that now has to be corrected in that the reduction goals for CO₂ emissions need to be reformulated more explicitly. They also write: 'The judgment also proves that we have climate protection in our own hands and can achieve the 1.5°C target.'

Carbon limit

Explicit recognition with mention/objective of reaching the max. carbon footprint

Environmental sustainability has been, since the company's founding, 'at the core of the company'. This mainly includes the goals of **replacing fossil fuels with renewable energy by producing or enabling citizens to produce renewable energy and delivering renewable energy**. Naturstrom pursues this goal inside and outside of their core business, including their offices, IT equipment and vehicles.

Environmental sustainability

Environmental sustainability is a core issue, and is considered in goal setting

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Further information

facebook.com/naturstrom
youtube.com/user/naturstromTV

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<https://www.naturstrom.de>

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La Borda. Housing Cooperative through transfer of use

Summary

La Borda pursues a cooperative housing model governed by a grant of use, whereby property is always collective while use is personal. The model eliminates property speculation and profiteering. Members of the cooperative can decide on juridical, legal and economic aspects and the housing infrastructure itself. One of its main objectives is to prioritise environmental aspects, which is economically achievable through creating homes with a passive design or low-energy consumption, with local, decentralised and self-managed renewable energy generation. Less energy and materials are consumed as major appliances and amenities are shared.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

La Borda represents an example of energy citizenship in the form of a housing cooperative whose objective is to change how people live and share, using a house built with energy efficiency measures whose members are trying to reduce the overall environmental impact of everyday living.

Goals

1. Guaranteeing access to affordable and decent housing, contributing to making access to housing universal;
2. Developing a new model of production, management and ownership of housing;
3. Creating and promoting an alternative societal model and implementing a viable community housing project in an urban context.

The story and the typology

La Borda aspires to become an alternative model to traditional public housing, affordable for people on low incomes. To this end, it is interested in becoming a self-managed neighbourhood on a human scale, in which social commitment and a different way of developing the city prevail, taking advantage of existing resources and reusing them in an ecological and sustainable way.

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Phase 1: Establishment of La Borda, 2012-2015

Before the formal beginning of the building construction, they “had already work[ed] on the project [for] about five years. The years before the construction were years of a lot of work at the model and group constitution level”.

La Borda was born in 2012 as a result of three contextual factors: (1) a housing crisis fuelled by a reduction in household disposable income; (2) the emergence of the social economy – and in particular, the cooperative movement – as a potential basis for the development of alternative housing schemes; and (3) the existence of a neighbourhood movement linked to the urban renewal process of the former industrial estate of Can Batlló.

A group of neighbours occupied one of Can Batlló’s abandoned industrial buildings and used a

Phase 2: Construction, 2015-2019

After intense negotiations, an agreement was signed between Barcelona City Council and the cooperative in 2015, whereby the municipality leased a plot of land in Calle Constitució, registered as social housing, to the cooperative for 75 years.

To create a space with a sustainable and participatory design, a “constructive phase [involving the] participatory design of the building” was implemented, whereby “future inhabitants c[ould] define the entire project according to their needs”. This is important, as it also contributed to the council considering giving permission for the similar use of other land on the territory of the city. In this phase, the main energy citizenship type of case became community-based, with a

participatory process to determine how they would like to see the site used.

This was the beginning of the self-organisation and self-promotion process for creating the La Borda Housing Cooperative. During this phase, the case may be classified as the collective (citizen-based and hybrid) and reformatory “Do their share” ENCI ideal type.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformatory	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do the job

Reformatory outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

transformative goal orientation, as the framework was established and construction started. With the strengthening of the cooperative, an organisationally embedded, transformative type of citizenship type also arose.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformatory	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims				

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Do it their way (within organisations)

Reformatory outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Phase 3: Cohabitation, 2019-

In 2019, the construction was completed, and the community moved in. As members saw it, *“it was a very big phase of finishing the houses (...) we entered a phase of starting to live together, we entered [during the] pandemic [which] also gave us another rhythm”.*

The case has become a benchmark for the development of public policies.

After the construction phase, the experiential phase started. Here, the main type did not change, as the purpose of the cooperative remained the same. But, by moving in, people became residents of the community rather than ‘just’ members of the cooperative; thus, an individual, household type of

energy citizenship has also appeared as a secondary ideal type.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Collective agency

Secondary types:

Do it their way (within organisations)

Reformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Do their own (in the household)

Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

The aspects of energy citizenship

“Direct participation is the central axis of the project and this has a lot of influence, from how the building was designed to how we live, to what priorities we have at any given moment.” **Several members pointed out that such participation “through a horizontal and democratic organisation has been crucial to launching and consolidating the initiative (...) (and) has been promoted and channelled through dialogic and participatory spaces, among which the general assembly and the working commissions stand out”.**

Citizen control
Citizens exert effective control, and their votes have to be taken into account

One of the central aims of La Borda is "to make the best use of existing resources and to reuse them in an environmentally friendly and sustainable way". **This is embodied in activities that reduce consumption and carbon emissions in housing construction.** The commitment to reduce consumption and carbon footprint on a daily basis is also significant.

Carbon limits
Explicit recognition of the carbon limit

The ultimate objective of La Borda is to ensure that its members can “access affordable accommodation” in a space which is “self-initiated and self-organized by a group of citizens, whose objective was to live in a community and take advantage of the socioeconomic advantages of designing, building and living collectively”. For the moment, this is a challenge to be achieved in a transversal way, not as a central focus of the initiative. To achieve their goals, they also need to consider energy issues.

Democratic energy future
Energy democracy is considered as a positive value, but it remains limited to formal energy democracy

La Borda is committed to “finding decent and efficient housing at an affordable price for member families”, as well as establishing a replicable model which allows “universal access to decent housing through mechanisms which place use, not ownership, at the centre of the activity”. **The fee that can be charged for the use of housing is minimized so as to allow humble people to access it, which is one of the main purposes of the cooperative.** In fact, a long-term goal is to “increase accessibility for people who are in a housing emergency, people with low educational levels or [are] vulnerab[le], etc.”

Equity and justice
Equal access is granted, but limited by various criteria

One of the founding objectives of La Borda is to “give priority to the environmental aspect, economically achievable through homes with a passive design or low energy consumption, with the local, decentralized and self-managed generation of renewable energy. And, in the same sense, promote during the life of the dwelling the achievement of local and closed cycles of energy, water and waste”. **The building is made of wood, with a bioclimatic building design, in addition to having other measures for community life, such as the collectivization of some facilities, which increases efficiency.**

Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability is a core issue, and is considered in goal setting

Further information

facebook.com/labordacoop

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Source of images

<http://www.laborda.coop/es/proyecto/fotografias/>

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Zsuzsanna
Hojtsy-Keresztény:
EnergyNeighbourhoods
energy master, local
change maker

Summary

Zsuzsanna participated in GreenDependent's EnergyNeighbourhoods programme as a volunteer “energy master”. Her friend, who supported her has experience with another Hungarian NGO's community-based household greening programme called ÖkoKörök (EcoTeams). Based on methods and ideas learnt in these two programmes, a local eco-club was founded in Zsuzsanna's home town, with her as one of the main organisers of the first meeting in 2019. Since then, the informal community has grown into a formal NGO. They aim to develop a community whose members are willing to address the current ecological crisis and are ready to learn about and apply solutions that help create an ecologically sustainable way of life.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

As a catalyst, Zsuzsanna is playing an important role in supporting the local community and leading it on a sustainable path. As an energy master, she has taken on the role of coordinator among her close circle of friends, helping them to save energy. As one of the founders of a local NGO, she organises lectures, community forums and other community activities to mobilise the local population around sustainability goals.

HOLISTIC

INDIVIDUAL

PERI-URBAN

Goals

1. Creating and expanding a local, cohesive, green community among core members, combined with internal organisational development;
2. Promoting green lifestyles and opportunities and reaching as many people as possible who are not part of the core community (programme participants, residents);
3. Creating a shopping community.

The story and the typology

In summary, Zsuzsanna's initiative transformed from an individual to a collective energy citizenship case, with more and more people getting involved in the life of the local community. The initiative has moved from a reformative, household-based energy citizenship type to a transformative, community- and settlement-based one as the range and depth of issues have broadened with the range of participants.

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Phase 1: Before EnergyNeighbourhoods, 2019

Zsuzsanna's story started with her being an environmentally conscious citizen who decided to make her lifestyle more sustainable. Her motivation was specifically to fight the climate crisis.

In terms of energy citizenship ideal types, in this phase, her work can be classified as a reformative, individual case, focused on the household level, as she started using small steps to change her own household and family lifestyle, but she did not yet

have the knowledge and empowerment to influence others.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their bit (in the household)
Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Phase 2: EnergyNeighbourhoods' community 2019-2021

In 2019, on social media, Zsuzsanna saw an advertisement for the EnergyNeighbourhoods programme (a household energy-saving competition organised by GreenDependent¹) and applied to become an energy master. Here, she learned about energy saving at home; she became the energy master of a small, mainly local community of families. After a successful first season, she continued participating in the programme with a new group the following season. As an energy master, this can still be seen as an individual type of energy citizenship, but it is more transformative, as she has become a mentor for others (as indicated by the change of main type).

However, as a small community has been created through her team, a collective phase has started, which is reformative in nature (as indicated in the secondary type).

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their own (in the household)
Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Secondary type: Do their share
Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

¹ See more details at <https://intezet.greendependent.org/en/node/480>

Phase 3: Informal community, 2019-2020

In parallel with the second season of the EnergyNeighbourhoods programme, Zsuzsanna wanted to get more involved in community organising. At the suggestion of a friend, she started a local green community called the Göd Eco-Club, at first informally.

At this stage, the initiative moved in a collective, transformative direction in terms of energy citizenship (as indicated by the change in the main type). As the focus remains on greening and supporting households, the ideal types at the household level remain secondary types (Type 1, Type 2).

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types:

Do their bit (in the household)

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Do their own (in the household)

Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Phase 4: Eco-club, 2021-

In 2021, the informal community took the form of a registered association.

Göd Eco-Club is a democratically operating organisation whose members can implement their own ideas according to the principles of sustainability, for which the association provides a framework.

In this context, Zsuzsanna’s role is primarily to bring together, support and coordinate the organisation and the community, and of course, to achieve her own “smaller” goals, e.g. setting up a shopping community.

The eco-club has joined a Hungarian organisation, the Small Communities Programme's eco-community networking initiative called the "New Koma Network". The programme's main aim is to create more such communities in Hungary.

This has also led to the introduction of the ideal type associated with the social movements agency (Do the job) as a secondary type.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types:

Do their bit (in the household)

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Do their own (in the household)

Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Do the job

Reformative outcome / Social movements agency

The aspects of energy citizenship

The official president of the association is Zsuzsanna, but in practice this is only manifested in the fact that she undertakes the necessary administrative tasks. Otherwise, decisions are basically taken democratically. **The association works on the tasks that its members want to and are committed to managing and implementing** – they become the project leaders, the so-called “godparents”, and are assisted by other members who are interested in the topic. The association is currently entirely voluntary.

Citizen power/control
Citizens exert effective control, and their votes have to be taken into account

Zsuzsanna has noticed a decrease in emissions associated with her own lifestyle since she started participating in EnergyNeighbourhoods, e.g., she thinks twice about using a car, and walks or uses public transport instead. **The community also considers it important to communicate externally about the carbon footprint and encourages people to reduce theirs.** “There are always questions about what is a better solution (for making reductions)”.

Carbon limit
Explicit recognition of the carbon limit

Anyone is welcome to join the events, but the association itself is not primarily engaged in classical democratization activities, like advocacy or lobbying for energy system transformation. It is primarily concerned with promoting a green attitude and a more sustainable lifestyle among its members and those who participate from a greater distance. **The democratising factor is primarily in the education and empowerment of participants.** What also helps with democratisation is the possibility to rent power meters and tree chipper, which greatly increases energy awareness and helps establish independence.

Democratic energy future

Energy democracy is considered as a positive value, but it remains limited to formal energy democracy

Anyone from the local population can join the initiative, but limited to the settlement of Göd, or at least requires some connection to the it. In general, equality issues are not the focus of the case, as operations are concentrated in the municipality of Göd, where energy poverty is not a primary problem, as it is a wealthier, agglomeration close to the capital. However, there have been examples of providing support to less well-off families, e.g., by donating LED light bulbs.

Equity and justice

Equal access is granted, but limited by various criteria

Zsuzsanna's motivation for taking action and joining the EnergyNeighbourhoods programme was specifically to fight the climate crisis. She has continued to maintain the skills and green practices she learnt during her participation in EnergyNeighbourhoods after it ended. The Göd Eco-Club, which she has founded, also shows a clear commitment to environmental sustainability, as it is an eco-community.

Environmental sustainability

Environmental sustainability is a core issue, and is considered in goal setting

Further information

www.facebook.com/godiokoklub

godiokoklub.hu

godiokoklub@yahoo.com

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Source of images

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Proofreading by Simon Milton / **Reviewed by** case participants

Social media influencer "Edgar Fresh"

Summary

Edgar Fresh is a well-known influencer in Latvia, especially aimed at young people. He actively communicates about issues related to the environment and climate change on his social platform. In addition to social networks, he is a civic participant in public consultations who follows processes and tries to influence them.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

Edgar Fresh has been an enthusiast and promoter of a climate-friendly lifestyle from a young age. He communicates his thoughts on environmental sustainability actively on social media to a wide audience in Latvia. He also gets involved in various activities and campaigns related to climate change, acts as a moderator in discussions on climate change, edits videos to promote climate marches, and draws posters. His YouTube channel, Edgar Fresh, is a unique blend of environmental activism, eco-friendly lifestyles, internet marketing and a little entertainment.

HOLISTIC

INDIVIDUAL

Goals

1. Drawing people's attention to climate-related issues and invite them to participate in climate action;
2. Showing people that by changing their habits and being environmentally friendly, it is possible to save money and live a better lifestyle;
3. Promoting civic participation in political and administrative processes.

The story and the typology

Edgar Fresh started his activities in 2016, and at the beginning focused on “greening” his lifestyle, giving advice and providing tips to others on reducing their ecological and carbon footprint. Later, he broadened his use of communication tools and learned more about the systemic conditions for sustainable living and environmental management in Latvia. Although the case's main and secondary ideal energy citizenship types have remained the same throughout its history, its operations have broadened, so the relative importance of the ideal types has changed, as explained below.

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Phase 1: Creation and initial stage of the case, 2016 - 2019

During the first phase, Edgar set up his YouTube channel and social media pages. He started to communicate about his efforts to live a more sustainable lifestyle, gradually building up his audience and broadening the scope of the topics he was sharing. He also encouraged people to participate in climate action, including public action, inviting them to participate, e.g., in the first Climate March organised in Latvia in 2019.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their own
Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Secondary type: Make their voice heard
Transformative outcome / Public agency

Phase 2: Broadening partnerships and communication tools, 2019 - 2023

In the second phase, Edgar's cooperation with various organisations, such as Fridays for Future Latvia, WWF, etc., broadened, and his cooperation with others, both organisations and individuals, also grew in number and variety. Furthermore, he also broadened the use of his communication tools and channels; e.g., he created a podcast series and a new YouTube channel in cooperation with another organisation. He also started participating in events and conferences, presenting and moderating discussions.

Finally, to better manage his work as an influencer and professionalise his activities further, he created a communication agency.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organization)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Make their voice heard
Reformative outcome / Public agency

Secondary type: Do their own
Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Phase 3: Future, 2023 -

Edgar plans to broaden his activities further and would like to secure funding for his various project ideas and/or find sponsors for his activities. At the moment, he is more actively communicating about green energy and technologies, such as solar panels, electric cars or micro mobility.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Make their voice heard
Reformative outcome / Public agency

Secondary type: Do their own
Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

The aspects of energy citizenship

As this is an individual case, in general, decisions related to the case are made individually. However, other people often serve as a source of inspiration. Sometimes suggestions for content creation come from followers. When a broader view of citizen power is taken, civic participation is important in the content created by Edgar as well as in his opinions; **thus, he often invites and encourages others to be active citizens and to get involved in political and decision-making processes.**

Energy democracy does not appear as a distinct and prominent topic in Edgar's communication. However, this topic is indirectly present through other topics. In general, Edgar's overall position is based on the fact that energy, especially green energy, should be available to everyone. He **calls on people to be active citizens and to get involved in public consultations**, and to try to influence the direction of policy-making.

Citizen power/control
Citizens can express their views, but their views are not necessarily taken into account

Democratic energy future

Energy democracy is considered a positive value, but it remains limited to formal energy democracy

Issues related to **equity and justice do appear in the content created by Edgar Fresh in a fragmented way.** For example, he discusses the mobility rights of people, such as cyclists in overly car-dominated cities, and consumer rights related to the right to repair and other issues.

Equity and justice
Equal access is granted, but limited by various criteria

Addressing climate change and reducing carbon emissions are key concerns of Edgar Fresh. **Carbon reduction and mobility are some of the current topics that Edgar includes in his communications.** In addition to creating his own content, he also joins other people and projects, including European level ones, to amplify their messages in Latvia.

Carbon limit

Explicit recognition with mention/objective of reaching the max. carbon footprint

Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability is a core issue, and is considered in goal setting

Environmental concerns are at the heart of the case. In creating content, Edgar puts great emphasis on environmental sustainability, which is communicated in different forms and about different sectors. In addition, setting a good example by acting in an environmentally friendly manner is also very important for Edgar.

Further information

facebook.com/edgarfrsh/

tiktok.com/@edgarfresh

twitter.com/EdgarFresh

instagram.com/edgarfrsh/

youtube.com/c/EdgarFresh youtube.com/@druskuizglabtpasauliaredga5540/featured

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<https://www.tv3.lv/pedas-pec-tevis/ka-ar-savu-macinu-var-nobalsot-par-labaku-nakotni-stasta-jutuberis-un-finansu-entuziasts-edgars-fresh/> (Accessed 30.08.2023)
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Source of images

facebook.com/edgarfrsh/; youtube.com/c/EdgarFresh

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The Drechtsteden cooperative

Summary

In 2017, Drechtsteden was one of the first regions in the Netherlands to create a Regional Energy Strategy (RES) called RES 1.0 in cooperation with 30 other organisations. In 2018, the Drechtsteden Energy Agreement was signed. The Drechtsteden cooperative works with many regional partners, each with their own interests but sharing the same goal of a sustainable future. The energy cooperative also acts as a facilitator and intermediary organisation for the partners involved in the energy transition in the region. For example, Drechtsteden ensures alignment and correspondence between the seven municipalities regarding their regional 'Heat Transition Vision' programme.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

Drechtsteden Energy is a good example of a regional organisation that works with many stakeholders. They draw up the RES agenda with local residents, entrepreneurs, businesses, environmental organisations, water boards, seven municipalities, and other interested parties. Residents of the region were closely involved in the process of drafting the RES.

DIRECT ENERGY
PRODUCTION /
CONSUMPTION

COLLECTIVE

PERI-URBAN

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Maastricht University

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Institute

Goals

1. Producing energy sustainably in the Drechtsteden region;
2. Promoting more sustainable homes and heat infrastructure;
3. Making the energy transformation as socially rewarding as possible.

The story and the typology

Drechtsteden Energy can be classified into the expanded “citizen-based and hybrid” ideal energy citizenship category with collective agency. Although it focuses on energy citizenship in the broader sense, it enables it at the level of hybrid organisations, also by involving people/citizens. Thus, the main ideal type of energy citizenship supported is Type 7. Accordingly, it has a reformative outcome orientation. Citizens participated in the formulation of RES 1.0, and also participate through getting solar energy in their homes, but do not (yet) participate in internal decision-making involving the case. In terms of RE projects at Drechtsteden, citizens are also given the opportunity to get involved via participation/consultation evenings and online surveys. Thus, another secondary, public, with individual agency, is also relevant, as indicated in the figure below.

Case history summary

For the summary
methodology,
click [HERE](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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Phase 1: Creation of the case in 2017

Drechtsteden Energy came into existence in 2017 after the drafting of the Regional Energy Strategy (RES 1.0) for the Drechtsteden region.¹

Two concrete goals have been defined for these regions. The first was to contribute to the national 2030 target of having 35 TWh of sustainable electricity generated on land. Drechtsteden aims to contribute 1.1% (0.37 TWh) of this target.

The second concrete goal (set by the Dutch Climate Agreement for the 30 energy regions) is to collectively make 1.5 million homes more sustainable by 2030 and use more sustainable heat sources. Drechtsteden Energy aims to consume 20% less energy (electricity and gas) in the built environment by 2030. Moreover, they aim to make 12,000 - 25,000 more sustainable homes that are connected to sustainable heat sources by 2030. By planning and implementing this objective, the case supports individual energy citizenship as well (Type 1 in the table).

The Dutch Climate Agreement was formulated by the national government and involved dividing the

Netherlands into 30 energy regions. Drechtsteden is one of those regions; hence, Drechtsteden Energy is closely tied to the government through the specific area of the RES. This is because each energy region was tasked with drawing up its own RES document, with the involvement of citizens.

Due to the scope of activities, public, citizen-based, and hybrid agencies appear as the main type of citizenship. In the second place, since citizens are invited to express their views on the strategies developed, Type 5 agency is also relevant.

	Individual			Collective	
	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types

Do their bit

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Make their voice heard

Reformative outcome / Public agency

¹ The Administrative Consultation RES consists of the parties/coalition responsible for drawing up the RES (seven municipalities: Alblasserdam, Dordrecht, Hardinxveld-Giessendam, Hendrik-Ido-Ambacht, Papendrecht, Sliedrecht and Zwijndrecht, the Province of South Holland and two water boards: Water Boards Hollandse Delta and Rivierenland) based on the Dutch National Climate Agreement.

Phase 2: Impact of the Drechtsteden Energy Agreement, 2017-2021

In 2018, the Drechtsteden Energy Agreement was concluded, establishing the Drechtsteden Energy Programme Council. The Agreement was signed by more than 35 parties, who committed to achieving energy neutrality by 2050.

The partners represent organisations with their own ambitions and planning regarding the energy transition who are committed to deploying their knowledge, people and resources to substantially reduce the region's energy consumption and the use of fossil fuels.

Phase 3: Current phase since 2022

Completing the RES 1.0 is perceived as an achievement by the case actors. However, they do acknowledge that it has not yet been significantly impactful because it needs to be translated into practice. Importantly, they have selected development areas for large-scale sustainable energy generation in the region and intend to start granting permits as soon as possible.

As a part of this, Solar on Land ('Zon op Land') was successfully launched in 2022 as an online platform (called 'Denk mee!' ('Think Along!')) where citizens can register and participate in renewable energy generation projects as well as express their opinions about the proposals, design and construction of forthcoming solar parks in the region. The 'Denk mee!' platform is also used for democratic voting (e.g., concerning the potential locations of solar farms in the region); 'the basic principle is that everyone is allowed to participate – without

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types

Do their bit

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Make their voice heard

Reformative outcome / Public agency

restrictions.' Until recently, several initiatives have been developed in the region, the largest being the solar park Kijfhoek (with 91,245 panels) in the municipality of Zwijndrecht, which provides over 22,000 households with green electricity and contributes up to 0.031TWh (towards the overall target of 0.37TWh) of renewable energy generation by 2030.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types

Do their bit

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Make their voice heard

Reformative outcome / Public agency

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The aspects of energy citizenship

Drechtsteden Energy promotes citizen participation via the use of public consultations, an online platform, and financial participation. The RES 1.0 was also made with significant citizen input and citizens can respond to the area selections for renewable energy generation. **However, the democratic energy future envisioned by the cooperative appears to be limited.** It does not seem to be a core concern because the organisation does not appear to put the energy system in citizens' hands but rather includes them in the process.

Citizens participated in drafting the RES 1.0, but in general, they do not participate in internal decision-making. Decision-making regarding the implementation of its aims is done primarily by the seven collaborating municipalities. Together, they map the opportunities, capacities and resources that are available. **Citizens' input does not appear to be compulsory in the decision-making process, although it does appear to be meaningful.**

Citizen control

Citizens can express their views, but their views are not necessarily taken into account

Democratic energy future

Energy democracy is considered as a positive value, but it remains limited to formal energy democracy

FOCUS ON DISADVANTAGED GROUPS

Anyone from Drechtsteden Energy can participate in the online platform and in public meetings regarding the renewable energy projects. **The organization is striving for an energy transition in which the benefits and burdens are distributed fairly and no one is left behind.** They have taken more than a year to draw up a policy and undertake an intensive participation process for involving residents, entrepreneurs, social organisations and governments in this issue.

**Equity and justice
Involvement is fully open**

It is described in the summary of RES 1.0 that 'If global warming exceeds 1.5 degrees Celsius, irreversible damage will be done to Earth's ecosystems. To keep the earth liveable for future generations, it is therefore important to stabilize the climate as quickly as possible'. **The goals are tied to the explicit recognition of the ecological limits of atmospheric carbon emissions and the carbon footprint of the region,** as the former was developed as a result of the Dutch Climate Agreement and the national carbon emission targets for 2030.

Carbon limit

Explicit recognition of the carbon limit

The Drechtsteden Energy cooperative refers to the Dutch Climate Agreement and the environmental reasoning which justifies the required energy transition (e.g., regarding natural gas and global warming). **In their code of conduct, they say that no irreversible development will take place and no pollution or waste will be left.** The ecological value of nature reserves is also acknowledged in the selection of areas for solar fields 'in order to protect the natural values [that are] present'.

**Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability is a core issue, and is considered in goal setting**

Further information

twitter.com/SmartDeltaDS

[linkedin.com/company/smarddeltadrechtsteden](https://www.linkedin.com/company/smarddeltadrechtsteden)

www.drechtstedenenergie.nl

<https://www.smarddeltadrechtsteden.nl/home>

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Source of images

www.res-drechtsteden.nl/

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CLUSTER 4 CASES:

Name of case in English:	Country	Cluster
Energy Transition of City of Burgas: Going Smart and Sustainable	BG	4 / 1
Som Energia – Green Energy Cooperative	ES	4 / 1
Nagypáli, the renewable energy village	HU	4 / 1
Consultation: Shaping Our Electricity Future (EirGrid Public Consultation: Shaping Our Electricity Future)	IE	4 / 1
Installation of solar heat panels in multi-apartment building, complementary with energy efficiency improvement of the building	LV	4 / 1
Reindonk Energy	NL	4 / 1
Energy efficiency mission ULB	BE	4 / 2
Bike Evolution	BG	4 / 2
Student Energy Teams	BG	4 / 2
Couso ´s project	ES	4 / 2
Hauts-de-France Pass Renovation	FR	4 / 2
Association “City for people”	LV	4 / 2
OFF-GRID: Renewable energy DIY (DO IT YOURSELF) for rural development	LV	4 / 2

Energy Transition of City of Burgas: Going Smart and Sustainable

HOLISTIC

COLLECTIVE

URBAN

Summary

Fifteen years ago, the Bulgarian town of Burgas was highly energy inefficient, leading to very high energy costs for local authorities and citizens, as well as poor living conditions and environmental inequality. Today, it is a different story. Burgas is a smart, energy-efficient city that implements the most up-to-date energy approaches and measures, demonstrating local authorities' power to drive sustainable change.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

Investments in energy efficiency, renewable energy sources, electric vehicles, efficient street lighting, and smart management systems – implemented with the support of EU funds and state and private resources – have turned the city of Burgas into a smart and sustainable place to live. An important part of this transformation is due to the efforts of the Municipality to motivate citizens to participate in building retrofitting initiatives funded by various programmes.

Goals

1. Reducing energy consumption and its respective costs for the municipality and its citizens;
2. Increasing the use of RES and energy-efficient materials, investment in energy efficiency;
3. Alleviating energy poverty and sustainable improvement of living conditions.

The story and the typology

Since 2007, energy efficiency has been one of the priorities of the Municipality of Burgas. As a result, the entire population of Burgas Municipality (232,000 people) has directly or indirectly benefitted from this decision. Burgas municipality is leading the country when it comes to energy-efficient living, with more than 200 multi-apartment residential buildings retrofitted under the National EE Programme, and the number of hybrid and e-vehicles in the city is constantly rising.

The energy transition of the Municipality of Burgas has not undergone any radical changes since it started, so there is no change in the ideal type of energy citizenship enabled by the case. The municipality initiated the programme Going Smart and Sustainable. Thus, it began with a high degree of professionalisation and sufficient resources (see details below).

Type 7: Do their share

Reformative outcome /
Collective agency

Type 7: Do their share

Reformative outcome /
Collective agency

Type 7: Do their share

Reformative outcome /
Collective agency

2007

Type 9: Do the job

2008

Type 1: Do their bit

Type 9: Do the job

2014

Type 1: Do their bit

Type 9: Do the job

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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Phase 1: Start of the programme, 2007-2008

In 2007, the energy transition activities of Burgas began operating under the Operational Programme "Regional Development" and the national "Demonstration project for renovation of multi-family buildings".

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Do the job

Reformative outcome / Social movement agency

Phase 2: Broadening of the scope, 2008-2013

In the second phase, the scope of the case broadened: more buildings were audited and approved for renovation, infrastructure and mobility became priorities, and the business potential of the energy transition (investment in materials and human resources, administrative and technical positions, etc.) was considered. Due to the broadening of the case, energy citizenship evolved into a more fundamental component: residents organised themselves into associations to participate in the renovations, public discussions were organised, and the circulation of relevant information increased. However, citizens remained largely inactive participants in the energy system, and their agency in decision-making processes did not increase significantly. Residents' associations

acted and communicated with the municipal authorities on their behalf. Very little citizen involvement was required outside of forming an association of residents.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types:

Do the job

Reformative outcome / Social movement agency

Do their share

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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Phase 3: Concluding stage, 2014-2020

The main structure of the case remained the same. The municipality cultivated measures pertaining to energy efficiency, many of which were supported by national and European programmes, and citizens benefitted. The retrofitting programme is reported to have decreased residents' energy bills by up to 30%. The programme concluded in 2020.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their share

Reformative outcome // Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types:

Do the job

Reformative outcome / Social movement agency

Do their share

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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The aspects of energy citizenship

Citizens were invited to participate in discussions before each investment. Public discussions were regularly held in administrative buildings, and citizens could obtain the respective details through local news outlets and social media. **Public opinion was then studied and taken into account. However, citizens did not comprise the most influential stakeholder group.** Decisions on a local level were taken by local authorities. Thus, involving citizens' voices was not regarded as compulsory in this case.

Citizen control
Citizens can express their views, but their views are not necessarily taken into account

The case's focus was not specifically on environmental limits, however, the reduction of carbon consumption and emissions were prioritized, and the expected results of the retrofitting initiatives according to the municipality's documents amount to the prevention of over 640 tons of carbon emissions per year. No overall assessment has been made, but some of the municipality's **records of renovations of public buildings include details of the expected or achieved amount of emissions that were prevented.**

Carbon limit
Explicit recognition of the carbon limit

The case seeks to alleviate energy poverty and increase the participation of citizens through inclusive measures and distribution of knowledge and information. However, **citizens in this case did not become active participants in the energy system, nor did their agency in decision-making processes increase significantly.**

Democratic energy future
Energy democracy is considered a positive value, but it remains limited to formal energy democracy

FOCUS ON DISADVANTAGED GROUPS

Equity, transparency and informed involvement became core pillars of the case. **Inclusivity and the representation of different stakeholders are priorities in the achievement of energy efficiency.** This is displayed through the public discussions held prior to the implementation of investments, the study of public opinion, facilitating discussion, and the creation of administrative units in various neighbourhoods across the municipality, with which citizens could consult concerning the renovation and retrofitting of their housing.

Equity and justice
Involvement is fully open

The focus of the case itself was not on mitigating the effects of climate change, but rather increasing efficiency and reducing energy-related costs. No assessment has been made by the case organizers of the impact of the reduction of fossil fuels or the mitigation of pollution.

Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability is part of the process, energy remains the main focus

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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Further information

facebook.com/Burgas.Municipality

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Som Energia – Green Energy Cooperative

Summary

Som Energia is a non-profit green energy consumer cooperative. Its main activities are the marketing and production of energy from renewable sources. Som Energia is committed to driving a change in the current energy model to ensure the use of 100% renewable sources.

Som Energia was created due to the increasing need for purchasing electricity derived from renewable sources, but this was impossible in Spain in 2010. Thus, in the same year, Som Energia arose as a citizen participation project, whose *raison d'être* was to bring about a change in the energy model, to create a cooperative and to put energy in the hands of citizens.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

It is a clear example of a citizen initiative for energy sustainability and democracy. Over the years, Som Energia has been growing and diversifying its operations; the activities carried out are numerous, although it maintains the essence of its social innovation model based on the non-profit consumption of green energy.

DIRECT ENERGY PRODUCTION / CONSUMPTION

COLLECTIVE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Goals

1. Promoting a 100% renewable, efficient and citizen-owned energy model;
2. Favouring the growth of a more social and solidarity-based economy;
3. Participating in a transformative social movement.

The story and the typology

Som Energia is Spain's first national energy cooperative, so it is a pioneering case in the country. Moreover, it serves as a reference and example for other European cooperatives. Since its foundation in 2010, Som Energia has achieved significant citizen participation through its local groups and, at the same time, incorporated more transformative objectives.

For the summary
methodology,
click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Phase 1: Creation of the case, 2010 - 2012

Som Energia started as an initiative proposed by Gijsbert Huijink, who wanted to install solar panels at home. To do this, he asked friends and colleagues to organise and create the cooperative. Therefore, it is primarily a participatory citizenship project since it involves a group of people, but it also has an individual component since it originates from an individual and affects people who install solar panels at home individually. The initiative began as a campaign for citizen participation to transform the non-sustainable energy model. It started as a citizen-based participative project that enabled both individual and collective agency.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Do their bit (in the household)

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Phase 2: Creating multiple local groups, 2012 - 2022

Several other local groups were created as decentralised forms of government that allowed the initiative to be self-managed from different parts of the country, thus increasing the number of people who could be involved. Therefore, citizen-based collective agency was maintained, and organisationally integrated individual agency was incorporated.

A change came with the introduction of local groups, which allowed citizens to take part in the initiative more directly.

Som Energia has experienced rapid growth in recent years. As reported by the European Environment Agency (2022), between 2018 and 2021, the cooperative almost doubled its electricity sales. Creating a "kWh Generation" financing scheme¹ has enabled the cooperative to initiate projects with financial conditions that would not be profitable for a traditional business but are sufficient for the community.

Som Energia's operations are not limited to installing its own plants, but it also aims to promote other local energy cooperatives by advising them and becoming partners.

It has expanded throughout Spanish territory by creating local groups, thus incorporating organizationally embedded individual agency.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Do their bit (within organizations)

Reformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Secondary type: Do the job

Reformative outcome / Social movements agency

¹ Generation kWh is an innovative contribution model based on energy returns rather than financial returns. It is a way for the cooperative to obtain financing for the construction and start-up of renewable energy production plants.

Phase 3: Current state, 2022 -

The cooperative has started to build momentum at the national level. It has started becoming involved in public debates (e.g., an appearance in the Senate) to talk about the challenges of the energy transition in Spain. Som Energia has begun to act in the public sphere, participating in debates on energy transition that affect the country. New contacts have been established with different political parties and central and regional governments to convey Som Energia's vision of the energy transition. Moreover, all these meetings have been requested by the other parties, not Som Energia. Slowly, it is beginning to have a voice in the broader energy system, thereby also becoming a social movement.

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Do the job

Reformative outcome / Social movements agency

GRUPOS LOCALES

GRUPOS LOCALES QUE IMPULSAN UNA COMPRA COLECTIVA EN 2021 **40**

- | | | |
|-----------------------|--------------|------------------|
| Alacant | Extremadura | Osona |
| Almería | Garraf | Ripollès |
| Alt Penedès | Girona | Rubí |
| Anoia | Granada | Sabadell |
| Bages | La Manchuela | Sant Cugat |
| Baix Llobregat | La Palma | Selva Marítima |
| Baix Montseny | Lleida | Sevilla |
| Baix Penedès | Los Alcores | Tenerife |
| Baix Vallès | Madrid | Terres de l'Ebre |
| Barcelona | Málaga | Terrassa |
| Berguedà | Mallorca | Valencia |
| Castellar del Vallès | Maresme | Zaragoza |
| Energia Gara Nafarroa | Menorca | |
| Eivissa | Moianès | |

GRUPOS LOCALES QUE IMPULSAN UNA COMUNIDAD ENERGÉTICA EN 2021 **9**

- | | |
|-----------------------|------------------|
| Barcelona | Lleida |
| Castelló | Sabadell |
| Energia Gara Nafarroa | Sevilla |
| Granada | Sierra de Huelva |
| La Palma | |

NUEVOS GRUPOS LOCALES 2021 **2**

- | | |
|--------------|---------|
| La Manchuela | Moianès |
|--------------|---------|

TOTAL DE GRUPOS LOCALES **57**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

The aspects of energy citizenship

Som Energia believes that as energy is central to our society, **citizens should be able to decide on how it is produced** and if they want more sustainable management methods to be implemented.

Som Energia's relation to the democratization of the energy system has been used as an example in essays and reports related to the social and solidarity economy, as well as prosumerism.

Democratic energy future

A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

Som Energia is a cooperative with clear horizontal organization, in which "all members have their degree of autonomy in making their own decisions", and where a management team – which coordinates different decisions – contributes to self-management. The only limit to autonomy derives from the different regulations.

To participate in internal governance and decision-making, citizens must be a member of the coop. **The Statutes recognize several rights of members.**

Citizen control

Citizens can express their views, but their views are not necessarily taken into account

The cooperative questions the sustainability of the current energy model based on the use of fossil fuels. They also act as intermediaries for other institutions that are partners of Som Energia in achieving this goal. They provide partners with an Infoenergía service aimed at improving their understanding of energy use and accompanying them in their journey to improve energy efficiency and make economic savings. Their mission is also to convey a message about the need to minimize energy use and production.

Carbon limit

Implicit recognition of the carbon limit

Som Energia invites any individual, company or public body that shares their values to be part of the cooperative. Its Statutes establish the obligation to make a minimum contribution to share capital (100 euros/member) to become a member. Further, the General Assembly has introduced the possibility of making a voluntary donation (0.01 €/kWh used), part of which is used for activities related to reducing energy poverty and advising people in need of this. It also incorporates a concern for equity in its Code of Ethics, advocating the use of a close, human, and transparent model.

Equity and justice

Equal access is granted, but limited by various criteria

Som Energía's Code of Ethics establishes – as one of the main values guiding the achievement of the organization's objectives – "environmental, but also social and economic sustainability". They do this through producing energy using renewable sources and marketing energy certified as 100% renewable, although their mission is also to convey a message about the need to minimize energy use and production.

Environmental sustainability

Environmental sustainability is a core issue, and is considered in goal setting

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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Further information

facebook.com/somenergia

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Nagypáli, the renewable energy village

Summary

The Green Road Village Development Program started in 1997 in Nagypáli, the main goal of which was to develop the village into a European-standard, self-sustaining settlement yet preserve the traditions of the villages of Western Hungary. The main directions of development were using renewable energy sources, developing tourism, building a community, environmental protection and awareness raising, and producing local products. In 2007, they opened the Renewable Energy Innovation Eco Centre, which serves as a promotional centre at which temporary exhibitions, conferences and workshops are organised on the use and implementation of biomass, biogas, solar and wind energy, and energy plantations.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

The village is an outstanding example in Hungary of how far determination and a strong community can take you regarding the use of renewable energy on a settlement level. It also proves that one does not have to wait for national level decision-makers to make such changes – you can do it for yourself, at the municipal and community level, and become self-sufficient.

HOLISTIC

COLLECTIVE

RURAL

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Goals

1. Being self-sustaining (in relation to energy and using renewables);
2. Producing and using renewable energy to reduce dependence on fossil fuels (phasing out fossil fuels/reducing carbon footprint/settlement-level energy transition);
3. Supporting, promoting and enabling prosumerism.

The story and the typology

Within two decades, a sustainable, liveable, and well-functioning settlement was established with all kinds of renewable energy use: a biosolar heating plant, solar collectors and solar panel farms (with minimal municipal overhead costs), e-mobility (bikes and cars) powered by solar panels, energy plantations, etc. The main characteristics of the case have not changed much over time. How the initiative operates seems sufficient, and the participants are satisfied. Therefore, no significant changes are planned except for further technological advancement. The energy citizenship ideal type and agency of the case has remained the same throughout its history and reflects the fact that Nagypáli is a pioneer in its region.

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Phase 1: Creation, focus on energy efficiency, 1997 - 2000

This case has quite a long history of ca. 25 years. It started when an innovative and ambitious mayor began work in the village (he was elected mayor in 1996). Back then, Nagypáli was a settlement in the Hungarian countryside in danger of extinction, lacking an attractive profile for residents or businesses. Based on his personal interests and skills, the mayor created a development plan called “Green Road” involving many ideas for development, most of them related to renewable energy.

Phase 2: Planning, 2000 - 2003

The Green Road development plan had three leading solutions (pillars) for addressing existing problems in the village. First, it included increasing the number of residents and building a community among them. Then, the plan suggested focusing on policymaking and different types of economic development (energy, tourism, enterprises, and real estate). Finally, the Green Road plans, together with the mayor and his ideas, gained more and more supporters locally and started to succeed step by step.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Do it their way

Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Do it their way

Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Phase 3: Realization of the plans, 2003 - 2015

After the planning phase, the mayor remained the village's leading actor, but many people are developing related ideas. The case has achieved a lot since its initiation – e.g., significant investment into renewable energy, booming resident numbers, a stronger community, a blooming business environment and an increase in tourism – and it is still a case in progress with many ambitious plans. Problems are approached as challenges and new opportunities, so innovation is ongoing. As a result, the village is becoming increasingly independent from an energy perspective. The case has achieved the milestones defined in the development plan under the firm control of the mayor as manager, but

locals and their ideas are also incorporated into the plans.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types:

Do their bit

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Do their own

Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Do it their way

Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Phase 4: Preservation of results and stability, 2015 -

The village considers itself a pioneer and intends to be on the front line in adopting new technologies. Although many project elements have been successfully implemented, the initiators continuously experiment and plan to pilot new and innovative practices to maintain their leading role. The village has received various prizes and attracts visits to the site. Requests for reports (interviews, documentaries, theses, etc.) are received regularly. The latest plans include building a biogas plant and turning an old water tower into a lookout tower with a wind turbine to generate electricity.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types:

Do their bit

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Do their own

Transformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Do it their way

Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

The aspects of energy citizenship

The municipality tries to involve the public from the very beginning of the development planning process by giving them the opportunity to express their ideas, problems and suggestions on different forums and platforms. They are fully involved in the implementation process and are typically partners in various activities aimed at promoting environmental awareness.

Although the inhabitants' views are listened to, the **mayor's word is ultimately the main factor in making decisions.**

Participants explicitly **aim at creating a self-sustaining village and being prosumers** within it, not being dependent on the regular energy system, thus a more democratic system is clearly envisioned. They (particularly the mayor) always look for innovation, newer technological solutions, and ways of changing old systems.

Democratic energy future

A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

Citizen power/control
Citizens can express their views, but their views are not necessarily taken into account

Reducing emissions is a main motivator and is addressed through various renewable energy projects, but "limits", "targets", "footprint" and staying within a **specific carbon limit/budget are not explicitly mentioned** in official publications.

Carbon limit
Implicit recognition of the carbon limit

Those living in the settlement can enjoy the advantages of the innovations, and take part in the projects and the community. However, due to the nature of the case, others do not benefit from it other than by being inspired and learning from this example.

Equity and justice

Equal access is granted, but limited by various criteria

Sustainability and environmental protection are the basis for all developments. The mayor personally **sees the future as sustainable living** and the village represents this to its residents. This is not only visible in the **predominant renewable energy practices**, but in many other practices such as forbidding the use of salt on icy/snowy pavements (but instead encouraging residents to use metal-free ash or sawdust) and not allowing open fires, except for on specified days.

Environmental sustainability

Environmental sustainability is a core issue, and is considered in goal setting

Further information

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EirGrid Public Consultation: Shaping Our Electricity Future

Summary

EirGrid, the state-owned electric power transmission operator in Ireland, has been tasked by the Irish government with preparing the electricity grid in anticipation of 80% of Ireland’s electricity coming from renewable sources by 2030, as envisioned in the Government's Climate Action Plan (2019). Addressing this challenge has been outlined in the ' Shaping Our Electricity Future' strategy, which presented four different approaches to grid development. Due to the high level of impact and transformative nature of this transition, EirGrid implemented a nationwide consultation process in the form of several online workshops and an online consultation platform to improve engagement with the public and all stakeholders.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

The case involves energy citizenship as the consultation process run by EirGrid allowed individual citizens to voice their opinions and views on grid development as a key energy topic. Although not formally compulsory, the results of the consultation process have been taken into account in planning the development of the grid.

DIRECT ENERGY PRODUCTION / CONSUMPTION

INDIVIDUAL

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

OLLESCOIL NA GAILLIMHE UNIVERSITY OF GALWAY

gr²Independent Institute

Goals

1. Understanding stakeholders', including citizens' and communities', views on and preferences for four approaches developed by EirGrid concerning how to develop Ireland's grid to meet the 2030 clean electricity target.
2. Understanding what influences these views, including the underlying assumptions, risk profiles associated with the proposals, and trade-offs in stakeholder preferences.

The engagement activities were designed to answer four key research questions:

- What do stakeholders think about the proposals for each workstream?
- Which proposals do they prefer, and why?
- What is the conditionality of their views?
- What values, motivators, and messaging influence their views, and how?

The story and the typology

As part of the Shaping our Electricity future, the consultation process was conducted in 2021, after having been prepared by EirGrid since 2020. During this time, there were no fundamental changes to the chosen approach. As the initiative was started within the organisation, it first took the form of organisationally embedded energy citizenship. As the emphasis shifted to consulting and involving citizens, the agency became public.

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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Phase 1: Preparation of the consultation, 2020

This first phase in the preparation of the consultation was characterised by intensive reflection on the design of the process. A key aspect of this was collaboration with several partner organisations (e.g., Irish Rural Link, National Youth Council) to obtain external expert knowledge and ensure that the different consultation events could be implemented with sufficient independence.

The main form of energy citizenship in this phase can be understood as organisationally embedded within EirGrid itself (as reflected in the main ideal type, type 3), expressed by the engagement of persons within EirGrid who advocated to expand

and consequentially implement meaningful citizen engagement. This fostered a shift in attitude within the organisation of EirGrid towards more openness to input from public consultations.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their bit (within hybrid organisations)

Reformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Phase 2: Implementation of the project, 2021

In the implementation phase, EirGrid partnered with several organisations over a period of 14 weeks, including:

- engaging over 30 local authorities;
- holding six rural community workshops (with over 300 attendees);
- holding a national youth assembly and seven regional youth events, in addition to...
- two national civil society forums;
- a deliberative dialogue/citizens assembly in Ireland, and
- a youth event with TEDxStormont in Northern Ireland.
- In addition, they received over 500 submissions through an online platform.

Gathering this feedback was done at an unprecedented scale and was the largest public consultation and engagement programme undertaken in this sector in Ireland.

The main form of energy citizenship agency associated with this second phase is classified as individual public, as expressed by citizens participating in the various consultation formats.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Make their voice heard

Reformative outcome / Public agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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Phase 3: Follow up, 2022-2023

According to EirGrid, the consultation proved successful as they were exposed to broad perspectives and views from society and industry that helped clarify a way forward. This fed into the development of the Shaping Our Energy Future Roadmap.

In response to key feedback from the consultation, EirGrid has made greater recognition of the role of communities and sustaining post-project participation integral elements of the roadmap.

To continue this involvement, EirGrid has organised a series of energy citizen roadshows to inform local

communities and citizens about the roadmap as an outcome of the consultation.

The ideal type of energy citizenship has not changed during this phase.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Make their voice heard
Reformative outcome / Public agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

OILSCOIL NA GAILLIMHE
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The aspects of energy citizenship

External experts have shaped the consultation process, e.g., by highlighting the role of energy communities. Participants in the consultation emphasised that **they would like more engagement beyond this particular project and generally more public involvement in key decision-making about Ireland’s energy future.**

Although participation in the consultation was only on “invited” basis, **it was a key concern to increase the voice of citizens, communities and other stakeholders.** Significant consideration went into ensuring that citizen participation was widespread, and had meaningful impact. This included partnering with external actors, both in the presentation of viewpoints and in the organisation of consultations with a variety of stakeholder groups.

 Democratic energy future
Energy democracy is considered as a positive value, but it remains limited to formal energy democracy

Citizen power/control
Citizens can express their views, but their views are not necessarily taken into account

EirGrid paid significant attention to making the consultation open and accessible. **Anybody could participate through the online consultation platform, with no barriers.** Widespread inclusion was promoted by 1) collaborating with the National Adult Literacy Agency to ensure that language was accessible to all audiences, 2) partnering with Irish Rural Link to ensure the representation of rural communities and with the National Youth Council of Ireland to ensure the representation of young people.

The background of the consultation process involved considering how EirGrid should approach the development of the grid so that the Government’s Climate Action Plan could best be implemented. **This includes meeting the target of net zero carbon emissions by 2050.**

 Equity and justice
Involvement is fully open

Carbon limit
Explicit recognition with mention/objective of reaching the max. carbon footprint

Due to the focus on the electricity grid development, environmental sustainability was not a major focus. **No indicator was used to represent environmental sustainability in the characterisation of the four scenarios used as a basis for the consultation process.** In the rural community workshops, attendees remarked on environmental issues related to windfarms, which were portrayed as disastrous for the bird population in some regions.

 Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability issues are not explicitly taken into account

Further information

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Installation of solar heat panels in multi-apartment buildings

Summary

Energy efficiency improvements in apartment buildings can be complemented by installing local RES technologies. The decision to do this has to be made by the formally established community of apartment owners of the particular building. ERDF financed the complex financial instrument provided by the Latvian state-owned development finance institution ALTUM. When using this instrument, most apartment buildings only implemented energy efficiency improvements. Only a few apartment buildings took advantage of the additional option to install zero-emission solar heat panels. One such case is 18 Riga Street in the town of Valmiera, Latvia.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

The case (1) is an example of prosumerism in a district heating network, (2) shows that apartment owners can cooperate to create shared energy-related benefits due to energy savings, and (3) highlights how a few communities of apartment owners have been able to go further than making “classical, traditional” energy efficiency improvements to a building.

DIRECT ENERGY
PRODUCTION /
CONSUMPTION

URBAN

COLLECTIVE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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Goals

1. Making energy savings and thus generating economic benefits for the owners of a Soviet-era multi-apartment building which had never been deeply renovated and was slowly degrading inside and outside.
2. Increasing the self-production of heat energy and local community ownership of a decentralised energy system. The inhabitants wanted to support energy self-production and self-sufficiency to counter energy poverty.
3. Promoting climate action – by reducing CO2 emissions.

The story and the typology

The project design and documents for preparing for installing solar heat panels in multi-apartment buildings started in 2013. This work was mainly done in partnership with the municipal property management company *Valmieras Namsaimnieks* (Valmiera Housing Management), which is a serving also for inhabitants of multi-apartment buildings, having contract with house, and then also choosing their services for related project design and management. The same company was later the main intermediary for all the processes associated with the building renovation stages, including management for European ERDF co-funding and remaining co-funding via contracting for inhabitants' loan from bank.

There were no fundamental changes until 2018 either related to outcome orientation (reformative/transformative goals) or the aims/objectives of the case. This is obvious considering that the case only concerns an initiative created by the community of apartment owners of a single multi-apartment building.

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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Phase 1: Setting up the case and installing the panels, 2013 - 2018

The first initiative was taken by two individuals (house inhabitants) who were elected by the community of apartment owners to their House Council and expressed their views about the unfavourable situation with the interior and exterior status of the shared dwelling. Joint discussions followed in the Council, led by those two initiators, particularly Nauris Kalniņš (chairman of the Council) and other flat owners. Finally, after several meetings, the community of apartment owners decided to go ahead with the project. This included insulating the external walls, foundations, basement and attic slabs; replacement of windows, doors and roofing; electrical installation in the basement, attic and stairwell; improvement of the ventilation system; reconstruction of the water supply and heating system, installation of lightning protection and repair of the stairwell. One speciality is that a solar heat collector system was also installed to provide hot water for the house.

The project proposal was dormant following 2013 as this particular multi-apartment building did not

Phase 2: In operation, present and future, 2019 -

After the refurbishment and the solar collector system were installed, the second phase started with energy savings and functioning. The building was submitted to the 2020 Latvian national competition “Latvia Energy efficient building” in the category “Energy efficient renovated multi-apartment building” and received the ALTUM affection award “For innovation”.

correspond to some of the general rules defined by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Latvia, specifically established for ERDF funding provisions. Only after those rules were amended did this building become eligible, too.

Following this, the project proposal was activated, and the related work was carried out in the second half of 2018 after all co-founding resources were successfully secured from the EU, from the bank loan for the building's residents and from the financial support from the municipality (through a grant system from the Valmiera city municipality).

	Individual			Collective	
Reformativo	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their bit (in the household)

Reformativo outcome / Private in the household agency

Secondary type: Do their share

Reformativo outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

	Individual			Collective	
Reformativo	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their bit (in the household)

Reformativo outcome / Private in the household agency

Secondary type: Do their share

Reformativo outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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The aspects of energy citizenship

The case shows how apartment owners in a shared building were able to decide on joint action that creates shared energy benefits due to energy savings and were able to go further than making the “traditional” energy efficiency improvements associated with buildings by complementing them with the installation of rooftop solar heating panels.

Decision-making by the community of apartment owners of building was consensual as majority decision-making occurred. The decision to renovate the building was made by the community of apartment owners through the democratic decision-making process prescribed by the relevant legislation.

Democratic energy future
Energy democracy is considered a positive value, but it remains limited to formal energy democracy

Citizen power/control
Citizens exert effective control, and their votes have to be taken into account

The case is limited to multi-apartment building-scale activity. At the same time, equal access is granted to all citizens potentially concerned – the owners of apartments.

Equity and justice
Equal access is granted, but limited by various criteria

The national co-funding requirement is to work towards reducing GHG emissions, thus the **goal of reducing CO₂ is mandatory**. Beneficiaries/the building inhabitants must evaluate CO₂ reductions during the project execution.

Carbon limit
Explicit recognition of the carbon limit

Energy and energy efficiency remain the focus. There is a good combination of energy efficiency improvements and energy self-production; however, environmental sustainability cannot be considered the core issue.

Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability is part of the process; energy remains the main focus

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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Reindonk Energy

DIRECT ENERGY
PRODUCTION /
CONSUMPTION

COLLECTIVE

PERI-URBAN

Summary

The mission of Reindonk Energy is to make the municipality of Horst aan de Maas energy neutral. Together with, for and by local residents, companies, authorities, and organisations from the local region, the initiative focuses on the sustainable energy transition. Reindonk Energy aims for local energy generation that contributes to resolving the global energy challenge. Because of its local character, it generates energy from renewable sources, aiming for sustainable energy, a clean environment and healthy air in the living environment. The initiative claims that “Because energy is a local product, energy is ours, and energy is cooperative”.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

This case focuses on producing and co-creating energy with the local community and the involvement of local stakeholders, including local businesses. It is an initiative together with, for and by inhabitants, companies, authorities and organisations that are committed to promoting a sustainable energy supply to create an energy-neutral Horst aan de Maas municipality. With local residents, they want to give shape to the energy transition.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Maastricht University

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Goals

1. Making the municipality of Horst aan de Maas sustainably energy neutral¹;
2. Promoting a democratic energy transition by involving as many local residents as possible in their renewable energy projects;
3. Providing energy for all and promoting social cohesion in the local area.

The story and the typology

Reindonk Energy is an energy cooperative located in the municipality of Horst aan de Maas in Limburg. Since its inception, the main goal has been to contribute to making the municipality of Horst aan de Maas energy neutral. As this is a citizen-based and hybrid initiative with a transformative focus, the main type of energy citizenship is classified as Type 8: Go ahead.

Case history summary

¹ While municipal energy neutrality means energy demand is met entirely by renewables, this does not mean all that energy is necessarily generated within municipal boundaries. As long as the power is generated from renewable sources (offshore wind turbines, for example), it still satisfies the definition.

Phase 1: From the creation of the case in 2015 until 2018

Reindonk Energy was founded in 2015 to give a voice to its members and to focus on social returns in addition to economic benefits.

The organisational structure has developed alongside its projects since its inception. The cooperative is formed by four different associations (sub-companies with separate legal entities for each project). These sub-companies give a focus to Reindonk Energy operations because each project is different in nature and needs a dedicated company behind it to organise it. This includes finances, project construction and site development and the

project development advice they provide. This organisational form of the cooperative has not changed over time.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Phase 2: Starting and building the solar panel farms since 2018

Reindonk Energy is already working in close collaboration with various commercial companies that, for example, help with the installation of solar panels. Since its inception, it has developed four projects: NEWRAIL, Zonneweide 't Veen Griendtsveen, Collectief ZonDelen 't Brugeind, and KODE Horst aan de Maas.

The Zonneweide 't Veen solar farm (with 4,000 solar panels) was the first to be launched in the former Griendtsveen sports complex and covers the electricity needs of the whole of Griendtsveen, making the village an energy producer. The solar farm includes an energy garden with a biodiverse design through the use of seed mixtures and hedges. The solar park not only provides electricity but is a meeting place with a picnic table, a place where people can charge their electric bikes and a scavenger hunt. Reindonk Energy has plans to employ people with disabilities in the future

(presently under construction) café. In collaboration with the municipality of Horst aan de Maas, construction started in 2018, and the installation of the solar panels will be completed in 2022.

In the memorandum of the Zonneweide 't Veen Griendtsveen solar park, it is stated that for Reindonk Energy, trust and, thus, the social acceptance of the solar farm play an important role. The reason for offering an investment opportunity to local residents, businesses and organisations is part of a more comprehensive participation plan.

The cooperative also works very closely with the municipality to promote a sustainable and cooperative energy transition. For example, the Policy Framework for Generation of Sustainable Energy (entitled: KODE – Kader Opwekking Duurzame Elektriciteit) has been developed in

consultation and close collaboration with Reindonk Energy.

In 2020, the cooperative reached an agreement with the municipality that the roofs of municipal buildings can be used to generate energy. The first project is the installation of 330 solar panels on the roof of the Sporthal 't Brugeind in Meerlo. With this project, Reindonk Energie is offering residents from the region the opportunity to generate energy locally – not on their own roofs, but on the roof of the sports hall. Residents can buy solar cells and thus benefit from green energy from their own region at an attractive price.

The cooperative is also participating in the NEWRAIL pilot project in Dronten (an initiative of ProRail – a commercial rail company and collaboration with other partners), which aims to build experience and

obtain greater insight into the technical possibilities and risks of using solar panels.² The project is experimenting with the installation of solar panels on noise barriers, with the first prototype installed in April 2022. This is a multi-year program designed to provide noise barriers with integrated solar panels.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

² Although this location will not be in the municipality of Horst aan de Maas, ProRail has asked Reindonk Energy to continue to participate in the project because of its experience and effort to date.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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The aspects of energy citizenship

Reindonk Energy claims that its mission is to work together with local residents to shape the energy transition in the municipality. The claim is made on its website that the organization is: 'Democratic, open and independent'. **It is stated that members have the right to think with and decide on the path ahead.** The organization regularly organizes member meetings to support this.

Democratic energy future

A more democratic energy future is a core concern of the case, and is part of the vision

Citizen control

Citizens can express their views, but their views are not necessarily taken into account

Any citizens can become involved who want to join the cooperative without any specific conditions. Reindonk Energy members pay an annual membership fee. All members can attend the member meetings and receive publications and newsletters. **A precondition is living in the region.**

Equity and justice

Equal access is granted, but limited by various criteria

Reindonk Energy aims to promote local energy generation that contributes to resolving the global energy challenge. Because of its local character, it generates energy from renewable sources and promotes sustainable energy, a clean environment and healthy air in the living environment. **Although the focus is on energy production, the initiative contributes greatly to the attempt to promote environmental sustainability.**

Environmental sustainability

Environmental sustainability is part of the process, energy remains the main focus

Carbon limits

Implicit recognition of the carbon limit

There is no mention or recognition of the 1.5C target or environmental limits in general. **However, by focusing on building a more sustainable, decentralised energy system based on renewable sources, the initiative implicitly contributes to reducing carbon emissions and promoting clean energy production.**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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Further information

[facebook.com/ReindonkEnergie](https://www.facebook.com/ReindonkEnergie)

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Energy efficiency mission ULB

Summary

The energy efficiency mission ULB (Université Libre de Bruxelles) has a short history of about four years. The specific energy efficiency mission started in 2019 to spur activities related to energy management, real-estate planning, technical services, and the overall organisation of the university, which all existed well before this.

This mission is associated with significant legacy issues: this is particularly clear in the building stock, which was developed when energy efficiency was not technically advanced – and when it was considered relatively unimportant.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

One of the three main achievements of the case is the specific focus on democratisation and the development of collective responsibility for the energy efficiency of the university.

DIRECT ENERGY PRODUCTION / CONSUMPTION

INDIVIDUAL

URBAN

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Goals

1. Reducing the environmental impact of energy consumption and production beyond climate goals to incorporate other resource and ecological-limit considerations.
2. Professionalising university activities in the field of environmental management, specifically energy management (e.g., making energy efficiency an integral part of building/real estate planning decisions).
3. Achieving more democratic energy decision-making at the university and promoting greater community ownership of a decentralised energy system.

The story and the typology

The motivation for this case is based on the individual energy citizenship activities of the current coordinator. The case was initiated at the university under his management. Thus, it started as an individual, organisationally embedded case. Afterwards, more and more people became involved, and the case gradually transformed into a collective, citizen-based energy citizenship type. The case is transformative in its aims, but for the time being, its actions tend to be of a reformatory type, thus not explicitly system-contesting.

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Phase 1: Workplace activism, 2019-2021

The coordinator of ULB's organisational mission was for many years an activist and an energy-conscious household member in parallel with his work. He had a transformative mindset whilst pursuing a rather pragmatic, step-by-step approach.

He engaged in activism within his workplace more widely and was not alone in this as others were also active – e.g., student organisations, activists and engaged researchers. Additionally, the university itself was developing a Climate Plan and initiated organisation-wide sustainability action. However, especially at the organisational level, official moves to promote sustainability action and energy citizenship were relatively reformatory and system-confirming in nature.

Phase 2: Institutional mission, 2021-2022

In 2021, the position of the coordinator became formalised into a paid one and expanded to incorporate another position. This organisationally embedded individual action generated a mandate and an explicitly collective mission (as indicated in the secondary individual type).

Throughout the evolution from individual to collective energy citizenship agency, the mission can be characterised as transformative, but it may appear reformatory from the outside. This is because even though the mission involves a conscious decision to deepen and broaden energy management activities at ULB from mere quick fixes and technical maintenance to a more ambitious form of energy management, in practice,

As this case involves organisational transformation, the energy citizenship ideal type is organisationally embedded. Although it is mainly reformatory in nature (Type 3), there are also transformative elements (Type 4), notably regarding the aim of making profound (if incremental) changes in organisational culture.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformatory	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their bit (within organizations)

Reformatory outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Secondary type: Do it their way (within organizations)

Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

implementation remains a matter of incremental organisational and institutional changes.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformatory	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their share"

Reformatory outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types:

Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Do it their way (within organizations)

Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

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Phase 3: Current state, 2022-

Now, the energy efficiency mission has become institutionalised in the organisation of ULB and, as such, extends to interactions with other organisations linked to the university (e.g., subcontractors who manage the real estate). It has taken some first, cautious steps towards implementing a somewhat more radical, fundamental strategy, i.e., activating ‘users’.

The coordinator of the case anticipates progressive shifts in organisational change and is more systematically considering energy/sustainability in important real-estate decisions. However, he has also observed that calling for behavioural change remains somewhat off-limits; user satisfaction and ensuring continuity remain the key principles driving the energy management system.

The current characterisation of the case is halfway between a reformative and a transformative outcome orientation, i.e., between Types 7 and 8, with the reformative nature dominating, and it is unlikely to change in the near future.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative 	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative 	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their share”

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary types:

Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Do it their way (within organisations)

Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

The aspects of energy citizenship

The pursuit of a more democratic energy future was not originally a main goal, in the sense that the mission was primarily set up for the sake of improving energy efficiency. On the other hand, **the initiative does involve the serious ambition of making energy efficiency a central concern for the university as an organisation, and accordingly, making it the subject of collective decision-making and conscious political choices.** In this sense, it was also a core concern, going clearly beyond merely formal changes.

The low level of involvement of the university community is a key concern in this case. **The coordinator of the mission considers it low, but he seeks to increase active, civic engagement in energy issues across the university.** In contrast, university authorities, technical services and some of the university community do not appear to consider 'effective citizen control' to be particularly low: channels have been set up through which people can express their voice, and there are policies in place that ensure the sufficient provision of energy services.

 Democratic energy future
Energy democracy is considered as a positive value, but it remains limited to formal energy democracy

Citizen control
Citizens' voices remain hardly heard or taken into account

The energy efficiency mission is, as its name states explicitly, focused on energy efficiency. **Equity and justice are perhaps less of an issue as the mission is implemented within a university – the population that is addressed is relatively homogeneous and consists of employees and students rather than citizens.** Issues of equity and justice do come up in the context of major renovations that are planned – e.g., university authorities are sensitive to the disturbance and emotional distress caused by this to particular groups, and related to specific uses.

 Equity and justice
Justice or equity are essentially out of scope or restricted to access to market

The mission is focused on energy efficiency, driven both by financial and environmental objectives. The latter are explicitly addressed in the mission, which is connected to the Climate Plan 2030 that ULB has drawn up. However, **carbon footprints and climate targets are acknowledged only implicitly for now.**

Carbon limit
Implicit recognition of the carbon limit

Environmental sustainability is a core issue; the mission revolves around the very challenge of operationalizing this. This means translating the general commitment of university to energy efficiency into concrete interventions, strategic management, systematic monitoring and evaluation, communication strategies, and human resource management that work towards this goal. **The mission involves the development of a holistic strategy.** Nevertheless, the coordinator feels that it could be more radical and have effects beyond the efficiency focus.

 Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability is a core issue, and is considered in goal setting

Further information

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Bike Evolution

Summary

Bike Evolution is a non-profit organisation registered in 2007. The objective is to promote cycling as a valid alternative to modern urban mobility. To achieve this, Bike Evolution organises events (in association with partners and friends), participates in working groups and other bodies set up by the municipality, and organises and hosts training and design workshops and many other activities to promote safe cycling. Bike Evolution represents its members in discussions with the municipality and other authorities related to urban mobility.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

Bike Evolution emerged as an initiative of a small group of enthusiasts who love to ride bicycles in the city and consider cycling the most convenient and sustainable way to move around – even in a city such as Sofia, which is completely car-dominated. Over the years, the initiative has evolved (as its name suggests) into a fairly professional non-governmental organisation.

MOBILITY

COLLECTIVE

URBAN

Goals

1. Promoting cycling as a more affordable, healthy and environmentally friendly alternative mode of transport;
2. Carrying out activities related to sustainable transport and representing cyclists, presenting their views and defending their interests and rights;
3. Providing a platform for developing and implementing ideas and working collectively to improve cycling conditions and culture in Sofia.

The story and the typology

Since the initiative was founded, there has been no significant change regarding the transformative/reformative aims. In contrast, the objectives have been narrowed down from the more general purpose of supporting and popularising cycling as an environmentally friendly and sustainable transport method to a clear focus on developing relevant legislation and proposing amendments to existing ones.

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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Phase 1: Creation of the case in 2007

During this phase, i.e., the establishment and the initial set-up of the case, the role of intermediaries was crucial (e.g. other NGOs providing support and know-how, donors providing start-up funding). Bike Evolution started as an informal community group and became an established and registered NGO with an Executive Board, Director and professional staff.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Phase 2: Early stage, 2008-2018

During this stage, the case was active in a wide variety of areas including the organisation of various events and activities to promote cycling and encourage more people to choose bicycles as their preferred transportation option, participation in working groups and other bodies set up by the municipality, the organisation of training and workshops, drafting of municipal plans and strategies for the development of cycling infrastructure.

The professionalisation came at the expense of size. In the initial years, between 150 and 200 people were considered to be active members and participated in the work in various capacities. Many members were active in one or more working

groups. The case had seven working groups: "Finance, Business and Projects", "Planning and Infrastructure", "Events Organisation", "NGO cooperation", "Institutions", "PR" and "ICT".

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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Phase 3: Mature phase, 2019-2022

In recent years, Bike Evolution has focused its efforts on planning and proposing legislative changes and providing expert commentary on the legislation that affects the interests of bikers. In this period, the case also ended/interrupted its relations with the current municipal administration.

With the drop in active membership over the years, the working groups were discontinued, and the remaining core of 15-20 individuals now plan and implement all the activities with the assistance of volunteers and interested citizens. For similar reasons (reduction in the number of active members), the number of Executive Board members was reduced from five to three. The agency has not

changed over time – since its establishment, Bike Evolution has been a non-governmental, not-for-profit association of citizens.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Phase 4: Current state, 2023-

There has been no change compared to the previous stage, but 2023 is an election year (national and local level), and the predictions are that after almost 20 years of status quo, there will be a change in the Sofia city government, which might restart the cooperation between the municipality and Bike Evolution. Thus, there may be more changes ahead in the longer term.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Secondary type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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The aspects of energy citizenship

The case focuses on mobility and therefore does not concern wider energy democracy as such, but rather **democratic participation and inclusiveness in issues pertaining to sustainable mobility in general and biking in particular**. The main democratic deficit Bike Evolution is attempting to overcome is the insufficient participation of citizens, experts and the civic society in the policymaking and decisions.

Bike Evolution is a membership-based association. Any citizen who shares the goals of the association and pays the annual membership fee can become a member. Decisions based on suggestions made by citizens become compulsory if confirmed and approved by the Board. However, it seems that this happens rather sporadically and is more the exception than the rule.

Citizen control

Citizens can express their views, but their views are not necessarily taken into account

Democratic energy future

Energy democracy is considered a positive value, but it remains limited to formal energy democracy

The activities of Bike Evolution are completely open to all citizens who want to get involved, and the initiative itself is an active and vocal defender of the rights of all cyclists, regardless of their age, gender and socioeconomic status.

Equity and justice

Equity and justice issues are not relevant/not addressed by goals

*There is no explicit mention of the ecological limit of atmospheric carbon emissions or sustainable carbon footprint. However, the representatives of the initiative persistently underline the **potential contribution of cycling to the reduction of carbon emissions** in Sofia. The case is strongly involved in activities to reduce the consumption and emission of carbon.*

Carbon limit

Implicit recognition of the carbon limit

Environmental sustainability

Environmental sustainability issues are not explicitly taken into account

*Environmental sustainability is not a core issue and is **rather seen as a desired and somewhat logical outcome of the main goal** – transport sustainability. The strategy and the measures are not holistic but focused only on the area of mobility.*

Further information

facebook.com/Veloevolucia

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velobg.org

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Source of images

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Student Energy Teams

Summary

Ten Bulgarian schools from three urban communities participated in an international consortium comprised of seven EU countries within the project Bridging European and Local Climate Action (BEACON). The in each school (aged 10-12), mentored by their science teachers, were the core actors in the project. They planned and implemented various science-backed activities to educate their peers, teachers, and parents on sustainable energy consumption and production. The Student Energy Teams achieved tangible results, reducing energy consumption in their schools and homes.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

The initiative is a great example of achieving bottom-up holistic civic engagement in sustainable energy consumption by students, teachers, and parents through a large EU project initiative. By making middle-school students the focus, the project managed to bridge and bring together schools, households, and municipalities around a common purpose.

**DIRECT ENERGY
PRODUCTION /
CONSUMPTION**

COLLECTIVE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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Goals

1. Enhancing international cooperation in climate action and achieving a shared vision for implementing the Paris Agreement;
2. Promoting and enabling climate action as well as energy saving;
3. Reducing the carbon footprint (individual, household, organisational, etc.).

The story and the typology

In the beginning, this case had more of a top-down approach, with teachers being the initiators and main monitoring actors. However, after a few years of the case being active, students became more independent in terms of implementation. They even got more responsibilities, e.g., teaching their younger schoolmates how to apply the skills required to save energy.

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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Phase 1: Creation and initial development of the case, 2017-2019

Initially, the case required intense collaboration between the students and the teachers to exchange information and instruct students on how to use the measuring equipment. After the students became familiar with the case's aims and the resources to implement them, they became more independent and proactive. They were given more room to take the initiative without depending too much on the teachers.

Teachers taught students how to save energy and monitor energy consumption at school by gaining knowledge and skills; then, students started

applying what they had learned about energy savings at home.

	Individual		Collective		
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their bit (within organisations)

Reformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Secondary types:

Do their bit (in the household)

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Phase 2: COVID years, 2020 - 2022

The COVID-19 pandemic resulted in schools closing, so the Student Energy Teams initiative was stopped. Although the teachers were unable to continue to organise the teams, the students themselves had the interest and desire to continue the case, teaching other students and motivating them to join the teams.

Students became more independent, started sharing knowledge with their peers and younger classmates, and showed them how to monitor energy consumption through out-of-class and online activities. Although the Student Energy Teams were not active at school, students continued to apply their skills at home and even taught their parents how to save energy. The

change happened as teachers started trusting the students and empowered them to take the initiative in their own hands and take action as a team, even without the supervision of the teachers.

	Individual		Collective		
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their bit (within organisations)

Reformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Secondary types:

Do their bit (in the household)

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Phase 3: Current state and future, 2023 -

Students are now back at school and have plans to start the Student Energy Teams again. Students who were part of the previous Energy Teams still measure energy consumption at school and pass on their knowledge to other children. A large quantity of informational material is available to all interested students. Students' energy interests have spilled over into other classes as well – for example, Bulgarian language and literature, where students wrote an essay entitled "Man's small steps for the future of the environment".

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their bit (within organisations)

Reformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Secondary types:

Do their bit (in the household)

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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The aspects of energy citizenship

All students had the right to propose activities, themes, etc. If a decision had to be taken, the students organized a discussion where everyone could argue to defend his/her opinion. The decisions were taken on a consensual basis. It has been an open and deliberative decision-making process, allowing everyone to express opinion and propose solutions.

Citizen control
No effective citizen power/control

The Student Energy Teams in Sofia have been supported by the EU project BEACON. The aim of the project is to contribute to the successful implementation of the Paris Agreement through the engagement of local actors – schools and other educational institutions. They can play a key role by reducing their own energy consumption but also educating future generations for a climate-friendly world. Also, **they can be pioneers and drivers of profound decarbonisation and social transformation processes** as their activities have considerable potential for increasing energy efficiency and avoiding the emission of greenhouse gases.

Carbon limit
Explicit recognition of the carbon limit

Energy democracy has not been referred to as among the main goals of the development of the Student Energy Teams and the BEACON project as a whole. The aim of the teams is more to raise awareness of the importance of mitigating climate change and taking action towards net-zero emissions but not explicitly through achieving energy democracy.

Democratic energy future
Energy democracy has not been among the goals

The Student Energy Teams involve pupils that take action to mitigate their carbon footprint at school and at home through energy saving. Equity and justice are not among the objectives of the initiative, but rather energy saving at school and at home through awareness raising.

Equity and justice
Justice or equity are essentially out of scope or restricted to access to market

Current environmental concerns and the need to address them through the school curriculum have been among the drivers for the creation of the Student Energy Teams. **Stimulating the environmental behaviour of pupils has been considered the area with the greatest potential for schools to advance the energy transition.** The students who are involved consider environmental sustainability as their motivation to participate in the energy teams. However, since the activities are undertaken by children, they are not sophisticated enough to involve the assessment indicators necessary for identifying “high” environmental sustainability.

Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability is part of the process; energy remains the main focus

Further information

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Couso´s project

Summary

O Couso is an integrated and open community where everyone operates according to the principle of ‘*Leave what you can; take what you need*’. The self-sufficient ecovillage has many permanent residents and hosts pilgrims doing the Camino de Santiago. They have adopted the principles of permaculture and managed to become self-sufficient energetically, reducing the workday and transforming work into a communal and shared activity. At the same time, they have started to operate as a ‘gift economy’.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

It is an energy citizenship case as the community pursues the goal of maintaining energy self-sufficiency, providing a refuge for ecological travellers and residents. The people who live in O Couso aim to promote the pedagogy that another world is possible – another way of doing things, consuming, based on ecology, alternative energies and in dialogue with nature.

HOLISTIC

COLLECTIVE

RURAL

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Goals

1. Rehabilitating the village of O Couso to turn it into a house of welcome for pilgrims on the Camino de Santiago according to the paradigm of the Gift ("Leave what you can; take what you need");
2. Creating a school of experience concerning the values of the New Ethical Culture, an 'international school of gifts and talents' where these values can be put into practice and serve as inspiration to the world;
3. Creating an integral and open community where people who feel inspired by these values (the gift economy and generosity) can live a complete life in a privileged place and environment;
4. Becoming self-sufficient in terms of energy and drinking water.

The story and the typology

The project is based on the principles of voluntary simplicity and austerity and argues that the current system and lifestyles are not sustainable. Hence, a paradigm shift with new values is necessary – the New Ethical Culture, intended to be taught through the 'international school of gifts and talents' and designed to create an open community inspired by the values of the gift economy and generosity.

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Phase 1: From the creation of the case in 2013 until 2023

Since its creation, there have been no changes in the type of collective agency that characterises O Couso. Over the years, however, there have been several changes related to the goals of the case. Some have to do with the adaptation to a new way of life in connection with nature and the lack of the means and tools of urban life. Others are related to improving the energy system and scaling up growth in the use of photovoltaic panels, which have been an essential element. In this sense, a large part of the control over consumption has been lost due to the lack of technological instruments that would

allow the community to learn about means of production and consumption within the community.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Phase 2: Current state and future, 2023 -

The creation of the shelter for pilgrims has been achieved, but the project members are currently undergoing a period of reflection as its implementation entailed great effort that members consider cannot be sustained over time. If this is not reconsidered, it could affect the survival of the community. The natural community approach is being reconsidered.

In the near future: The main conditioning factor will be overcoming the debts that have been incurred, which have reduced the shelter's opening time to the summer season only. The possibility of generating more energy that makes it possible to acquire electric means of mobility (an electric car, for example) may also favour the project's progress. In the longer-term future: changing the

consumption paradigm of visitors to the shelter. It is also considered important to maintain the motivation of the permanent members of the community, who experience significant attrition due to the living conditions and contact with visitors with different motivations, interests and expectations.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Go ahead

Transformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

The aspects of energy citizenship

Although it is not a main objective of the project, which is focused on creating a different way of living and relating to nature, members share the idea that **society must find different ways of participating in the debate and decision-making about everything related to energy generation and consumption**, especially with regard to the transition to using renewable energy sources.

Democratic energy future

Energy democracy is considered a positive value, but the vision does not really address it

All those involved in the initiative have a say in the decisions that are taken at O Couso, but as one of the members states, "We are not governed by democracy as usual, because as a shelter, where there is a high turnover of people, we could not adhere to the whims of each group, because if the group changes, the rules change and that is unfeasible." **Decision-making occurs through hierarchical consensus.**

FOCUS ON DISADVANTAGED GROUPS

O Couso defends the principles of equity and justice. One of the founders of the project states, "**We want to help people who, for some personal circumstances are going through a difficult time or social exclusion.** We have realized that many people who were living on the streets were coming here to try to rebuild their lives and people who had gone bankrupt financially and didn't know where to go. So, we decided to get completely involved with this just cause, to lend a hand as much as we could".

Citizen control

Citizens can express their views, but their views are not necessarily taken into account

**Equity and justice
Involvement is fully open**

Although the project is derived from the application of a set of principles and philosophy, there is no explicit recognition or mention of the ecological limits to carbon emissions.

Carbon limit

There is no recognition or mention of the carbon limit related to the case goals

The project aims to be self-sustainable from the production to the consumption of food, energy and everything related to day-to-day life. For example, participants feed themselves with seasonal products harvested in the garden; their mobility is as ecological as the landscape allows (bicycle, electric car, etc.); they consume spring water, produce their own photovoltaic energy and dispense with everything superfluous.

**Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability is part of the process; energy remains the main focus**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

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Further information

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Hauts-de-France Pass Renovation

Summary

Hauts-de-France Pass Renovation is a public service supporting technical and financial assistance for renovation created by the Hauts-de-France region. It is the first public operator to implement a third-party financing mechanism for energy renovation for individual and collective homeowners. The service provides an “all-in-one” solution, with technical assistance for homeowners from the first audit to post-work energy audits, together with an innovative and attractive financing model. It contributes to creating a market for energy renovation in the region and directly pays contractors to undertake the related renovation work, acting as an intermediary between homeowners and companies.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

The programme supports the uptake of energy renovation among homeowners by addressing key barriers with appropriate technical and financial assistance. It also supports the creation of a market for construction companies.

**DIRECT ENERGY
PRODUCTION /
CONSUMPTION**

COLLECTIVE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Goals

1. Boosting deep energy renovation for homeowners by providing tailored technical and financial assistance through all project stages;
2. Converting energy savings into financial resources for households, especially those with limited self-financing capacity, so that they can engage in deep energy renovation work;
3. Mobilising and supporting local employment in the building sector favours regional sustainable development with a deep renovation market that meets expectations of quality.

The story and the typology

Hauts-de-France Pass Renovation was initiated in 2019 due to a legal obligation for the region to have an energy efficiency scheme in place and strong political will to pilot third-party financing and support household access to renovation, thereby making its agency correspond to the energy citizenship practised at the organisational level, with transformative aims. In the five years prior to its launch, the scheme was piloted in the former Picardie region. Pass Renovation is governed by the Hauts-de-France region but functions as an independent organisation and supports energy citizenship at the household level by facilitating the energy retrofitting of homes.

Case history summary

For the summary methodology, click [HERE!](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Phase 1: Creation of the case in 2019

While the project was piloted in 2014, it was officially launched in 2019. In the beginning, the project emerged from a legal obligation, thus corresponding to the reformatory organisational energy citizenship type; however, the project was driven to go beyond this obligation by a strong political will to pilot third-party financing and support household access to renovation corresponding to the transformative organisational ENCI type. The unique offer of third-party financing by Pass Renovation and their integrated technical

and financial offering made the project a pioneer in this field from the get-go.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformatory	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do it their way

Transformative outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Secondary type: Do their bit (within organizations)

Reformatory outcome / Organisationally embedded agency

Phase 2: Post-creation until 2023 and beyond

Looking beyond the project's creation phase, Pass Renovation currently supports energy citizenship in the household that complies with the transition requirement of deep renovation. The case has not developed regarding its objective. However, its outcome orientation has become reformatory and more system-confirming as the solution offered by the case has become more widespread. In the future, minimal changes are planned. Pass

Renovation will focus on achieving its objectives in the years to come.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformatory	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way within organizations	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their bit (in the household)

Reformatory outcome / Private in the household agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

The aspects of energy citizenship

Citizens do not participate in internal decision-making in this case, per se. The case can be described as top-down. Hauts-de-France Pass Renovation is an independent public body operating under the Regional Public Service Energy Efficiency Board (SPEE), in turn governed by the regional government. All interaction with citizens benefiting from the scheme is governed by regulatory documents and leaves no room for participation in decision making by citizens.

This case does not explicitly focus on energy democracy. The programme, however, enables citizens to participate in the decarbonisation of the building stock through deep renovation. From that perspective, the activities of the programme could be considered key enablers of the democratization of the energy system as they address key issues such as a lack of information, technical assistance, and appropriate financial instruments for making energy renovation accessible to all, especially targeting disadvantaged households.

Democratic energy future

Energy democracy has not been among the goals

Citizen control
Citizens' voices remain hardly heard or taken into account

The initiative does not explicitly mention carbon footprints nor the goal of carbon neutrality before 2050, but it is involved in activities that reduce energy consumption (9% of renovations achieved more than 75% savings, 30% led to savings of between 25-50%, and 18% of renovations led to savings of up to 25%), thus reducing carbon emissions is an implicitly recognized objective.

Carbon limit
Implicit recognition of the carbon limit

FOCUS ON DISADVANTAGED GROUPS

Issues such as energy poverty and inclusivity are at the core of this case. Beneficiaries are mainly low to very low-income households (60%). The third-party financing scheme allows the programme to evaluate the repayment ability of households by taking energy savings into consideration regarding their creditworthiness (and thus exposure to the risk of energy poverty). This enables access to financing for households that may have difficulty accessing renovation-related loans from traditional banks.

Equity and justice
Involvement is fully open

Environmental sustainability is only superficially addressed through the leaflets about eco-friendly materials. Energy is the main focus of the scheme, but dedicated assessments are carried out through the energy-savings audits that are undertaken as the first step in the renovation process. The outcomes in terms of energy savings achieved after renovation are also assessed.

Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability is part of the process; energy remains the main focus

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101022492.

Further information

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Source of images

<https://www.pass-renovation.hautsdefrance.fr>

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Association “ City for people”

Summary

The association "City for People" was established in January 2016 to help create a good urban environment in Riga and other cities in Latvia. The team and supporters include specialists in various fields – programmers, architects, communication, and urban environment specialists. The goals of the association are to create people-oriented, high-quality public outdoor spaces where everyone is safe, to promote convenient and safe mobility opportunities in the city and beyond for everyone, regardless of age and health status, and to promote environmental protection.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

Sustainable mobility has a direct role in energy transition and reducing CO₂ emissions. The transition towards low-carbon energy systems is part of energy citizenship since conventional mobility planning approaches have changed toward sustainable smart mobility. This is aimed at guaranteeing the participation of all social groups and reducing the impacts of transport, such as energy consumption, CO₂ emissions, air quality, wasted space in the streets, and impacts on public health.

MOBILITY

URBAN

COLLECTIVE

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Goals

1. Promoting alternative modes of mobility and improving their safety
2. Improving urban air quality and reducing noise pollution
3. Increasing public awareness of mobility and urban sustainability

The story and the typology

The Association "City for People" was established in January 2016 to promote a good urban environment in Riga city. The team and over 100 voluntary members and supporters include specialists in various fields.

The case is categorised as a collective, citizen-based and hybrid "Do their share" ideal type. There were no changes in the classification of the energy citizenship ideal type in the period 2016-2023, i.e., during its operation, but in terms of organisational development, the case can be divided into three phases.

Case history summary

For the summary
methodology,
click [HERE!](#)

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Phase 1: Awareness raising activities, 2016-2018

The association “City for People” was launched in 2016 as a voluntary movement – the majority of contributions were voluntary and unpaid. The case started with initially fragmented informal awareness-raising activities. The aim was to raise public awareness about current unsustainable urban practices and planning. These activities took many forms: campaigns, petitions, street festivals and smaller technical solutions.

The association may be qualified as a Collective citizen-based and hybrid ENCI case, more precisely:

type 7 “Do their share”. Awareness-raising activities have been present throughout the history of the case.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Phase 2: Organisational development, 2019-2022

The case's organisational capacity increased after it received a grant (EEA and Norway grants) in 2022 to recruit staff and develop a website and communication strategy.

In this phase, the case grew from a few volunteers into a highly professional organisation with members with diverse educational and social backgrounds – all having a synergetic positive impact on the functioning of the whole.

Their professionalism is essential in ensuring the democratic functioning of the organisation, as the professional opinions (backed up with support from diverse areas of knowledge) are used to lobby for necessary improvements in the urban mobility system.

The case aimed to unite like-minded people through workshops, public debates, and local days – empowering local communities to tackle urban problems, find solutions and represent their needs to municipal decision-makers.

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

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Phase 3: Expansion of operational areas, 2023-

In the last phase, there has been an expansion in the areas of operation and the impact on local decision-making has increased. Participation in public hearings and consultation mechanisms has been strengthened, and broader public recognition and visibility have been achieved – the case has become a 'voice' for some areas of sustainable urban governance.

So far, the main achievements of the case are achieving organisational visibility and recognition in the public sector and among decision-makers at the

municipal level, as well as making practical improvements in the quality of public spaces and alternative mobility modes (cycling and walking).

	Individual			Collective	
 Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
 Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

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The aspects of energy citizenship

Citizens have the right to take part in decision-making by submitting their proposals to the municipal administration, which is obliged to consider them, though not act on them. Nevertheless, the number of citizens' actions adds weight to the importance awarded to problems, and this pressure should be followed up by the necessary reactions from the municipal council.

Citizen power/control
Citizens can express their views, but their views are not necessarily taken into account

Activities include awareness raising about available bicycle routes, control of the technical conditions of the city's bicycle paths and relevant proposals for improvements submitted to the city administration, including proposals for city re-planning and improvements with an eye on bicycle mobility. **The goal of reducing the carbon footprint is also indirectly articulated through activities that promote green public space.** Activities include campaigning against carparking and planning trees along streets.

Carbon limit
Implicit recognition of the carbon limit

Energy democracy is considered a positive value supported by the democratic participation of citizens. However, **the democratic energy future that is envisioned remains limited to formal energy democracy** (democratic procedures). A significant part of City for People activity is lobbying through participatory mechanisms based on compulsory requirements defined for municipalities by national legislation with respect to stakeholder involvement in decision-making.

Democratic energy future
Energy democracy is considered as a positive value, but the vision does not really address it

In this case there is a limited focus on goals of equity and justice. **It is indirectly intended that equal access to safe and diverse modes of mobility have to be available for anyone** regardless of social and geographical restrictions (with preference to environmentally friendly modes of travel). The issue of equity is relevant as economic income is related to social equity and this drives mobility choice.

Equity and justice
Equal access is granted, but limited by various criteria

One of the goals is improving urban air quality and reducing noise pollution. A contribution to environmental and climate goals is made in several ways: **by promoting better transport and alternative infrastructure that reduces transport-related pollution**, thus contributing to the city's air quality and emission reductions and climate goals.

Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability is part of the process, energy remains the main focus

Further information

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Source of images

facebook.com/PilsetaCilvekiem; www.pilsetacilvekiem.lv/

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Off-grid: renewable energy DIY for rural development

Summary

The objective of the project has been to collect and explore appropriate renewable energy technology solutions and develop physical prototypes and an open license manual to promote decentralised renewable energy generation opportunities. The project involved the installation and demonstration of alternative technologies on selected farms and practical workshops in which experts trained an interested rural audience on self-making and installing technologies such as solar heat and PV panels and other related equipment capable of generating energy as a part of energy-active rural houses.

Why is it a case of energy citizenship?

The case was initiated and implemented by LEADER local action groups (LAGs). The case defines itself as “A platform & community for smart solutions & ways to live with energy, a space where we share research, knowledge & experiences to deepen our common understanding. We do it for all of us and for [...] nature.” The case has provided relevant activities to close the gap in competences and skills for utilising and installing renewable energy solutions.

DIRECT ENERGY
PRODUCTION /
CONSUMPTION

RURAL

INDIVIDUAL

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Goals

1. Collecting and further exploring appropriate renewable energy technology solutions;
2. Developing physical prototypes for decentralised renewable energy generation;
3. Establishing an online platform where ideas, solutions and activities connected to the topic are spread to a broader community.

The story and the typology

The Off-Grid DIY Renewable Energy for Rural Development project was initiated to connect actors in the Baltic Sea region and create a platform where ideas, solutions and activities connected to the field of energy could be spread to a broader community. But the project, which started in 2018, has a transformative and individual type of agency, with a secondary collective agency as private households and groups of households were invited to participate.

Case history summary

For the summary
methodology,
click [HERE!](#)

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Phase 1: EU funds through LEADER, 2018 - 2020

The first phase of the OffGrid project was funded by EU funds through LEADER local action groups (LAGs), including four LAGs from Latvia.

The project started in 2018 with an individual type of agency: private households and groups of households were invited to implement concrete, practical measures in individual households/farms for small-scale energy solutions and larger installations. An example of the latter is the Trians-S modular house using solar panels. In Latvia, activities have been implemented in three locations, one of which is in a Natura2000 territory, the natural park “Pape”.

The initial goals were reformative and, as such, have remained so. However, if an increase in skills and awareness in society regarding self-energy production in the long term can lead to systemic

change and transformative innovation that increases energy independence, this could become a radical change.

The project was also initiated to connect actors in the Baltic Sea region, so it has a collective secondary ideal type.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their bit (in the household)

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Secondary type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

Phase 2: Since 2020

Since 2020, activities have been maintained, and the installed energy equipment is currently in operation and practical use.

It is worth noting that the DIY idea in Latvia is not a new practice; it has a legacy in the country’s past when resources were scarce, and many things had to be invented, produced and/or created at home by individuals. This applies to homemade equipment for producing energy from RES (wind, water, sun) for individual use or as an amateur activity.

As an ENCI case, the project was stable; the ideal type did not change over time.

	Individual			Collective	
Reformative	1. Do their bit (in the household)	3. Do their bit (within organizations)	5. Make their voice heard	7. Do their share	9. Do the job
Transformative	2. Do their own (in the household)	4. Do it their way (within organizations)	6. Make their vote count	8. Go ahead	10. Make their claims

Main type: Do their bit (in the household)

Reformative outcome / Private in the household agency

Secondary type: Do their share

Reformative outcome / Citizen-based and hybrid agency

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The aspects of energy citizenship

Members of the implementing organization (NGO, or LAG “Abulas Rural Partnership”, which is a collective decision-making mechanism according to its statutes), are involved in controlling the activities that are implemented by the organization. Democratically elected representatives vote when necessary. **This is a self-governance (bottom-up) case, thus the case exhibits quite strong elements of citizen control.**

Citizen power/control
Citizens can express their views, but their views are not necessarily taken into account

In public materials available about the case there are some references to sustainability and ecological limits. **The case involves activities designed to reduce carbon emissions by selecting alternative means of energy production.** This is mentioned (e.g., in the project poster, which refers to climate-related activities being significant for reducing CO₂ emissions).

Carbon limit
Explicit recognition of the carbon limit

However, the main profile of the case has not been related to any decision-making mechanisms or participatory activities, **but the character of the project (supporting a decentralised energy system) does have a democratising effect.**

Democratic energy future
Energy democracy is considered as a positive value, but the vision does not really address it

The project was not targeted at addressing energy equity; it was about demonstrating individual opportunities and technologies for generating energy. This is a case of a nature-protection-territory pilot, but it involves applying a rather holistic approach to nature protection in general, emphasizing the need to identify sustainable solutions for nature management. However, it **indirectly moves equality issues forward.**

Equity and justice
Justice or equity are essentially out of scope or restricted to access to market

Environmental sustainability issues are mainly seen as self-evident in respect to the use of renewable energy sources as an alternative to grid-produced energy. **Energy independence (in terms of producing energy) is mainly addressed in this case.** Organized training seminars for Microenergy production actors about pedal energy included some brief information about sustainability issues.

Environmental sustainability
Environmental sustainability is part of the process, energy remains the main focus

Further information

facebook.com/OffgridDIY/
youtube.com/@offgriddiy9658

www.off-grid.rocks
www.abulas.lv/lv/projekti/starptautiskais-projekts-off-grid-diy

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